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UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI BARI ALDO MORO

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

PNRR

Resilience

multi-Risk science for resilient communities under a changing climate

Multi risk models from assessment to validation and implication for decision making

BARI ^{JUNE} 2024

CAMPUS UNIVERSITARIO

19 JUNE ore 14:00 - 18:00
YOUNG DAY

Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra e Geoambientali
Aula 1

20 JUNE ore 14:00 - 18:00
SPOKE

14:00 - Saluti Istituzionali
14:30 - Sessione **VS1**
15:00 - Sessione **VS2**
15:30 - Sessione **VS3**
16:00 - *Coffee break*
16:30 - Sessione **VS4**
17:00 - Sessione **TS1**
17:30 - DISCUSSIONE
18:00 - Sessione POSTER
Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra e Geoambientali

21 JUNE ore 09:00 - 18:00
SPOKE

09:00 - Sessione TS2
09:30 - Sessione TS3
10:00 - Sessione DS
11:00 - DISCUSSIONE
11:30 - *Coffee break*
12:00 - Interazione spoke e ambasciatori
13:00 - *Buffet*

WORKSHOP

Multi risk models from assessment to validation and implication for decision making

14:30 - Interventi delle autorità
15:00 - Interventi dagli spoke e ospiti da altri progetti PNRR
18:00 - Sessione POSTER
Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra e Geoambientali

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MULTI RISK MODELS FROM ASSESSMENT TO VALIDATION AND IMPLICATION FOR DECISION MAKING

RETURN Dissemination Workshop

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VS1 ‘Water’

Development of an a-priori numerical indicator for the evaluation of the impact of diffusion and dispersion in water distribution systems

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Water quality modelling plays a significant role for detecting contamination in distribution networks (Piazza S. et al. (2023)). Current models ignore diffusion and dispersion, critical in low Reynolds number scenarios (Piazza S. et al. (2020)). These simplifications work for turbulent flows in short pipes but fail in laminar and transitional flows, common in low-flow situations, dead-end pipes, or service connections. Despite turbulent flows in main pipelines, diffusive-

dispersive processes become significant due to laminar flows in complex network areas, particularly at night. Advective simplification offers computational efficiency for large networks, yet a method to discern when this approach suffices or when diffusion is necessary is needed. The Péclet number has been widely used to determine when one-dimensional advective transport is reliable without compromising model accuracy (Abokifa A. A. et al. (2020)). A recent analysis conducted by the authors (Piazza S. et al. (2024)) extended the use of the Péclet number to two-dimensional advective-dispersive modelling, highlighting that it could not be used as a parameter to identify the dominance of the advective or dispersive process in real systems, as the latter cannot be neglected for long pipes, in any flow regime. For this reason, the present study aims to determine a new indicator that can effectively discriminate the dominance of the advective or dispersive process, to have a rapid decision-making tool capable of establishing a priori the behaviour of the distribution network, to use the numerical model more for water quality modelling.

Starting from the definition of the dimensionless Taylor time, the new indicator τ_{mod} was determined as the ratio between the product of the longitudinal dispersion coefficient E and the time with the travel time t_r , and the diameter of the pipe d , as reported in equation (1).

$$\tau_{mod}=(E \cdot t_r)/d^2 \quad (1)$$

The EPANET model, the one-dimensional (1D) advective-diffusive model (Shang F. et al. (2023)) and the new dynamic model proposed by the authors EPANET-DD (Dynamic-Dispersion) (Piazza S. et al. (2022)) were applied to a district of the Palermo water distribution network (Oreto-Stazione), contaminated with a soluble contaminant, and the Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) coefficient was evaluated in order to measure how well a simulation model predicts an outcome variable. It is observed that in correspondence with a threshold having an NSE efficiency equal to 0.9, values of the parameter τ_{mod} are identified such that below them the two models reproduce similar results in modelling the contaminant.

The results of this study have highlighted that by assuming a priori the efficiency/error that one wishes to obtain in the modelling of contaminants within a water distribution network, it is possible to discriminate values of this new indicator that allow distinguishing the dominance of dispersive processes compared to those advective ones.

Keywords: advective-dispersive-diffusive model, numerical indicator, water distribution network.

References:

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Towards event-based representation of design rainfall: a spatio-temporal framework

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Design rainfall is currently estimated based on univariate statistical analysis of rainfall intensity time series, with the single stations analyzed independently. Key variables for hydrological processes, such as the duration and spatial extension of the rainfall events, are accounted for based on basin characteristics, often with empirical laws, rather than using rainfall information.

In this work, a new framework for event-based representation of design rainfall is proposed, allowing to account for a larger set of rainfall event characteristics. Leveraging a dataset of rainfall height measurements at 268 stations in the Tuscany region, with a time resolution of 15 minutes, in the time period ranging from 1999 to 2020, a dataset of rainfall events

has been created, by testing different criteria for spatial and temporal aggregation and computing the resulting aggregate characteristics.

Spatial aggregation is based on a k-nearest neighbours criterium, accounting for the spatial density of the stations; the temporal aggregation criterium has been instead determined aiming to obtain time series of independent events at each station. Independent rainfall events are assumed to resemble a Poisson process, with exponentially distributed delays; with this assumption, several temporal aggregation criteria have been tested and evaluated with a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Different rainfall records from the same station have been assigned to the same event if the temporal aggregation criterium was satisfied; analogously, different rainfall records at the same instant have been assigned to the same event if the spatial aggregation criterium was satisfied. The resulting events were used to obtain related indicators such as rainfall intensity, volume, duration, spatial extension and dispersion, allowing to obtain multiple related probability distributions.

Keywords: rainfall events, event-based design rainfall.

VS2 ‘Ground Instabilities’

A new easy-to use tool for shallow landslides propagation assessment at basin scale

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Shallow landslides as debris flows, mud flows and debris avalanches are fast moving landslides involving the non-cohesive shallow material lying upon the bedrock, triggered by rainfall infiltration when the soil becomes saturated. This landslides typology typically originates from steep slopes, often in sparsely populated areas, and travel and/or flow downstream over considerable distances, with maximum velocity of several meters per second, affecting along the

path human settlements, roads, and critical infrastructures, widespread in the valley areas. Over the last decades, shallow landslides have taken on an important role among the natural phenomena impacting on territories: while urbanization has increased the exposure, climate changes have contributed to increasing their frequency and intensity.

The hazard maps for shallow landslides at basin or regional scale often provide solely information about events already occurred (inventory maps) and/or on potential source areas (initiation susceptibility maps). Despite the availability of several propagation assessment software, the runout maps providing an estimation of the propagation areas of potential shallow landslides at basin scale are very rare. Meeting the demand of public administration for straightforward tools to manage and guide regional planning, a new GIS tool was implemented based on the geometric approach (Moretti et al., under review). ShaLPA (Shallow Landslide Propagation Assessment) aims to contribute to bridging a gap in the shallow landslide hazard assessment process at basin/regional scale.

The methodological process aiming at estimating the potential runout distances based on geometric approach consists of two subsequent stages (Falconi et al., 2023):

1. Site-specific parameters assessment;
2. Runout assessment.

The identification of the site-specific runout parameters (step 1) requires the availability of a significant and digitalized database of landslides occurred in the study area. Instead, the application of the ShaLPA tool (step 2) requires a high resolution DTM and geotechnical data about soil thickness and unit weight. The implementation of the ShaLPA tool has been conducted using a simple function that expresses a strong correlation between the runout and the volume of the detached material (Legros, 2002): $L=aV^b$, where L is the runout distance (measured in 3D on the DTM), V is the volume of the detached material and a and b are the site-specific parameters. The computational framework of the ShaLPA GIS tool can be summed into five main steps: (i) source area features attribution, (ii) water drop paths identification, (iii) Legros runout assessment, (iv) kinetic features assessment and (v) model accuracy analysis.

The ShaLPA GIS tool delivers a runout assessment of shallow landslides at regional and basin scale, not only providing an estimate of the runout lengths of each potential phenomenon, but intending to place this measurement in the available digital spatial model, from the source areas along the slopes downward to the valley areas, identifying the location of the paths and the arrest points. Furthermore, a coarse but indicative assessment of the dynamic features of the propagation process is also performed providing an estimate of the kinetic energy distribution along the paths connected to the mobilized material.

The propagation process of the shallow landslides was extremely simplified by making some approximations. Despite its limitations, the ShaLPA GIS tool matches the three conditions for runout hazard mapping (Hurlimann, 2008):

- a spatial distribution is provided, and results cover the entire study area;
- different volumes are incorporated as input data;
- the output provides an intensity assessment.

The ShaLPA GIS tool was tested for the first time in the Giampileri and Briga area, allowing to identify strengths and weaknesses of the process and to improve the structure of the scripts. The reliability of the model results is assessed by two different indicators, both normalized to the length of the specific observed LP:

- Distance Index, the distance between the observed and estimated by the model corresponding Landslide Arrest Points;
- Length Index, the difference in length between the observed and estimated by the model corresponding Landslide Paths.

The Giampilieri and Briga test provided encouraging results: the errors greater than 50% are limited to the 10% of the case while 48% of the data show an accuracy level greater than 75%, while in 90% of cases the accuracy is greater than 50%.

The development of easy-to-use, accurate and effective methods, joining cost efficiency and scientific reliability, is a strategic issue in landslide hazard assessment and in defining interventions priorities. The application exploits the potentiality of the QGIS free software in the automation of the data processing required by the runout analysis. The simplicity of the use of ShaLPA tool fosters the opportunity to integrate runout and failure susceptibility analysis, boosting a more complete hazard and risk assessment in valley areas where urban settlements are concentrated and helping to improve the efficacy of landslide mitigation measures (Vegliante et al., 2024). ShaLPA output may also contribute to estimating the solid volume that can be delivered into the hydrographic network, which represents a very useful data in the multirisk approach analysis of both shallow landslides and flash floods.

Keywords: Runout, geometric approach, GIS tool.

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A workflow to identify uncertainty sources in ground instability models

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In geoscience applications, data are acquired, processed, analysed, modelled and interpreted to improve the general knowledge about the functioning of physical environment. Such complex applications are generally subjected to uncertainties arising by both Objective and Subjective limitations. Objective limitations are related, for instance, to technologies and techniques employed and Subjective limitations include subjective knowledge, skills and biases of the geoscientist (Pérez-Díaz et al. 2020; Hetényi et al. 2022). As Pérez-Díaz et al. (2020) point out, uncertainty and its effect on the validity of geoscientific outputs have often been overlooked or only discussed superficially.

The importance of evaluating uncertainty assumes a crucial role when the outputs of the applications concern the assessment of the occurrence of ground instabilities, understood as

phenomena capable of generating geological hazards and possibly related risks (Beven et al., 2018). The assessment of uncertainty must address both the possibility of such phenomena being triggered and the effects that such ground instabilities are likely to produce, for instance, in terms of volumes of material involved, rates of displacement, energies, etc.

This study examines the activities undertaken as part of the RETURN project, with the aim of investigating the management of uncertainties arising from both input data and modelling concerning ground instabilities. In particular, the primary information source utilised for this study comprises the rationalisation sheets previously prepared by project partners, describing operational tools that can address issues related to predisposing, preparatory and triggering factors of ground instability phenomena. By extracting the relevant information from 91 Learning Examples (LEs) composing the Proof of Concept (PoC), the operational tools that assess uncertainties were identified and collected in a general workflow. The uncertainties associated with required input data were distinguished from those inherent to modelling approaches. The obtained workflow is applicable to a chain-like sequence of tools devoted to quantifying effects related to ground instabilities in a multi-hazard scenario perspective.

The LEs were selected with specific reference to predisposing factors, as well as preparatory and triggering processes responsible for ground instabilities. The variability of the contexts examined in this study (terrestrial and marine) and of the environments belonging to them (which vary from high mountains to the coast, passing through hill, plain and coastal systems) means that the diversification of the parameters and factors controlling the predisposing conditions, as well as the preparatory and triggering processes, is particularly pronounced. Nevertheless, the procedure for identifying the main sources of uncertainty is considered general and applicable in all areas.

However, while analysing the LEs, some classification has been done. Among the input data considered in the LEs, some categories that play a more important role has been recognised. In the terrestrial contexts, topographic data, geotechnical or geo-mechanical data, land use and/or land cover data, geo-lithological data and inventories of previous ground instabilities are the most widely considered. While in the marine context, topographic and bathymetric data are the most frequently used input data. Furthermore, the outcomes of LEs were categorised into two groups: (1) Quantitative approaches, where numerical values are utilised in mathematical models to generate probabilistic results and forecasts, and (2) Qualitative approaches, where descriptive classes, which ranges from values of specific physical parameters/variables to qualitative classes, are generated to describe the status of a physical processes (e.g., unstable/stable, etc.).

Probabilistic methods and sensitivity analysis were found to be the most usable approaches in LEs. Probabilistic Methods involve the use of statistical models to represent uncertainty in model inputs and parameters, where all uncertainties are characterised by probability distributions, and model outputs are presented as a range of possibilities with associated probabilities. Sensitivity Analysis is employed to identify which variables most significantly influence the output of a model, thereby aiding in understanding which input data are most critical.

The proposed workflow delineates best practices and procedural steps to address the principal sources of uncertainty inherent in the LEs. This workflow serves as starting point for the development of the next deliverables of this Task, and, in general, the outputs of Spoke VS2. In

fact, the PoC will include a "synthesiser" to assess the susceptibility of specific territories to various ground instabilities, including the preparation, triggering, and resulting effects of geological processes. A framework to assess uncertainty is a pivotal step for the effective development of the PoC.

Keywords: ground instability, uncertainty, workflow.

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Analysis of multiple geohazard scenarios

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The focus of VS2 is on developing methodologies and procedures for reconstructing scenarios of ground instabilities (GIs) effects due to changing environmental conditions in three main compartments –subaerial, subterranean, and submarine–, as well as their impact on the built environment. Three macro-categories of process factors (predisposing, preparatory, and triggering) are considered to have a specific role in the occurrence of GI.

Existing knowledge from numerous case histories, referred to as Learning Examples (LE) and related to their specific processes, have been rationalized. From this activity, a number of

working tools have been derived, including their application fields, constraints, and data requirements.

These tools have been linked into several toolchains, each of them specifically designed for different GI characteristics, environments, scales, and output metrics of tools. An example of a toolchain for evaluating a multi-hazard scenario in different environments is presented, considering cascading effects between GI and different hazards triggered by the same event.

In the simulated scenario, the identification of the most prone areas to GI is the first step, and then the presence of preparatory processes to GI is evaluated. Finally triggering factors are individuated, and their effects are assessed.

In the hilly-mountain environment the simulated case deals with a specific ground instability type and related kinematics (rock slope failures, fast movement), a single trigger (earthquake) and preparatory factor (rainfall) and takes into account both the detachment and invasion areas. Furthermore, a switch has been considered to simulate the activation of different tools based on the availability of ancillary data. In summary, we acted as follows:

1. Identification of rockfall-prone areas by means of susceptibility analysis performed over a wider area.

2. Sub-classification of susceptible areas by means of the SIF (Susceptibility Index to Failure, Napoli et al. 2024) index, which requires site-specific information also on a qualitative basis, and allows for the identification and relative ranking of locations prone to failure as well as the assessment of the effectiveness of the seismic input in increasing the proneness to failure (i.e., co-seismic worsening of susceptibility scenario). The presence of classification parameters dealing with the effects of meteo-climate forcing accounts for the role of preparatory factors.

3. As an alternative to the previous step, another tool has been activated considering the availability of site-specific, high-resolution data. In this case the tool performs quantitative analyses, providing information on the stability of the slope on a cell-by-cell basis in both static and pseudo-static conditions and computing the co-seismic displacements for a given seismic input (or set of inputs) for those location where the pseudo-static safety factors are lower than a given threshold. Furthermore, this tool also accounts for preparatory factors in terms of hydraulic conditions of the joint sets (from dry to fully saturated).

4. The propagation (in terms of areal extent and related energies) of unstable blocks is simulated by means of another tool which is part of the SFI approach but can also be applied to the unstable areas pointed out by other methods.

Regarding the plain areas, an application of the tool chains for liquefaction phenomena is shown. In general, the assessment of any seismic-induced ground failures can be analyzed with approaches of increasing complexity in terms of data and methods. In this study, level I and level II were carried out, as the most suitable for territorial analyses. They were developed accounting for the presence of predisposing factors to liquefaction, following the “if/then (else)” logic Boolean scheme. Considering that liquefaction is never witnessed where seismicity is low, the distribution of PGA values can be considered both a predisposing and a triggering factor. For these reasons, the scheme for assessing liquefaction susceptibility can be updated also adopting this parameter. According to NTC (2018), the value of PGA must be higher than 0.1g to have liquefaction. The chosen test site has been simulated to struck by an important seismic sequence, whose main shock was Mw 6.1. The susceptibility maps confirmed that the majority

of occurred liquefactions fall within the high and very high susceptibility class. A further validation was also gotten by the application of level II approach on some verticals knowing the mechanical characteristics of soils and the assessment of the LPI.

Regarding submarine landslides in the nearshore environment, existing criticalities related to the different resolution and scale of observation used for offshore G.I.s must be considered. Therefore, the toolchain for evaluating multi-hazard scenarios begins with the first tentative to analyze susceptibility in submarine environment and progresses through preparatory and triggering processes, with tools selected based on data availability to conduct qualitative, semi-quantitative, and quantitative analyses of preparatory processes such as debris accumulation from riverbed/ flash floods or outgassing phenomena related to fluid seepage. After determining triggers and calculating the run-out of instabilities, the final step involves using quantitative tools to assess the potential tsunami impact on coastal areas.

Keywords: ground instability, toolchain, scenario based analysis.

Ground instability predisposing factors and susceptibility spatial analyses

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This abstract details the scientific research conducted in the last months (from November 2023 to May 2024), that focused on the categorization of the different types of ground instabilities, with particular reference to their subdivision in rapid vs. slow, on the quantitative analysis of predisposing factors to ground instabilities, and on the spatial analysis of proneness to ground instabilities using statistical methods. These efforts were developed as components of the work designed to establish a state-of-the-art knowledge base to define impact-oriented hazard indicators within the Extended Partnership RETURN Project.

In detail, we initially ranked the ground instability processes into different categories (namely, landslides, sinkholes, subsidence, and liquefaction), in turn distinguishing then among

rapid and slow processes, given the different impacts on society that the velocity of the phenomenon (especially in its final stage) may have. Later, an internal validation phase was carried out, where specific Learning Examples (LEs), selected on the basis of the availability of a good amount of data, were used to produce and further develop susceptibility maps. This phase involved an expansion of the initial LEs by collecting additional data at test sites, including the foundational ones originally utilized by partners for mapping susceptibilities. To streamline this data collection, a structured form was introduced, encompassing fields such as descriptions of ground instability types, available data types and formats, methodologies used for defining susceptibility, methods for validation, and potential areas for improvement. Notably, this phase of work highlighted a distinct focus on submerged environments, underscoring the unique challenges and adapted methodologies pertinent to these contexts.

As next step, a spatial analysis of susceptibility to ground instabilities through statistical approaches was performed, aimed at providing a solid contribution toward the creation of a Proof of Concept (PoC) for analyzing ground instability. A prototype was developed to handle various types of ground instabilities and integrate diverse geospatial data using a user-friendly Graphical User Interface (GUI) developed in Matlab, with potential adaptability to R or Python for enhanced accessibility. This GUI facilitates the application of different susceptibility analysis methods (such as Logistic Regression, Weight of Evidence, and Random Forest models, along with a geomorphic method, Flow-R), tailored specifically to various scales of ground instabilities. The general aim is to offer a functional prototype of the PoC that conforms to the project's preliminary goals and supports informatics experts in enhancing the operational version of the PoC, showing the expected integration and functionality of input data, data structuring, and analysis techniques.

These phases of work set the foundation for the initial phase of evaluating ground instabilities, focusing on identifying areas that are susceptible. However, it is crucial to recognize that this assessment relies on experts to identify the types of instability affecting each area. This essential first step informs all subsequent analysis and the development of mitigation strategies. It involves detailed examinations of geological and geomorphological settings and uses historical data to uncover patterns and triggers of past instability events, allowing to obtain susceptibility maps useful for the analysis of the single typology of ground instability, as well as for their possible combination through a series of tool chains to define ground instability-induced scenarios in a multi-hazard perspective. This thorough initial evaluation is vital for effectively using the developed Graphical User Interface (GUI) and for applying the correct susceptibility models.

The findings from this initial stage then feed into the next steps of the evaluation process. This includes analyzing preparatory and triggering factors as well, that contribute to ground instability. With this data, experts can select the appropriate analytical tools for the identified areas at risk, enabling a targeted and informed approach to managing and mitigating ground instabilities.

Keywords: ground instability, predisposing factors, susceptibility.

Mapping social vulnerability to multi-hazard scenarios for risk reduction strategies

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In recent years, floods and landslides have occurred regularly as consequence of heavy rainfall and deforestation (Nguyen et al., 2023) causing significant damage to ecosystems, infrastructures, and population. These events are often connected or coexist in a specific geographic area producing multi-hazard scenarios that threaten the exposed elements. Due to the complexity of such phenomena, different dimensions of vulnerability (social, physical,

environmental, economic, and institutional) need to be taken into account in disaster risk studies. However, a multi-hazard social vulnerability represents a significant aid for DRR policy as it provides insights for actions to reduce population vulnerability, improve mitigation, enhance resilience, and promote disaster risk management (Drakes & Tate, 2022). Specifically, the interaction between the multi-hazards occurrence and the socio-economic environment suggests the application of multidisciplinary assessment procedures that merge the physical and the socio-economic features of the affected territories providing a useful approach to support multi-risk reduction strategies.

In this context, this study underlines the interaction between the activities carried out within the RETURN project, suggesting a methodology that integrate landslide and flood hazard scenarios with social vulnerability at the sub-municipality level. Open-source platforms were exploited for hazard and social vulnerability data collection, whereas a Geographic Information System (GIS)-based approach was applied to combine different hazard scenarios with social vulnerability distribution to detect the most vulnerable sub-municipality areas. The multidisciplinary analysis was based on three main operational steps: a multi-hazard assessment, a social vulnerability evaluation, and the combination of the results. The investigation was carried out by the use of a semi-quantitative approach that allowed to combine results deriving from different types of analyses (i.e., qualitative, quantitative) in a single classification and providing an overview of the main findings.

The cartographic approach provides a significant example of interaction between VS2 and TS3 offering detailed maps for civil protection agencies and local authorities that need precise identification of areas with heightened vulnerability within the possible affected territories. These final maps would bring the local authorities to know the detailed risk context of their competence territories also constructing plans capable of protecting the most vulnerable populations. Moreover, the computation of a social vulnerability index coupled with the exposure index could bring to the measurement of the socio-economic damage associated with multi-risk contexts, contributing to the output of the Proof of Concept (PoC) of VS2.

The present work points out a relevant outlook about the multidisciplinary methodologies that adopt the co-production of knowledge (Righi et al., 2021; Lahiri et al., 2021) and different techniques belonging to various study fields in order to promote risk reduction strategies and community resilience solutions.

Keywords: social vulnerability, multi-hazard, risk reduction strategies.

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Multihazard analysis and management of the landslide debris transported downstream

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A multi-hazard analysis (seismic, landslide, flood) is conducted to verify the impact on the road network. The ENEA CIPCast platform is an innovative Decision Support System (DSS) used to implement the analyses by using GIS. Using analytical and geoprocessing tools, the hazards were assessed and mapped. Overlapping of different geospatial layers allow to implement a specific hazard map for the road network. GIS-based methodologies are particularly

suitable for identifying the portions of land where disasters triggered by natural hazards of various kinds may occur. Multi-hazard values were obtained by an appropriate matrix of single values, classified and then summarised into four classes of values. The analyses were conducted at the regional (Campania Region), provincial (Naples Metropolitan City), and local scales (Island of Ischia and Municipality of Casamicciola Terme). In particular, the landslide event that struck the Municipality of Casamicciola Terme on the Island of Ischia on November 26, 2022, is considered as a case study to determine the impact on road network, infrastructures, buildings and jeopardising inter-municipal connections. The results are mainly visualised through map processing and statistical summaries of the data. Management of landslide debris, which can contain a multitude of fractions (waste, biomass and vegetation, sludge, soil, and rocks transported downstream by water), was also explored. This is a frontier issue for which international manuals and guidelines as well as national and emergency acts have been examined. A specific protocol for the sustainable management of debris generated by floods and landslides is needed, and discussed in Cappucci et al. (2024), in order to overcome emergencies after catastrophic events.

Keywords: multi-hazard analysis; critical Infrastructures; debris management.

Nearshore submarine landslides: from the susceptibility assessment to the landslide run-out and tsunami simulation in the Capo D’Orlando Basin

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VS2 focuses on developing methodologies and procedures to reconstruct scenarios of ground instability (GI) effects caused by changing environmental conditions across three main compartments—subaerial, subterranean, and submarine—and their impact on the environment. The occurrence of GIs is influenced by different controlling factors such as preconditioning (long term), preparatory (short term) and triggering processes/events. Each category is analysed in specific work packages (WP2, WP3, and WP4, respectively). GI is therefore fully constrained in a chain of processes and states with different temporal durations of influence with respect to the failure occurrence. In the RETURN project this concept is

rationalized through the toolchains, i.e. a series of operations (tools) used to simulate the effects of GIs. Each toolchain is specific to different GI characteristics, environments, scales, and output metrics of tools. Our aim is to perform a toolchain specifically built for rapid submarine landslide in the nearshore environment, starting from the definition of the susceptible slope areas (WP2) and ending with the landslide activation and estimation of run-out and velocity. The multihazard potential is also evaluated through a tsunami simulation.

Capo D'Orlando Basin (COB) is chosen as study area to perform the toolchain simulation. COB is located in the southern Tyrrhenian Sea on the Sicilian continental margin. The continental shelf here is carved by landslide scars and numerous submarine canyons whose heads, especially to the east, are very close to the coast and near to river mouths. COB is imaged by a high-resolution (10 m) multibeam bathymetry.

The first step in the simulated scenario consists in the identification of the most prone areas to landslide in the form of a susceptibility map using tools from WP2. In the literature, there are few examples of submarine landslide susceptibility maps and are all performed on deep-seated landslides since shallow-water landslides are more difficult to study due to the frequent overprinting of multiple events that cancel and/or coalesce on each other. For this reason, to perform a susceptibility map for nearshore landslides, a series of precautions have been taken. The landslides headwall selected were exclusively those where subsequent reworking, indicated by the presence of gullies, was absent, and where the failed slope could be clearly distinguished from the surrounding failures or stable areas. This method allowed to depict 303 landslide headwalls and transpose them as polygons. Due to the available data in this area, the possible predisposing factors, each of which has been divided into classes, were: bathymetry (5 classes), mean slope angle (5 classes), slope face direction (9 classes) and the distance from river mouth (5 classes). The latter is used as a simplified indicator of the impact of hyperpycnal flows correlated with the occurrence of flash floods considered as a determinant predisposing factor for rapid submarine landslides. The Weight of Evidence (WoE) method, considered well suitable for submarine environment (Liu et al., 2023), was applied in the study area. The contrast map revealed a good correspondence between landslides and depth range of 100-400 m, slopes comprised by 20°-50°, distance from river mouth between 2-4 Km and orientation towards N-NW. ROC curves value reveal a good correspondence (0.94) between input predisposing factors and instable areas.

Finally, the effects of landsliding in the nearshore environment have been assessed (WP4). Calculations of the slide dynamics, of the resulting tsunamigenic impulse and of tsunami propagation are performed applying two tools (OGSBO3_1,2) extracted from the learning example of the Assi Landslide (Ceramicola et al., 2014) and whose codes are developed and maintained by the University of Bologna Tsunami Research Team. The codes have been run on two different types of landslides that frequently occur in the nearshore environment: a rotational slide (volume of 4,9 Mm³) and a debris flow (volume of 0,2 Mm³). The tool OGSBO3_1 solves equations of motion accounting for gravity, buoyancy and all interactions between the sliding mass and the environment, to obtain the slide velocity and run-out. These elements are used to compute the impact of the tsunami on the shoreline, here parametrized in terms of the maximum wave amplitude along the coast with the second tool OGSBO_2.

The simulation of the toolchain, which included the definition of areas with higher susceptibility using the application developed within the context of WP2 and the quantification

of the effects of two existing landslides using two tools rationalized in WP4, demonstrated the good transposability of the methodologies proposed in different WPs to areas different from those of the learning examples, thus validating their transferability to the PoC.

Keywords: submarine landslide, nearshore, toolchain.

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Non-structural mitigation strategies for landslides hazard in structurally complex formations

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Studies on landslide phenomena in complex clay formations demonstrate a limited applicability of structural mitigation strategies (Greco & Pagano, 2017), which may result inefficient due to the depth of the sliding surface (often significant and hard to be located) and to the role played by the chemo-mechanical behaviour of materials (Ghulamzan et al., 2022; Di Maio, 2024) on slope stability.

Two examples of non-structural mitigation strategies will be presented below.

The first approach presented in the study is based on monitoring activities carried out on a clay slope located at the Pietrapertosa test site (Basilicata region). This method aims to collect

empirical data through direct observation and measurement of internal physical variables into the slope, namely:

- pore water pressure in the soil: this measurement provides crucial information about soil saturation, eventual seepage and potential swelling and/or decrease of available strength, that can weaken the soil structure and trigger or accelerate the slope movement.

- gradient of surface displacements of the slope: monitoring the gradient of displacements helps identifying slow and progressive movements of the soil that can precede large deformations.

To collect these data, the research group of University of Napoli Federico II developed and installed an innovative instrument called a "tensio-inclinometer", a device combining two functions:

- measurement of pore water pressure in the soil (as a tensiometer);
- detection of changes in the inclination of the ground, providing data on surface displacements (as an inclinometer).

The application of the proposed monitoring system is expected to yield data on the evolution of monitored physical variables at various positions along the landslide. When properly acquired and interpreted, these data can be exploited for defining alert and alarm thresholds within the framework of an early warning system. It is expected that measuring the rotation of a tensiometer pipe which also provides suction measurements results considerably simpler, more cost-effective and durable than installing an in-depth displacement monitoring system based on conventional inclinometers.

In the Pietrapertosa case-study, a direct correlation between pore water pressure and tilting evolution is evident. It can be noted that at the beginning of dry period, with suction still at high levels, the pipe experienced a tilting decrease (corresponding to counter-rotation that indicates a sliding deformation pattern). When suction vanishes, leading to values fluctuating around zero, there is a change in sign of the pipe tilting, with displacements increasing with elevation according to a flow-like deformational pattern. Summarizing, during some stages when suction values ranges around 0 kPa, rotation decreases with depth, corresponding to the typical movement of an earthflow; during some other stages, the counter-rotation registered recalls otherwise the kinematic of a rigid body.

The second approach presented, which is more complex, combines qualitative and quantitative considerations. The on-site monitoring activity conducted on a clay slope at the Cerda test site (Sicily), is corroborated by numerical interpretative analyses of the studied landslide movement. The physical variables considered are:

- Cumulated rainfall during the months before the landslide event,
- Variations in pore water pressures due to rainfall,
- Variations of the displacement rate due to rainfall.

In the Cerda case study, the displacement rates increased considerably when the pore water pressure variation Δu_w is higher than a threshold value equal to about 10 kPa. The threshold value of the 5-month cumulative rainfall CR was 400 mm: very low rates and almost nil variation in pore water pressure are measured for lower rainfall. Pore water pressure variation vs cumulative 5-month rainfall CR (mm). Mean daily horizontal displacement rate \dot{d} (mm/day) vs cumulative 5-month rainfall, CR (mm). The relationships between rainfall, pore water pressure variations and displacement rate are site-specific, and the parameters have to be calibrated after

a period of field monitoring. The method can be used to predict future process development scenarios from data calibrated over a monitoring period. Site-specific equations were developed by the research group of the University of Palermo to relate the 5-month cumulated rainfall to the pore water pressure variations and the displacement rate of the landslide.

Keywords: landslide, mitigation strategies, tool chain.

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Results of preliminary applications of a toolchain for subsidence

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In the context of WP4 (Trigger-based multiple geohazard scenarios) of the Vertical Spoke VS2, multiple geohazard effects are evaluated for different environments (near-shore and coastal areas, volcanic islands; hilly and mountain areas; large plains and sinkhole zones) through several tools, framed in a chain-like structure. To test the applicability of such tools, a part of the subsidence-related toolchain (developed in the Deliverable 2.4.5) has been

preliminarily applied to assess vertical ground deformations in two test sites of the Neapolitan area in southern Italy. These areas experience vertical ground deformation, including both subsidence and uplift due to natural and anthropogenic factors. Specifically, the first site is the northern sector of the Sarno river plain (SA), characterized by subsidence caused by tectonic activity and human-induced water table drawdown of the phreatic pyroclastic-alluvial aquifer (Valente et al., 2021). The second site is located in the territory of Casalnuovo di Napoli municipality in the eastern plain of Naples, where a reduction of pumping has triggered the groundwater rebound phenomenon over the last 30 years, causing a rise in piezometric levels of the multi-layered aquifer with localized ground uplift (Coda et al., 2019).

The toolchain used considers a set of parameters as predisposing and preparatory factors to produce process severity class maps (qualitative, quantitative, or semiquantitative).

Therefore, based on the geological and hydrogeological features of the test areas and the characteristics of the phenomenon, seven parameters are considered, i.e.: (1) lithology, (2) main faults (for SA), (3) landuse, (4) piezometric level depth, (5) piezometric variations, (6) depth of the aquitard layer (for CA), (7) distance from the main pumping area (for CA). Each parameter is reclassified, assigning scores which vary from 0 to 4 through a heuristic approach. The sum of the scores returns a preliminary estimation of subsidence (for SA) or uplift (for CA) susceptibility, expressed in three classes (low, medium, and high).

Validation of results has been carried out through a comparative analysis of the susceptibility classes with vertical ground deformation maps based on DInSAR data. A good correspondence emerges between areas characterized by higher values of deformation and the medium and high classes for both test areas. Despite being a preliminary attempt at testing the toolchain, these results are encouraging and provide a basis for the next scheduled objectives.

Keywords: subsidence, uplift, toolchain testing.

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Submarine fluid escapes. Their role on ground instabilities according to predisposing, preparatory and triggering factors

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Studies conducted under the RETURN Project have allowed us to analyze the submerged structures associated with processes of fluid uprising, such as water or gas, from the seabed. Submarine "fluid escapes" can play a significant role in the predisposing, preparatory, and triggering factors for the development of submarine landslides. The morphological structures,

Pockmark (negative structures) (Lo Iacono et al., 2011), Mounds (positive structures), gas chimney (Wan et al., 2002) and buried reservoirs like the Mass Transport Deposit (MTD) (Sun et al., 2017) depending on their depth, the nature of the emitted fluid, their extent, and the area involved, both on the surface and especially in the stratigraphy of the seabed, determine the formation of volumes, even of significant size, of incoherent sediments because uprising fluids impregnate the sediments of the layers flowed, causing the rupture of cohesive and friction forces.

The presence of submerged tectonic structures, stratigraphic sequences with alternating permeable and impermeable levels, particularly steep seabeds, and the presence of fluid sources (thermogenic, biogenic, and groundwater) are the predisposing conditions for the presence of fluid emission structures or buried reservoirs on the seabed at any depth.

The preparatory factors related to the continuous or discontinuous escape or the pressurized accumulation of fluids from the seabed can be geological or biochemical nature. The most significant geological factors are certainly linked to microseismicity which causes the mobilization of gases trapped in the layers towards an escape route or a common accumulation point; the slow depressurization of reservoirs due to the lithostatic unloading of the containing sequence; the regional uplift, and the increase in fractures in a fluid-saturated layer. Exclusively for groundwater sources, intense rainfall events are a preparatory factor for fluid escape.

There is a wealth of scientific evidence for the formation of submarine landslides linked to the presence of fluid escapes (e.g., Storegga landslide, Zhu et al., 2023). Strong earthquakes and sudden changes in lithostatic loads are, for example, triggering factors for the formation of submarine landslides linked to structures of fluid escapes.

Recently, a study attempt relate to the geomechanical variables associated with structures such as Pockmark, Mounds, gas chimney, and Mass Transport Deposit (MTD) (Sultan et al., 2004, Rozhko et al., 2007) is indeed necessary to extract quantitative data and study the geological evolution of these structures and the submarine landslides associated with them to best understand these important processes.

In the Palermo Gulf, pockmarks are observed and studied as a Learning Example in WP3 of the RETURN project. Here, submarine ground instabilities are connected to these structures; the fluid escapes plays a primary role as a preparatory factor of ground instabilities because it intervenes in the modification of the geomechanical variables (e.g., intergranular cohesion, internal friction angle, undrained shear strength, etc.) of the rocks it traverses, transforming them into a volume of unconsolidated sediment. The process is irreversible and therefore, even if the gas flux were to end or be interrupted, the geomechanical characteristics are not restored, leaving a sediment easily erodible and mobilizable by seismic triggers, which constitute the most important "toolchain" triggering of submarine landslides connected with structures of fluid escapes. The quantification of the volumes of these sediments, achievable through a study of seismic profiles, morphobathymetric data and geomechanical properties, allows us to the evaluation of the volumes of unconsolidated sediments and consequent, possible, submarine landslide hazard. It is a study of primary importance, especially if fluid escapes structures are present in near shore environments.

Keywords: fluid escapes, ground instabilities, marine environment.

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Toolchains for estimating earth-flow effects at regional scale: an example for evaluating the preparatory/triggering processes

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One of the goals of the RETURN project (multi-Risk science for resilient communities under a changing climate) is to study the ground instabilities driven by natural hazard exacerbated by climate change and to assess their impacts on the anthropic and the natural environment. To assess the impacts of different Ground Instabilities (GIs) such as landslides, sinkholes, liquefaction, and subsidence, the working group of the Vertical Spoke 2 (VS2) defined a series of tools to address issues related to predisposing, preparatory and triggering factors of former types of GI(s). Moreover, in the view of possible multiple geohazards that may characterise a certain portion of a territory, also the associated run out was assessed by specific tools. Once the working tools have been extracted from specific learning examples, the subsequent phase has been addressed towards the construction of the “tool chains”, i.e. the logical and operational workflow that put together the outcomes of the different Work Packages (WP) by combining the sequence of tools that can lead to the assessment of expected impact scenarios for different GIs, starting from predisposing factors and passing through possible preparatory up to the triggering processes.

The aim of the present work is to explore part of a possible “tool chain” focused on landslides occurring in mountain and hill areas at a regional scale and driven by hydrologic forcing (i.e. prolonged intense rainfall) and earthquakes. The part of the tool chain discussed herein considers both the preparatory and triggering factors of slow landslides, which, however, cannot be disregarded from a susceptibility analysis performed through one of the tool of the predisposing factors. In detail, an intense rainfall event (with a return time of 4 years as regards the millimetres of rain per hour) was taken into account as a preparatory factor for the earthflows, while the seismic action (magnitude) was considered as trigger. As an example, the approach proposed by Martino et al. (2020) was used to primarily assess the preparatory factors. This tool, characterised by qualitative/semi-quantitative logs, shows that the high saturation of the soil induced by an intense rainfall event (about 120 mm of rain in 3 days) preceding and concurrent with the earthquake aggravates the stability conditions of the slopes, making the latter more prone to failure. Beyond 10 km from the epicentre, it can be assumed that the contribution of rainfall with the consequent saturation of the soil and the increase of pore-water pressure can induce several landslides even at greater distances than expected for a low-magnitude earthquake. In particular, the distance at which landslides can be reactivated is one order of magnitude greater than the Keefer circumference (Keefer 1984), i.e., a distance of about 20 km compared to the 2 km foreseen by the Keefer radius. Concerning triggering process, the described scenario involves an earthquake that affect the area immediately after the rain event. The tool proposed by Rollo and Rampello (2023) quantifies the permanent seismic-induced displacements of natural slopes as a function of the intensity of the earthquake and the yield seismic coefficient condensing the slope geometry and the soil strength through a semi-empirical relationship developed on the Italian seismicity. The tool is also suitable to be combined within a probabilistic framework for a regional scale assessment of the permanent slope displacements at different return periods of the earthquake. It is shown that some areas of the Italian territory are more prone to slope instabilities as characterised by more severe seismicity and more critical geomorphological and geotechnical settings. Moreover, as the intense rainfall are expected to reduce the soil strength, this can lead to a reduction of the yield seismic coefficient of the slopes, with a consequent increase of permanent displacements.

Therefore, the tool chain proposed in this study could represent a new paradigm for large-scale ground instabilities assessment in which the results carried out with different methods of analysis on a series of well-established and documented case studies contribute to a more deep understanding of these phenomena. The philosophy of the tool chain is also promising as deals with a “cascading process” able to account for multi-hazard effects.

Keywords: ground instabilities, tool chain, landslides preparatory and triggers factors.

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Toolchains for estimating earth-flow effects at regional scale: an example for evaluating the predisposing factors

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Within the general frame of RETURN (multi-Risk science for resilient communities under a changing climate), the VS2 (Vertical Spoke 2) working group focuses on Ground Instabilities (GIs) like landslides, sinkholes, liquefaction, and subsidence. In this view, starting from focused learning examples, a set of tools has been identified, to address the different phases and stages of instability phenomena, with specific regard to predisposing, preparatory and triggering factors, as well as the associated run out. Such tools have been extracted and put into relationship to build “toolchains”, logical and operational workflows that put together the outcomes of the different Work Packages (WP). Starting from predisposing factors, through possible preparatory processes up to the triggering, related tools are combined for the assessment of expected impact scenarios for different GIs.

The present work aims to analyze part of a possible "toolchain", focused on the evaluation of the impact-oriented hazard indicators. In the frame of Return project, the Work Package 2.2 (hereinafter referred to as WP2) is devoted to this theme and the WP2 working group has developed a specific for the susceptibility analysis. Landslide susceptibility expresses the probability of occurrence of a landslide in a specific area based on its local characteristics (Brabb, 1984). These local characteristics are the specific geo-environmental conditions, considered stable over-time, for a specific area. The prototype developed by the WP2 working group (on Matlab platform) offers to the users the possibility to evaluate the activation areas of landslides using data-driven methods (choosing among three of the most used statistical methods: Weight of Evidence, Logistic Regression and, Random Forest) or geomorphological-driven method (Flow-R software). Several type of landslide typologies can be analysed, and, at the same time, several variables can be exploited for evaluating the relationships between past phenomena and geo-environmental variables to spatially recognize landslide-prone areas (which are considered as stable/unstable a priori of preparatory and triggering factors).

In this work, we consider a potential application to earthflow landslide typology, in mountainous and hilly areas on a regional scale. Therefore, geology, geomorphology, physical and mechanical characteristics, and land cover are considered crucial (directly or as proxy) for defining stable/unstable condition for earthflow landslides.

Among the available statistic methods, Logistic Regression was used. It is specifically designed for analysing datasets in which one or more independent variables determine an outcome (dependent variable) that has only two possible values (binary outcomes). It estimates the probability that a given observation belongs to a particular category of the dependent variable and applies a logistic function to transform the linear combination of predictor variables into a probability score between 0 and 1. The logistic regression model is formulated as follows:

$$P(Y=1|X)=1/(1+e^{-(\beta_0+\beta_1X_1+\beta_2X_2+\dots+\beta_nX_n)})$$

where:

$P(Y=1|X)$ is the probability that the dependent variable Y equals 1 given the values of the independent variables X ; β_0 is the intercept; $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n$ are the coefficients of the independent variables; X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n are the values of the independent variables.

The statistical model and the related map are finally validated so to define the accuracy, robustness and precision of the prediction image produced. In fact, according to Chung and Fabbri (2003), the susceptibility map must be validated by comparison to a target pattern (blinded), which represents the areas affected by landslides. Receiver Operating Characteristic

(ROC) -curve and related Area Under the Curve (AUC) are used to estimate the performance of the models. At the same time, cut-off or susceptibility threshold is used to establish a probability threshold for categorizing pixels into binary states of stable or unstable. By exploiting the ROC curve, the optimal threshold can be considered as the point nearest to the (0,1) corner, which indicates perfect prediction. Once the cut-off is applied to the score range, a binary predicted status is defined and by comparison to the observed status of stable/unstable cases, a confusion matrix is performed and the true/false positive/negative cases classified, so to evaluating the overall accuracy of the model.

In this way, the primary output of the tool, i.e. the susceptibility map, can be passed to the follow steps of the “toolchain”, so to evaluating the effect of potentially preparatory and/or triggering factors in modifying the static susceptibility to landsliding of a specific study area.

Keywords: landslide susceptibility, earthflow, toolchain.

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Trigger-based multiple geohazard scenarios: activities overview and tool application

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The return of products functional to the assessment of the level of damage associated with ground instabilities currently represents a key theme for shifting the axis of the analysis of

these connected processes from their detection and prediction to risk assessment and, ultimately, to recovery strategies for resilience.

In order to propose a quantitative solution to the evaluation of the expected damage and/or more generally of the impact of ground instabilities on urban, infrastructural or socio-economic systems, it is necessary to adopt outputs that are not limited to zoning the severity of a hazard or the attitude of the territory to suffer the same but rather aim to create real scenarios with an expected effect.

In this sense, within the Spoke VS2 - RETURN the research path undertaken is arduously moving from the well-established practice of spatial analysis of probability (more commonly known as "susceptibility") or the restitution of its temporal recurrence (properly "hazard mapping"), this last one possibly rendered as a probability of exceeding functional process thresholds, towards the return of quantitative "scenarios of effects".

The latter include spatial and temporal distribution of effects connected to ground instabilities quantified by classes/severity indices/scalar or vector physical quantities. The probability connected to triggering actions is not necessary. The scenario can also be addressed by a deterministic choice on the forcing actions.

To construct these scenarios, it is possible to make use of chains of tools, each of which has been validated through learning on specific techniques. Regardless of this, however, the tool chain itself requires its own validation which, rather than in terms of reliability, must at this point be understood in relation to its extrapolation to more generic environmental contexts/scales/processes for which it is considered potentially valid.

The advantage given by the tool chains is that they can make use not of "validation learning" but of "instructive learning" which aims to train and refine the quantitative analysis tools through outputs that can also derive from simulations, based on procedures calculation or semi-empirical algorithms.

Spoke VS2, in embarking on the path of building specific tool chains for the environment/scale/process, aims to create an IT tool for synthesizing them whose expected output is represented by a spatial and temporal distribution of quantities (expressed as classes/indexes /values of parameters) functional to the sizing of effects and therefore to transform this evaluation into a measure of the damage and/or repercussions of the ground instability process.

As an example, we can think of a susceptibility analysis applied to an extensive subsidence process from which derives the return of a susceptibility map, at regional scale, with respect to which the territory can be zoned for levels of severity based on the simple predisposition to the effect. If this basis is associated with a preparatory process (such as the seasonal oscillation of the water table or the evolution of underground caves) the probability of occurrence of a more instantaneous failure (sinkhole) becomes functional to the recurrence of a potential trigger that occurs a critical moment in the evolution of the underground system (e.g. underground cavities).

The hazard map thus returned is, however, not sufficient for the purposes of quantifying damage and/or impact because it does not measure the intensity of the effect (including its propagation in space starting from the origin/source area) expected but only the probability that it could happen.

For the purposes of sizing the damage, however, it is necessary to add to the hazard map a measure of effect intensity which, properly, constitutes the expected scenario. Unlike a hazard map, however, the scenario may not even have a probabilistic measure; as such, it can become completely disconnected from the hazard if, for example, the scenario wants to be driven by a sensitivity analysis to destabilized or forcing actions understood not as probable but as, simply, admissible.

Ultimately, the returned scenario can directly use the framework of a susceptibility map without necessarily having to include hazard information.

For the purposes of future projections of environmental conditions, such as climatic changes, for which the probability of occurrence is not a reliable measure, the scenarios of effects, unlike the hazard map, remains a functional tool for risk quantification and strategy design of resilience. A further challenge to be taken up and created a scenario product based on multi-hazard understood both as the superposition of single independent events and as cascade processes (i.e. “domino-like” effects). Such a "synthetic" product aimed at risk analysis becomes a tool capable of integrating the information layer relating to ground instabilities and its effects in the processing workflow that more extensively it concerns the RETURN project.

Keywords: ground instabilities, multi-hazard mapping, scenario based analysis.

Understanding the spatial patterns of hydro-geomorphological disasters in Italy using the CatBoost regressor

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Globally, the frequency and magnitude of hydro-geomorphological events, such as floods and landslides, are experiencing an upward trend due to climate change and unplanned development in hazardous zones. Italy was struck by 123 hydrogeological disasters between 2013 and 2022, with each province facing at least one event and some provinces enduring over ten incidents (Gatto et al., 2023).

This study aims to understand the spatial patterns of hydro-geomorphological disasters in Italian provinces using the CatBoost regressor and a wide set of environmental, territorial and economic factors. CatBoost stands out as a gradient-boosted decision tree algorithm designed to handle numerical and categorical (heterogeneous) data types (Hancock and Khoshgoftaar, 2020). Through the implementation of an ordered boosting technique, CatBoost effectively mitigates the risk of overfitting, a common problem in other boosting algorithms (Ozcan et al., 2024). Additionally, CatBoost will yield higher accuracy as an ensemble algorithm than standalone machine learning algorithms (Ibrahim et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2020). Five different groups of predisposing factors, namely geological (22 factors), soil sealing (14 factors), soil sealing trends from 2015 to 2021 (14 factors), IdroGEO platform (Iadanza et al., 2021) indicators (10 factors), and economic (four factors), have been considered, thus totalling 64 factors. The cumulative number of months of duration of the suffered emergency states (MES) is selected as the dependent factor for the regression analysis, expressing the persistency of the negative impacts of extreme hydrogeological events. The initial step includes the multicollinearity assessment and feature selection employing the Relief algorithm to discard the correlated and irrelevant/redundant factors (i.e., the factors with VIF scores above 10 and negative Relief scores will be discarded from the modelling). The second stage involves the k-fold (10-fold) validation of the regression analysis employing the MAE, RMSE, and R2 scores. The final stage is the assessment of the factor importance employing the CatBoost algorithm. The factor importance assessment also served as a selection process, i.e., the factors with importance scores below 10 will be discarded from all the five groups.

The two-stage feature selection process discarded 16 factors from the geological group, six from the soil sealing group, five from the soil sealing trend group, four from the IdroGEO group, and one from the economic group, thus totalling 32 factors.

The first experiment consisted of modelling MES using one group of factors at a time. The k-fold validation scores of the regression analysis employing the CatBoost regressor for the five groups are as follows: geological (MAE: 34.914, RMSE: 49.882, and R2: 0.789), soil sealing (MAE: 36.948, RMSE: 42.409, and R2: 0.742), soil sealing trend (MAE: 50.015, RMSE: 63.534, and R2: 0.322), IdroGEO (MAE: 39.337, RMSE: 50.350, and R2: 0.625), and economic (MAE: 57.740, RMSE: 78.342, and R2: 0.475). The R2 scores depict a strong internal relationship for the geological, soil sealing, and IdroGEO groups, a moderate relationship for the economic group, and a weak relationship for the soil sealing trend group. Based on the assessed explanatory power of factors, the second stage of factor selection discarded one factor from the geological group, four factors from the soil sealing group, five factors from the soil sealing trend group, two factors from the IdroGEO group, and one factor from the economic group since the importance scores are below 10 (thus, 19 factors have been selected). Though the economic group has a moderate relationship and the soil sealing trend group has a weak relationship, this second-stage selection and further exclusion of lower-importance factors will solve this issue.

Finally, the two-stage feature selection process was again applied to the total group with 19 factors, which discarded two factors with VIF scores above 10; thus, finally, 17 factors were selected for the modelling. The k-fold validation scores for the total group after the regression analysis using the CatBoost regressor are as follows: MAE: 34.247, RMSE: 38.102, and R2: 0.772. The R2 score for the final group reiterates a strong relationship. The modelling emphasized the dominant role of soil sealing factors, like soil sealing in medium hydrogeological risk zones, consumed land over 600 meters a.s.l. in hectares, the trend in soil sealing in medium hydrogeological risk, and consumed land in high-risk flood hazard zones in hectares being in the top five important factors, along with the gross domestic product (GDP).

This research is novel as it marks the initial endeavour to examine the spatial patterns of hydro-geomorphological disasters by employing machine learning algorithms which incorporate geological, soil sealing, soil sealing trends, and economic factors and indicators from the IdroGEO platform.

Keywords: CatBoost, hydro-geomorphological disasters, Italy.

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VS3 ‘Earthquakes and Volcanoes’

A dual structural monitoring system for the main building of the University of Naples’ Federico II School of Engineering

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Structural monitoring systems are tools that are being included in the support arsenal for the planning of loss mitigation strategies for the built environment with increasing frequency. The main building of the School of Engineering of the University of Naples Federico II is a landmark eleven-storey reinforced concrete structure situated in the Fuorigrotta district of the Naples metropolitan area, adjacent to the Campi Flegrei region, which is notoriously exposed to both earthquake and volcanic hazards.

Within the activities of the RETURN research project, a seismic and structural monitoring system was conceptualized and designed and is currently in an advanced implementation phase. This system consists of two separate sensor networks, that complement each other, both continuously providing data in real time.

One system consists of a network of high-sensitivity, three-component accelerometers that allow the measurement of ambient- or low-amplitude earthquake-induced vibrations and performing continuous dynamic identification of the structure's vibration characteristics by means of operational modal analysis. The other complementary monitoring system consists of stand-alone multi-instrument stations that record strong ground acceleration, velocity and absolute GNSS positioning at high frequency. These stations can provide real-time measurements of the relative displacements (translations and rotations) of the structure's elevation in relation to its foundation during future seismic events.

The combination of the two systems will allow acquisition of a steady stream of data that can provide information on the dynamics of the structure prior, during and after ground-shaking events and give the possibility of monitoring the exceedance of predetermined response thresholds.

Keywords: seismic risk, earthquake engineering, operational modal analysis.

A methodology for large-scale assessment of the seismic stability of infill walls

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A methodology for large-scale evaluation of the seismic stability of infill walls in reinforced concrete buildings is being developed. The study focuses on the area of Campi Flegrei west of Naples (Italy), as Demo Site. The proposed methodology aims to compare the Demand due to the expected seismic action with the Capacity of a sample of infill walls, assumed as common among the existing buildings of the studied area. The elements of the considered sample differ in terms of geometrical parameters, mechanical properties and boundary conditions with respect to the surrounding frame. The edges can be seen as fixed supports (supposing that all relative displacements are constrained) or as hinges (in case the relative rotations are allowed) or as free ends (if no degree of freedom is constrained). In general, different boundary conditions could be applied to the wall along its perimeter, e.g. due to the laying of materials or to consider past damages.

As a result of combining the above listed factors, each element of the sample has an own dynamic behavior and may experience a different interaction with the building inside of which it is located. The reliability of the seismic stability evaluation will depend on how demand and capacity will be computed, as well as on the accuracy of the modelling of building and wall. On the other hand, the more detailed the modelling will be, the more the results will be representative of the case of analysis. Then, as a first step, a simplified approach has been considered efficient to build a broad overview of the behavior of the sample. This approach consists on: i) modelling buildings (from 1 to 7 floors) as one degree of freedom systems and computing their natural periods through simplified formulas admitted by the rules; ii) assuming that the wall behaves as a plate connected to the frame by hinges along its whole perimeter; iii) expressing the Demand in terms of uniformly distributed seismic load q_d taking accelerations from the spectrum given by Rules (Circolare 7, 2019); iv) expressing the Capacity through formulas q_c that could be directly compared with load. On this regard, a literature review of several methods used to determine the out-of-plane capacity of masonry infills was carried out. These methods are based on empirical formulas or, alternatively, on semi-analytical capacity derivation.

In Dawe and Seah (1989) two equations are proposed considering simply supports on four or three (bottom and laterals) edges. These formulas are derived for masonry made of hollow concrete blocks within a pinned frame and, as the authors states, their use for infills in moment resisting frames may result in a conservative estimate of the ultimate load. Eurocode 6 (2005) proposes two more possibilities for capacity evaluation. The first one is based on the arch mechanism and is applicable only when it can develop, i.e., when no gap exists at one of the opposite edges in the direction of the thrust. The second formula is based on the yield line theory. Other empirical or semi-empirical relationships have been derived based on the arch mechanism in one direction (Liberatore et al. 2020). In Di Trapani et al (2021) a formula for capacity evaluation was defined from a hybrid database composed of experimental tests and numerical simulations. Consistently with boundary conditions assumed for this simplified approach, the empirical formula q_c given by Eurocode and based on the arch mechanism was established as the most suitable to use in the present context.

The quantity q_c/q_d has been plotted as a function of the ratio between the Natural Period of the wall T_w and the Natural Period of the building T_b to identify the walls of the sample which are not in safety conditions for a fixed value of Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA). Based on the

results of such preliminary overview, during next stage of the project we intend to investigate in more depth the behavior of the infill walls of the sample, also through numerical analyses by finite element modelling (FEM).

Keywords: infill walls, seismic stability, large scale assessment.

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A new UNIBA-INGV GNSS CORS Network for Gargano monitoring

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To significantly contribute to seismological studies in the Gargano area, this research proposes integrating the current OTRIONS seismic monitoring infrastructure with the implementation of a GNSS CORS (Continuously Operating Reference Station) network.

The Gargano region is very interesting from a seismological perspective, as it is characterized by several strike-slip faults with a preferential W-E direction, who are responsible of medium-low intensity seismic activity at least in recent times (Miccolis et al., 2021). The displacement, that involves the Gargano area, of few millimeters for year, is due to the convergence of the Apennines chain to SW and Dinaridi one to NE.

Currently the monitoring of deformations is carried out through the analysis of GNSS data recorded by 6 INGV stations that belong to the RING (Rete Integrata Nazionale GPS) network and 2 stations managed by the Puglia Region. The current limits of estimating the deformations of the Apulian platform are linked to the limited presence of GNSS stations in the region.

To study from a seismological point of view in more detail the Gargano area, the OTRIONS seismic network was installed starting from 2013 (Filippucci et al., 2021) and the seismic data collected by the network show that the crust is seismically involved up to a depth of 40 km. The ipocenters indicate the presence of a low-angle seismogenic structure trending SW-NE and dipping SE-NW (Miccolis et al., 2021). Furthermore, one of the sites where the OTRIONS seismic station is installed it is also equipped with a magnetotelluric station.

With this project we intend to strengthen the existing infrastructure by creating a multi-parameter network thanks to integration between seismic, GNSS and magnetotelluric stations as a Near-Fault Observatories (NFO). The collection of high-quality multidisciplinary data from different solid Earth disciplines, such as geodesy, seismology and magnetotelluric, could help the scientific progress in better understanding seismogenic processes, the fault systems and earthquake mechanisms that characterize the Gargano area.

The NFO are designed to collect scientific data to unravel the complex seismogenic faults (<https://www.epos-eu.org/tcs/near-fault-observatories/about>). From a technological and operational point of view, 6 sites have been identified on the Gargano promontory, in which will be installed the new GNSS stations. They cover the south-eastern part of the Gargano, i.e. the area discovered by the other existing networks. The implementation of the GNSS-CORS network also aims to create a geodesy center at Department of Earth and Geo-environmental Sciences of the Bari University, for teaching and research activities. These stations will be able to guarantee a more detailed velocity field than that calculated by Devoti et al. (2017). The GNSS network it is designed to use the latest technological innovations of the GPS system linked to the concepts of signal modernization and interoperability of satellite constellations. In recent years, GNSS processing strategies have evolved, taking advantage of multiconstellation and multifrequency availability to improve the estimation of relevant parameters to seismology. Long-term deformation captured by GNSS has contributed to models of the interseismic and postseismic phases of the earthquake cycle, in addition to identification and monitoring of slow slip.

Furthermore, thanks to the great advances in hardware and software, GNSS positioning technologies have massive success in dynamic monitoring of engineering structures and can provide real-time monitoring.

Real-time displacement monitoring with GNSS is highly important for detecting the damage caused by earthquakes. Nowadays, the Real-Time Kinematic Precise Point Positioning (RT-PPP) method can provide fast and accurate dynamic displacement also to check structural health and for early warning studies (Yigit et al., 2022). The network with the 6 new CORS stations was designed to have a geometry aimed at refining the existing networks in the Gargano area (RING and Puglia Region), in order to guarantee baselines of the order of 5-7 Km.

Keywords: Gargano, GNSS, PPP-RTK.

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A probabilistic multi-hazard approach from ICARIA project

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Within the ICARIA framework we are examining the implication of compound hazard events over time for both current and future climate change scenarios along with future Shared Socio-Economic Pathways (SSPs). For ease of definition, from the hazard modelling perspective we regard a multi-hazard event as being an event where the modelled hazards are affecting the same region (have overlapping spatial extents). With the spatial definition specified, from the temporal aspect we can consider multi-hazard events as:

1 Compound Coincident

Two or more hazards with overlapping spatial extents occurring either simultaneously or with overlapping timeframes. For instance, a low lying coastal region affected by compound flooding events due to storm surge coinciding with pluvial flooding.

2 Compound Consecutive

Two or more hazards (dependent or independent) with overlapping spatial extents but in place of overlapping time frames these events are occurring in sequence where the effects of previous hazard/s still influence the risk/impact of current hazard. For example, a sloped forested region previously impacted from extreme wind may have reduction in tree canopy cover resulting in increased surface runoff from rainfall events resulting in increased flooding.

From the modelling perspective, multiple hazards with overlapping spatial and temporal extents can be regarded as a multi-hazard event.

Based on these definitions of compound events, ICARIA is seeking to create a framework for modelling hazard chain pathways that depicts a chain of events that begins within an initial triggering event and captures potential interactions with other hazards and triggering events over time along with consideration of future scenarios. To capture the implications of a chain of events, we need to consider/define the interrelationships between the hazards. For this we consider the interrelationships for compound hazards outlined in Hielkema et al., (2021) where they can be defined as:

- Independent: Although hazards affecting the same region either simultaneously or in sequence, there is no triggering relationship or dependence between them. An example being an earthquake followed by a tropical storm.

- Triggering or Cascading: The effect of one hazard results in the triggering of subsequent hazard/s. For example, an earthquake followed by a tsunami.

- Change conditions: The environmental conditions within a region are changed as such where one hazard influences the likelihood of a secondary hazard occurring. For instance drought changing conditions of vegetation within landscape which in turn alters the likelihood of wildfire ignition

- Association: Where two or more hazards are the result of the same triggering event. Such as an extreme rainfall event occurring in a region with sloped terrain leading to flooding and landslides.

The general idea is to have a toolbox to be used according the specific Multi-hazard cases:

- Outline approaches used for the modelling and quantification of compound hazard events

- Joint Probability Analysis
- Markov Chains
- Monte Carlo Simulations
- Bayesian Networks

In Return starting from a such kind of definitions for multi-hazard events, the evaluation of multi-risk and the capability to evaluate impacts along the pathway and at final state is investigated combining dynamic vulnerability analyses, capable to quantify the cumulative damage on the elements at risk considered and the Socio Economic consequences.

Keywords: multihazard, multirisk, impact.

An EGF technique to infer the source parameters of a circular crack growing at a variable rupture velocity

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Circular crack models with a constant rupture velocity struggle to effectively model both the amplitude and duration of first P-wave pulses generated by small magnitude seismic events. Assuming a constant rupture velocity is unphysical, necessitating a deceleration phase in the rupture velocity to uphold the causality of the healing process. Moreover, a comprehensive failure model might encompass an initial nucleation phase, typically characterized by an increase of the initial rupture velocity. Studies have demonstrated that quasi-dynamic circular crack models featuring variable rupture velocities can accurately model the shape of the observed first P-wave pulse. Based on these principles, an Empirical Green's function (EGF) approach was previously formulated to estimate the source parameters of small magnitude earthquakes, called MAIN. In addition to determine the source radius and stress drop, this method also enables the inference of the temporal evolution of rupture velocity. However, this method encounters difficulties when the noise-to-signal ratio in the recordings of smaller earthquakes used as EGF exceeds 5%, a common situation when employing regional-scale recordings of small-magnitude earthquakes as EGF. Through synthetic tests, we demonstrated that, in such instances, the problem of this technique is that the alignment between the onset of P waves of EGF and MAIN is not rightly recovered after the initial inversion step. Consequently, a novel inversion method has been developed to address this issue, enabling the identification of the optimal alignment of P-wave arrivals in EGF and MAIN across all stations. A Bayesian statistical approach is proposed to meticulously investigate the solutions of model parameters and their correlations. Using the new technique on a small magnitude earthquake (ML=3.3) occurred in Central Italy enabled us to identify the most likely rupture models and examine the issue of correlation among model parameters. Application of Occam's Razor Principle suggests that, for the investigated event, a circular crack model should be favored over a heterogeneous rupture model.

Keywords: circular crack, variable rupture velocity, nucleation and deceleration phase.

An integrative perspective on frameworks for multi-risk research

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Multi-risk research aims to provide the instruments to describe and manage pluralities of interconnected risks in a specific area. Given the complexity of the subject, which involves several disciplines and is of interest for many geographical regions, in the relevant literature there is a multitude of alternative frameworks that aim to systematize the approach to multi-risk and provide instruments to guide risk assessment and risk management (Hochrainer-Stigler et al. 2023). This work tries to provide a perspective that integrates the main aspects of some crucial approaches, highlighting how they can be used to serve different purposes.

In most cases, the objective of a multi-risk framework is to identify the expected impacts on the exposed resources and allow to select and compare potential interventions able to reduce the impacts. In order to identify the impacts, the first step to implement a multi-risk approach is to determine a geographical and temporal reference frame to specify the potential hazards threatening the selected area.

Given the complexities of interconnected risks, multi-risk research relies on multi-level models that require a wealth of data, as well as significant time and resources. In some contexts, the extra complexity involved in multi-risk analysis may not be necessary or worthwhile. Liu et al. (2015) propose a framework that allows the modeler to determine whether, in their context of interest, multi-risk analysis can be expected to bring significantly more information than standard single-risk models, depending on factors such as the purpose of the analysis and the nature of the hazards and of their connections. The second step of our integrated perspective is therefore to run a qualitative evaluation of the context needs to assess whether a multi-risk analysis is necessary.

The third step is the construction of a matrix of the potential hazards and of their interactions for the space-time frame of interest, following the structure proposed by Gill & Malamud (2014). Once the relevant hazards are identified, it is possible to determine the resources exposed and the classes of potential impacts. Within the project RETURN, the work of TS3 WP2 provides a matrix of these classes for different types of hazards, with the relative indicators to allow impact measurement. This permits the uniform aggregation and comparison of the impacts across hazards.

The fourth step requires the creation of a Bayesian network of the hazards, which allows the propagation of probability between connected hazards: the probability of a cascade will then be the product of the probabilities of the single hazards involved (Marzocchi et al. 2012). However, probabilistic dependency between hazards is not the only type of connection in multi-risk. The occurrence of a certain hazard can impact on the exposure or on the vulnerability to some other hazard. It is therefore necessary to assess dynamic exposures and dynamic vulnerabilities, which can potentially change after some event occurs.

Finally, the total expected impacts can be calculated by aggregating the impacts that each hazard has with a certain probability (potentially dependent on other hazards) on its dynamic exposure with the relative dynamic vulnerability. The consequences of an intervention can then be measured by tweaking the data for probabilities, exposures, or vulnerabilities.

Keywords: multi-risk models, risk assessment, multi-risk scenarios.

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**Analysis of the factors affecting recovery process of
structures, infrastructures and communities considering past
Italian earthquake case studies**

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A recovery process after a destructive event like an earthquake involves a complex set of conditions, activities, and strategies. Each earthquake has a unique history, considering its impacts and the possible ways to return to or improve upon pre-event conditions. Moreover, differences between events mean that it's not possible to uniquely define strategies that will always positively or negatively affect the recovery process. However, previous experiences can help identify factors that influence these processes. Interpreting and adapting these factors to specific cases can aid decision-makers in defining the best recovery path.

In Italy, the recovery from each of the most devastating earthquakes over the past 50 years—Friuli in 1976, Irpinia in 1980, Umbria-Marche in 1997, L'Aquila in 2009, Lombardia-Emilia in 2012, and Central Italy in 2016—can be described by examining the related factors, decisions, and approaches. Each event tells stories of positive and negative processes and outcomes, with complete reconstruction still ongoing for the last three events. For each listed event, the recovery process was like starting with a blank slate, built step by step, drawing only some technical or limited aspects from previous experiences.

The recovery process had been widely analysed by researchers and institutions (as: Valeriani and Bertelli (2017), Ferrini et al. (2018), Platt (2017)), but a unique shared approach cannot be exactly established. However, the recovery process can be improved from many perspectives, not least, defining and applying procedure/plans to pre-organize its main phases, as suggested in several cases (e.g.: ATC (2021), UNDRR (2012), Bedini and Bronzini (2018)). In Italy, a law proposal (DDL, 2023) is following this direction too.

Moreover, recognizing the factors influencing the recovery process requires defining metrics. While recovery time is often considered the principal measure, it is insufficient to describe such a multifaceted process. It must be combined with measures of the quality, level, and type of expected recovery, especially when considering entire territories or communities. Additionally, a recovery process can be analyzed on different scales (country, regional, local, etc.), for different systems (building classes, single structures, lifelines, etc.), and from different perspectives (physical, social, cultural, economic, etc.). Consequently, metrics cannot be exactly the same for various cases and perspectives. Therefore, to identify the specific metrics to be used, assumptions about perspectives, recovery concepts and levels, scales, and objects must be established.

Based on lessons learned from past Italian cases, this study proposes a framework that organizes influential factors in the recovery process and analyzes their effects on the timing and efficiency at different scales of the recovery process. Specifically, the framework is divided into (i) pre-event factors, divided into event-independent and risk-related factors; (ii) post-event factors, divided into emergency management factors, recovery organization factors, and recovery activity factors. Time is the ordering factor, but not necessarily the one that determines the success of the process.

Keywords: recovery process, event singularity, complex factors interactions.

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Assessment of source processes and wave propagation mechanisms in fossil and active seismic structures: a multidisciplinary study from the Voltri massif (Genoa, Italy)

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The assessment of source processes and wave propagation mechanisms in heterogeneous rock media represent one of the most challenging frontiers to improve local seismic risk assessment. In this framework, the sector of the Voltri Massif located in the densely populated hinterland of the city of Genoa (NW Italy) is a natural laboratory to investigate (i) the triggering mechanisms controlling the switch from ductile to brittle deformation in serpentinites, (ii) the space/time relationships existing between multiple (and repeated) brittle events, (iii) the interaction between rock faulting and fluid circulation during (potential) paleo-seismic activity and (iv) the source characterization of micro-earthquakes along tectonic lineaments developed inland and offshore the city (i.e., in the Ligurian Sea; Morelli et al., 2023). Our multi-scale and multidisciplinary study, will include the structural/petrographic characterization of fault rocks (i.e., serpentinite breccias, microbreccia and gouges), the quantification of fluid-rock interaction and its impact on the fault strength, coupled to the analysis of the spatial distribution of serpentine-rich faults networks.

The detailed structural mapping and petrographic characterization of selected fault zones have revealed a complex, multi-stage deformation history, with older ductile structures (i.e., “Alpine-stage fabrics”, paragenesis: antigorite + ilmenite ± chlorite ± pyrite ± chalcopyrite, likely ascribed to the alpine subduction and exhumation stages) cut by steeply dipping fault planes NNE-SSW striking. These latter (oriented subparallel with the low magnitude seismic clusters detected in the area) develop multiple, anastomosed fault cores consisting of serpentinite-rich ultracataclasites (with antigorite-rich clasts bounded by matrix consisting of chrysotile ± polygonal serpentinite) locally bounded by polygonal serpentine-rich (±chrysotile) shear bands. The faults damage zones textures (e.g., breccias and microbreccias), the paragenesis of newly formed shear bands and associated veins coupled to the orientation of these faults (NNE-SSW striking, subparallel to the Miocene-age lineaments detected in the Gulf of Genoa) suggest recent tectonic reactivation at the regional scale.

Future developments of the research project will include the evaluation of the PT conditions of chrysotile matrices and polygonal-serpentine shear bands formation, the assessment of the impact on the rock strength caused by the crystallization of the newly-formed chrysotile/polygonal serpentine domains and the analysis of the network of inland-offshore tectonic lineaments. This work will be crucial to identify suitable areas for the deployment of high-resolution seismometers and for tracing the spatial-temporal evolution of micro-earthquakes and their static and dynamic source parameters.

Keywords: serpentinite, Ligurian Sea, micro-earthquakes.

Bracing System Development based on Topology Optimization Algorithm

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The interaction between the optimization code and the computed geometry in VPL was made possible through a C# component developed in Visual Studio. The expanded MATLAB – based code can handle dynamic loading that changes in magnitude, direction, and location over time, as well as random ground accelerations $u \ddot{g}$. The finite-element analysis (FEA) routine uses the HHT- α method (Hilber et al. 1977), which is a generalisation of the Newmark- β method that maintains unconditional stability for a suitable choice of parameters. This method is well suited for problems with many degrees of freedom because the α parameter tends to dampen high-frequency modes with minimal effect on lower frequency modes. The developed interface allows users to connect any geometry or meshing system (structured and unstructured) with the VPL (Grasshopper 3D®), for designing bracing systems subjected to dynamic loading for tall buildings. The process requires the (i) selection of passive areas, that is, those areas that represent a constraint in the optimisation phase, (ii) selection of the support points, (iii) selection of the connectivity, (iv) localisation of the concentrated masses, and if present, (v) the subdivision into subareas.

Keywords: topology optimization, retrofitting system, computational design.

Building Characterisation and Damage Estimation Based on Ground Motion Records in Northeast Italy

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Estimating the dynamic behaviour of structures plays a major role in determining a given building's response to seismic load. Determining a structure's seismic response leads to predicting expected damage during an earthquake. Thanks to projects such as VenetONE and ARMONIA, seismic monitoring infrastructures are installed in numerous buildings in northeast Italy to determine their behaviour. Those buildings provide vital information about the possible seismic load on the buildings and their adjacent regions.

This study determines the inter-story drift of the structures monitored by stations on the ground and top floors. To do this, buildings monitored in the ARMONIA project are selected as case studies. During that project, the fundamental periods of the monitored structures were characterised. Using the period information, displacement on the top floor is determined by the method of Jin et al. (2004), which is also implemented successfully in the region by Scaini et al. (2021). In this method, buildings are assumed to behave as a Single Degree of Freedom (SDoF) system, which is a good approximation as most monitored buildings are 1- to 4-story. Predicted time histories of the motion on the top floor are compared with observations from the stations on the top floor.

A second method is developed based on the earthquakes recorded by the seismic instruments on the buildings. In this method, the transfer function of the buildings is retrieved by using the height information of the buildings along with the mean shear wave velocity, which is retrieved using the deconvolution approach (Sneider and Safak 2006). Records at the top floor are used as a reference to retrieve the velocity model of the building in the recorded waveforms. From the deconvolved wavefield, propagation velocity is retrieved. With the velocity and height information, a given building is modelled as an elastic body and fundamental and higher modes are retrieved. Then, earthquake time history recorded on the ground floor is convolved with the frequency domain transfer function to predict the top floor's ground motion.

Both models show promising results in developing rapid estimation of damage states for the region. By predicting the motion on the top, one can calculate the inter-story drift, which can then be used as an indicator of the damage levels.

Keywords: rapid damage estimation; seismic monitoring; building characterisation.

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Decision support tools for allocating economic resources in seismic retrofitting of residential buildings

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A significant number of existing masonry and reinforced concrete (RC) buildings in Italy are situated in regions with medium-to-high seismic hazard and are particularly susceptible to earthquakes. Despite the urgent need for strengthening interventions, limited resources make retrofitting the entire building stock impractical. Therefore, it is essential to optimize resource

allocation for strengthening interventions, considering cost constraints and various factors related to repair and indirect costs, such as the number of inhabitants, building priority and size, and vulnerability level. This work addresses the decision-making process for optimal budget allocation for proactive strengthening actions on buildings in seismic areas and reactive repairs following an earthquake. The objective is to minimize the number of uninhabitable buildings by considering their capacity in terms of residents. A two-stage stochastic model with recursions is employed for the analyses, assuming a maximum cumulative budget that can be used for both proactive (strengthening) and reactive (reconstruction) actions. The solution of this stochastic problem is compared to the scenario where the budget is used solely for reactive actions. The results are presented and discussed with reference to a real case study of a small town in Sicily.

Keywords: seismic hazard, resource allocation optimization, stochastic model.

Deep vs shallow magmatic systems controlling pure Plinian vs caldera-forming eruptions: experimental constraints from analcime stability field

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In the context of Quaternary potassic volcanoes of Central Italy, Ventotene Island is a good example that records a change in eruptive style, shifting from pure Plinian events (Cala

Battaglia eruptions; UCB below) to an under-pressure caldera-forming eruption (Parata Grande eruption; PGT below).

In light of the different chemical and textural features of UCB and PGT juvenile clasts, among which is the notable occurrence of primary analcime in UCB, we infer the existence of two different magma feeder systems: i) magma batches that underwent a polybaric differentiation at different depths during ascent (UCB) and ii) a shallower, sill-like magma chamber that drove the PGT caldera-forming event. In UCB natural samples, the chemical and morphological characteristics of analcime, such as the absence of reaction rims, the abundance of Na₂O with respect to K₂O and the increase of K₂O from crystal core to rim, rule out the hypothesis of secondary origin for this phase.

In order to constrain the analcime stability field and to test our working hypothesis, two series of crystallization experiments were performed with a Piston cylinder at pressures of 150 and 600 MPa and temperature range of 700-900 °C, using as starting material an over-saturated phonolite (H₂O ~ 10 wt%), collected from UCB deposit. The target conditions were held for 3 hours.

All the experiments point to the coexistence of vesicular glass and crystalline phases. Specifically, the low-pressure set yields a K-feldspar+plagioclase+Ti-magnetite mineral assemblage, while the high-pressure experiments (PH₂O=600 MPa) produce a paragenesis that consists of plagioclase+biotite+Ti-magnetite±K-feldspar and analcime. The latter mineral phase is ≤20 μm in size, euhedral with hexagonal habit, and shows Na₂O/K₂O ratio ~ 1 and Fe₂O₃ content ~2 wt%. The high K content suggests an enlargement of the analcime stability field in K-rich phonolitic melts, where the cotectic crystallization of K-rich analcime and plagioclase seems to precede that of K-feldspar, whose crystallization at high PH₂O may occur through the reaction K-analcime+melt=K-feldspar+Na-analcime. On the other hand, the experiments at PH₂O=150 MPa on the phonolitic composition do not show the presence of analcime, in agreement with the literature [e.g. Henderson, 2014]. The synthesis of K-analcime might also suggest its occurrence as metastable phase at low pressure, where it may have the hidden effect of decreasing the activation energy of the leucite + Na + H₂O = analcime reaction. These preliminary experiments indicate that the pressure parameter plays a key role in controlling the differentiation of a H₂O-saturated K-phonolitic magma and that analcime is unable to crystallize from these magmas in shallow (<150 MPa) reservoirs. This piece of evidence supports the hypothesis that the depth of the pre-eruptive magma system, i.e., high vs low depth/width roof aspect ratio, is a primary factor controlling pure Plinian vs caldera forming events.

Keywords: potassic magmatism, analcime stability field, magma chamber depth.

Development of semi-analytical Fourier-domain ground motion prediction model for rapid earthquake hazard scenario calculation

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The choice of ground motion estimates used for seismic impact scenario calculation plays a key role in determining how well post-event impact estimates can be constrained. A common solution is to use synthetic waveform simulations, which are analytically accurate but usually have the disadvantage of using limited frequencies below 1 or 2 Hz and are computationally time consuming.

As a complementary approach, we aim to produce ground shaking estimates in the Fourier domain using a semi-analytical modelling technique consisting of two parts, one for modelling the Fourier Amplitude Spectra (FAS) and one for modelling the corresponding phase spectra. Combining the results of the two models yields realistic time-domain ground motion estimates that contain information from a wider frequency range and require less computational time than fully analytical simulations (e.g. Bora et al. 2015). This activity is carried out in synergy with the RETURN Task 4.4 of VP3, which is dedicated to the improvement of real-time risk mitigation measures.

To improve the accuracy of the ground motion estimates computed in near real-time, the models must be carefully calibrated in advance by inverting observational data. A test area in north-eastern Italy was selected, where many regional monitoring institutions provide good data coverage (e.g. Bragato et al. 2021). A dataset of 837 events that occurred in the area between 2016 and 2024 was selected and processed to create the spectral database used for the calibration. The calibration process aims on the one hand, to validate the theoretical choices made for the analytical model components and, on the other hand, to estimate the empirical components to be included in the forward model for the hazard calculation.

Keywords: ground motion prediction, seismic hazard scenario.

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Enhancing The Passive Monitoring of The Rock Damage Process

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Low-cost monitoring of incipient leaks from structurally trapped CO² must rely on accurate microseismicity locations to proactively address pore-pressure management and prevent damage from growing into bursts. Double-difference location has been used for high-resolution hypocenters, mapping the evolving fractures. However, accounting for time-lapse velocity changes, inherent to any damage process, remains an issue. Spatial-proximity of microseisms does not imply temporal-proximity within each damage stage, and by proxy, velocity changes are usually captured through expensive 4D seismic imaging. This study tested the role of point-in-time, average (2D) velocity variations in the accuracy of double-difference location of acoustic emissions (AEs) acquired in the laboratory and compared their spatial-temporal evolution against patterns of cracks coalescing into the main fracture imaged via X-ray Microtomography.

We performed a triaxial mechanical test on Berea sandstone while monitoring stress, strain, AEs, and acoustic velocity in time-lapse. P-wave arrival times from AEs were automatically picked and then manually refined to perform an absolute location of the events. AE magnitudes were calculated from the first peak of the P-wave and source-receiver distance. We used a traditional (constant-velocity) double-difference approach using catalog and cross-correlation differential times, which we then compared with an approach that includes temporal average velocity changes accruing with or causally linked to damage.

Results, Observations, Conclusions: During the initial stress stages pertaining to the sample elastic deformation, no AE activity is detected. AEs are observed increasing sharply over damage with cracks propagating and culminating into failure. Despite the use of the advanced double-difference technique, the AEs distribution appears highly clustered in the center of the sample (i.e., points farther away from the sensors) when the velocity measured at the onset of the experiment across the intact sample is maintained constant. Hence, the technique fails to accurately map the actual fracture geometry. Conversely, a more reliable co-location of the AEs distribution with the fracture geometry emerges when the double-difference technique makes use of point-in-time velocity changes measured over the damage stages. The AE distribution provides a clear time-lapse image of microcracks initiating at the bottom of the sample, and then propagating and coalescing inward along the direction of the main stress.

Novel/Additive Information: Permanent arrays provide cheap and continuous passive monitoring for injection-related microseismicity. This study shows that traditional double-differences lead to events overclustering, likely due to the need to make up for the slowness of the damaged zone, and demonstrates that point-in-time velocity changes accruing with damage are needed for an improved distribution of crack-generated events. While evolving, events align more closely to the actual fracture architecture, thus allowing for tracking the cracking progress. Average velocity changes can be measured during injection across wells or derived from the calibration of rock physics models

Keywords: rock physics, laboratory experiment, seismic monitoring.

Estimation of Source Parameters of Earthquakes from Fourier Phase Spectra Fitting

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The estimation of the parameters of an earthquake is of fundamental importance to improving our knowledge of the physics of the rupture that gives rise to a seismic event. In particular, the corner frequency (f_c) provides information on the high-frequency radiation, which is of great importance in seismic hazard studies. However, the estimation of f_c through spectral-fitting methods suffers from trade-offs with the estimation of seismic wave attenuation. This makes the obtained values precise but not necessarily accurate. For this reason, first, following a review of the source model proposed by Brune (1970), a new method, based on the phase fitting of Fourier spectra of the seismic pulse related to S waves, called Fourier phase spectra fitting (FPS) is proposed and evaluated for small to moderate events.

Secondly, the method is being tested on an extended source model, e.g. Haskell (1964), with particular attention paid to avoiding trade-off issues between arrival time and rupture time.

The method can be applied in cases where the models may be appropriate, while also considering the effects of propagation on impulse deformation, as demonstrated by the synthetic tests. For Brune model, the results, obtained initially using synthetic seismograms generated under controlled conditions and subsequently on a data set of recordings of real seismic events collected at the Groningen gas field in the Netherlands, demonstrated the method to be both promising and limited in its applicability. While the method was found to be accurate and precise, its applicability was restricted to moment magnitudes of less than 4 and to hypocentral distances of less than 20 km. The conditions under which the Haskell model can be applied have yet to be determined. However, the combination of the two models should be able to accommodate a wide range of magnitudes.

Keywords: earthquakes, source parameters, Fourier spectra.

Evidence for Inversely Related Rupture Velocity and Stress Drop from Mw 3+ Campi Flegrei Caldera (Southern Italy) Earthquakes

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In recent years, there has been a growing interest for high precision estimates of earthquake rupture parameters in volcanic areas to provide a better understanding of faulting mechanisms associated with magmatic and/or hydrothermal activities for a better assessment of seismic risk during volcanic unrest episodes. With the recent deployment of spatially dense, high-dynamics/wide-frequency-band sensor networks on volcanoes, earthquake source parameters can be estimated with unprecedented resolution, allowing for the in-depth exploration of the relationship between fracture mechanisms and fluid-bearing volcanic rock properties.

Here we propose a new method to determine the earthquake rupture velocity along with seismic moment, rupture radius and stress release for the largest magnitude (Mw 3.3+) earthquake sequence occurring during the 2022-2023 volcanic unrest in Campi Flegrei caldera (south Italy). The method jointly uses the time-domain measurements of P and S pulse half-durations, assuming a circular rupture propagating at uniform speed and static stress-drop.

The results show that no considered event ruptures exceed the shear wave velocity, and that rupture velocity shows a significant anticorrelation with stress drop. Among different hypotheses, involving flash heating or thermal pressurization, this evidence can be explained by a dissipative mechanism of the fracture energy that involves the creation of a plastic off-fault damage zone whose thickness increase with the level of stress triggering the fracture and on the consequent drop to the dynamic friction during the rupture propagation. Considering the ratio of the damage thickness zone and the total rupture length, we obtain a relationship showing that the shape of the damage zone influences the rupture evolution by controlling its velocity. Since the radiated body-wave pulse duration and amplitude critically depends on stress drop and rupture velocity our results help to investigate the effects of fracture complexity in a volcanic environment on the radiated wave-field and strong ground shaking.

Keywords: Campi Flegrei, source parameters, time domain.

Fault (re)activation and fluid-induced seismicity: an example from the Val d'Agri intermontane basin (southern Italy)

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Over the last few years, the occurrence of several fluid-induced seismic events around the globe sparked interest in the relationships between fluids and seismicity. A large number of studies suggest that variations of rocks' stress state, due to the increase or drop of the pore fluid pressure, are a suitable mechanism that can trigger earthquakes.

In this framework, the Val d'Agri represents a precious case study where the effect of fluids on seismic activity is observed. In this region, reinjection of wastewater from oil extraction activity reactivated the Costa Molina blind thrust in the eastern sector of the Val d'Agri, where previous seismic activity was almost absent. A few kilometers SW from this cluster, seasonal water loading from the artificial Pertusillo reservoir generates further seismicity within the buried carbonatic platform. The formation and evolution of the faults that generate seismicity at the present day are still a matter of debate, especially in the compressional/extensional tectonic setting characterizing the southern Apennines geological history. As a consequence, the distribution of the seismic potential in the region is mostly unconstrained.

Therefore, we built up a 2D numerical, thermo-mechanical model to identify the main mechanisms generating the present-day tectonic setting in the Val d'Agri and the surrounding region, and to assess the seismic hazard that characterizes this area. We suggest that a major décollement layer decouples deformation between the sedimentary cover and the crystalline basement. This layer is constituted by the Triassic Burano Formation. Our model quantifies the stress tensor and estimates Coulomb stress values in the Val d'Agri crust, allowing to assess the potential of the rocks to generate earthquakes.

We find that Coulomb stress is positive in a large part of the crust, consequently fluid injection may be particularly hazardous for the reactivation of buried structures, especially within the carbonatic platform at a depth between 2 and 6 km.

Keywords: Val d'Agri, numerical models, induced seismicity.

Fine particles and roughness effects on the granular flows mobility: insights from large-scale experiments

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Dry granular flows are gravity-driven mixtures of discrete grains that belong to the family of multiphase flows and are prevalent in a wide range of volcanological scenarios (e.g. pyroclastic density currents, block and ash flows, debris avalanches, etc.). These flows are polydisperse in terms of grain size and density and their flow characteristics are mainly governed by particle-particle collisions and frictional forces acting at the boundaries. These boundary forces are influenced by several factors, including the presence of fine particles and the roughness of the basal surface, both of which can affect the energy dissipation at the flow base and consequently, the flow mobility. These two factors were investigated through large-scale laboratory experiments, in which dry granular mixtures were released onto a sloped channel. The flow parameters were monitored using various sensors, including 15 laser barriers for flow front velocities, 5 load cells for bottom pressures, 3 highly sensitive pore pressure sensors, 1 high-speed camera (2000 fps) and 2 medium-high speed cameras (120 fps – 240 fps) for flow velocimetry. Different granular mixtures and experimental set-up were used to study the behaviour of granular flows under various conditions: i) ratio between the coarser and finer solid phases ($d_{\text{ratio}} = d_{\text{coarse}}/d_{\text{fine}}$); ii) weight percentage of the fine content ($d_{\text{fine}}(\%)$); iii) ratio between the roughness of the sliding surface and size of the finest particles (k). Preliminary results indicated that: 1) the greater d_{ratio} and $d_{\text{fine}}(\%)$, the lower the runouts of the granular flows; 2) the greater k , the higher the runouts. This study explores the dual effect of the fine content and its interaction with the basal roughness on granular flow seismological and instrumental records furnishing reference hazard levels pivotal for the correct management of seismo-volcanic crises at Campi Flegrei.

Keywords: dry granular flows, large-scale experiments, roughness.

First results of a rheological characterization protocol for fine volcanic sediment suspensions

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The physical behavior of lahars depends on the interaction between their two constitutive phases: the solid phase (consisting of large volcanic blocks) and the liquid phase (consisting of a suspension of fine sediments and water). Whereas the solid phase exhibits a collisional and/or a frictional regime, the liquid phase exhibits a viscous regime, which means that the application of shear stress results in the deformation of a fluid.

The characterization of the rheological behavior of volcanic sediment and water suspensions is one of the most important parameters for estimating lahar hazard from numerical simulations. Although, a standardized methodology has not been developed to obtain the viscosity and yield strength values of sediment and water suspensions in a consistent way throughout the literature. In addition, most of the previous rheologically characterized materials are of non-volcanic nature, e.g. mine tailings and soils.

The main focus of this work was to propose a standard methodology for the rheological characterization of suspensions of fine volcanic sediments and water. The evaluated variables were related to strain rate conditions and time conditions. For the first case, we carried out experiments with different ranges and functions of shear rate, while for the second case we carried out experiments with different measurement times.

We performed the rheological characterization of fine volcanic sediment suspensions with a maximum diameter of 63 microns, comprising silt and clay sizes. An Anton Paar rheometer with a rotational concentric cylinder geometry was used in a range of strain rates between 10⁻² y 10³ s⁻¹.

The first results of this work show that the rheological parameters values are strongly dependent on the methodology used to characterize them. We conclude that the best experimental method to characterize yield strength at low shear rates is achieved by applying the strain condition within a logarithmic ramp function. Whereas the most effective method for calculating apparent viscosity and fitting a rheological model at high shear rates is achieved by applying a constant interval function of shear rates over time. We expect to make a comparison of the experimental data obtained by both methods.

Keywords: rheology, lahar, protocol.

Fossil chemical-physical (dis)equilibria between paleofluids and host rocks and their relationship to the seismic cycle and earthquakes

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Understanding the behavior of fluids in seismically active faults and their chemical-physical (dis)equilibrium with the host rock is important to understand the role of fluids upon seismicity and their possible potential for forecasting earthquakes. The small number of case studies where seismic and geochemical data are available and the lack of accessibility to fault zones at seismogenic depth for recent earthquakes limit our understanding of fluid circulation and its relationship to seismicity. The study of fault-fluid relationships in exhumed faults can broaden the number of case histories and improve our understanding of the role of fluids in the seismic cycle in different tectonic settings. Here we use new geochemical and thermal data and a review of published studies from the Apennines fold-and-thrust belt (Italy) to provide a model of fluid circulation during the seismic cycle related to either the local orogenic compressional or post-orogenic extensional tectonics. We also suggest a workflow based upon different methods to identify tectonic-related chemical-physical (isotopic and thermal) (dis)equilibria in fluid-rock systems during the seismic cycle. The proposed workflow involves multiscale structural and isotope geochemical analyses, radiometric dating, and burial-thermal modeling. It is applied to carbonate-hosted faults exhumed from a depth shallower than 4 km (temperature $\leq \sim 130$ °C and pressure $\leq \sim 130$ MPa). We show that in the Apennines, during syn-orogenic shortening, thrusting is mostly assisted by fluid circulation in an effectively closed system where fluid and host rock remain close to chemical and thermal equilibrium. In contrast, post-orogenic normal faulting occurs in association with upward and/or downward open fluid circulation systems leading to chemical-physical disequilibria between the host rock and the circulating fluids. Isotopic and thermal fluid-rock disequilibria are particularly evident during pre- and co-seismic extensional deformation. Mineralizing fluids, whose temperature can vary between 30° C warmer and 16° C colder than the host rock, result from the mixing of fluids derived from both the deforming host rock and external sources (meteoric or deep crustal). The proposed workflow offers the potential to track past seismic cycles and provide indications on actual fluid-earthquake relationships including the identification of potential seismic precursors and modes of triggered seismicity that might be different in extensional and compressional tectonic settings.

Keywords: earthquakes, fluid-rock interaction, seismic precursors.

Global Format Method for Reinforced Concrete Structures: Global Structural Resistance as a function of Reinforcement Strain

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This study describes a novel methodology within the Global Resistance Format (GRF) to assess the design value of the global structural resistance of reinforced concrete (RC) structures as a function of the peak reinforcement strain (i.e., $\epsilon_{s,max}$). Several experimental tests on RC structural members have been selected from the literature (Leonhardt and Walther, 1966; Lefas and Kotsovos, 1990; Filho, 1995; Foster and Gilbert, 1998) and numerically reproduced by means of non-linear numerical analyses (NLNAs). The experimental outcomes are characterized by both brittle and ductile failure modes. The NLN models have been defined assuming specific modelling hypotheses aimed to simulate the experimental results in terms of both resistance and resisting mechanism.

Successively, considering the mechanical uncertainties (JCSS, 2001), a comprehensive probabilistic analysis of 30 NLN simulations for each RC structure is developed to characterize the probabilistic distribution of the global structural resistance. The concrete has been assumed as a random variable with a coefficient of variation (CoV) equal to $V_c=0.15$, whereas the CoV of the reinforcement steel is equal to $V_s=0.05$. Therefore, for each RC system, the mean value and CoV of the global structural resistance ($V_{R,m}$) have been computed.

Then, these statistics have been correlated with the ratio between the peak and yielding strain (i.e., $\epsilon_{s,max}/\epsilon_y$) monitored in the reinforcement characterizing the resisting mechanism for each RC structure. For each RC system, the peak strain in the reinforcement is the result achieved from a NLNA having the mean values as input data for the material properties.

In this way, a predictive expression has been proposed to define the statistical parameters of the global structural resistance as a function of the peak reinforcement strain. These results allow to apply easily the GRF to determine the design value of the global structural resistance according to the target reliability levels for RC structures for load scenarios.

Keywords: global structural resistance, reinforcement strain, material uncertainties.

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Holistic resilience modelling and assessment framework: integrating loss reduction with socio-economic and environmental co-benefits

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Understanding the effects of combined hazards on complex socio-eco-technical urban and regional systems is crucial to identifying measures that enhance both coping and adaptive capacities in local contexts. A holistic multi-hazard impact modelling framework incorporating evolutionary resilience approaches is proposed grounded on previous EU projects and findings from RETURN. The framework is aimed at reconciling the conventionally siloed approaches to risk and resilience assessment in the fields of geophysical hazards and climate change research, in accordance with the AR6 framework (IPCC, 2022). This integration requires resilience components to be connected to the conventional risk-based approach, defining corresponding quantitative metrics to support the inclusion of resilience pathways within the complete Disaster Risk Management (DRM) cycle (UNISDR, 2015; Zuccaro et al., 2018).

In the RETURN VS3 framework, resilience assessment is directly linked to impact scenario analysis through hazard-specific impact models, with resilience measures in place to evaluate their effectiveness in reducing impacts. This implies that the variation of Hazard, Exposure and Vulnerability parameters induced by resilience measures can be quantified through such models (WP6). Furthermore, the multi-dimensional nature of co-benefits of resilience strategies and measures – spanning from socio-economic to environmental aspects – requires an expansion of the assessment framework beyond the impact/loss reduction modelling approach (WP7). In order to transfer advanced tools and approaches for risk reduction to the various governance areas, it is essential that information derived from hazard/impact models can be combined with specific resilience assessment indicators, and further processed through cost-benefit and multi-criteria analyses, designed to offer decision-makers detailed information on the pros and cons of different intervention alternatives, but above all making clear the benefits deriving from synergistic actions (for example seismic risk and energy efficiency, or volcanic risk and climate adaptation).

Unlike hazard, risk and impact models, which are strongly oriented towards quantitative assessments, resilience metrics (T7.1) have always suffered from the prevalence of hybrid approaches, with strong qualitative components and characterized by a very high number of variables relating to the systems physical aspects, organizational aspects and interaction between decision makers, stakeholders and communities, which have historically undermined their effective applicability in a decision support context. The task, in synergy with TS1, proposes

a methodological approach based on quantitative parameters also to aspects linked to governance issues and the measurement of social, economic and environmental co-benefits.

The goal of a harmonized framework for multi-hazard risk and impact assessments represents one of the central objectives of the RETURN project. Starting from a rigorous taxonomy linked to the concepts of hazard, exposure and vulnerability, as well as from the definition of common spatial and temporal units through which to carry out assessments for the different types of geophysical and climatic hazards considered the spoke will contribute to strengthening a systematic and replicable multi-risk approach in different geographical contexts and scales of analysis (region, municipality, grid)

In this context, with respect to vulnerability (T6.2), important advancements relevant for both geophysical and climate hazards specifically concern its dynamic dimension, e.g. in relation to the processes of aging and degradation, with reference to urban and demographic growth (particularly relevant for climate-related hazards), and in relation to the theme of cumulative damage, peculiar of both seismic (e.g. presence of seismic swarms with a sequence of slightly damaging earthquakes) and volcanic (relating to the specific phenomenology of explosive eruptions and the EQ-AF-PF sequence), taking into account in the analysis the possible variations in terms of vulnerability classes due to the specific evolution of hazard event.

In this perspective, innovative approaches to mitigation and adaptation (T6.3) are aimed at classifying technical solutions in relation to their ability to offer, alongside the reduction of expected impacts from seismic and volcanic events, direct benefits in relation to priority environmental aspects, primarily linked to climate change, both in terms of mitigation (reduction of CO₂ emissions in the life cycle of products and systems) and adaptation (reduction of impacts from extreme events such as heat waves, surface flooding and river/coastal flooding). Furthermore, for each measure the social, environmental and economic co-benefits linked to their use should always be identified, in order to favor, with equal effects in terms of mitigation/adaptation, solutions capable of determining positive effects with respect to the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals).

In the transition from technical solutions for mitigation/adaptation to their integration in the urban and peri-urban context (T6.4), the priority of identifying strategies capable of simultaneously contributing to the objectives of climate neutrality and climate adaptation presupposes a strong integration between different disciplinary fields, combining the skills of engineering type with those of architectural and urban studies, alongside aspects related to urban ecology and social sciences, so as to contribute to the overall improvement of the resilience of urban and metropolitan systems starting from strategic visions shared with local authorities, public and private stakeholders and community.

Keywords: holistic impact/resilience modelling framework, resilience-oriented and climate-proofing rehabilitation, holistic resilience metrics and multi-objective strategies.

Interrelationship between the seismic velocity and attenuation, and electrical resistivity (ρ) parameters using rock-physics modelling resilience

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Understanding the interplay between seismic and electrical properties of porous rocks is crucial for assessing fluid distribution and seismic hazard in earthquake-prone regions. This study investigates the complex relationship between seismic velocity, V_p and V_s , and the Quality Factor (Q) together (Pride, 2005) with electrical resistivity (ρ) in porous media (Brace and Orange, 1966; Cai et al., 2017) within such zones using rock physics modeling. Various factors such as pore fluid properties, porosity, saturation, rock texture, and frequency dependence of Q are considered. The study highlights how fluid type, porosity, and fluid mobility influence V_p , V_s , Q and ρ . Additionally, the impact of rock texture, mineralogy, and temperature-pressure effects on these properties is explored. Integrating seismic and electrical data with rock physics modeling provides insights into fluid distribution and migration, aiding in seismic hazard assessment in earthquake zones. The present study contributes to a comprehensive understanding of fluid-rock interactions and their implications for joint seismic and electrical properties of rocks within earthquake-prone regions and is a premise for quantitative interpretation of multidisciplinary imaging of seismogenic areas.

Keywords: Resistivity, seismic velocity, attenuation.

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Investigation of seismic-electromagnetic effects in Southern Italy: implications for fluids detection and earthquakes precursors

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Fluids in porous or fractured media can generate electrokinetic effects, where seismic and electromagnetic fields are coupled. Co-seismic electric effect as well as independent – so, faster - electromagnetic signals are provide by the theory. Both can bring information about fluids in the subsoil, but the latter effect can be explored as a possible earthquake precursor tool.

On the occasion of the seismic swarm of Pollino area (2011-2014) a seismic and a magnetotelluric stations were placed near the town of Campotenese (39.8941° N, 16.0844° E), in order to possibly record the seismic-electromagnetic phenomenon. The analysis has shown – besides co-seismic effects - possible pre-seismic signals. Their amplitude is weak as expected by the theory and they can resemble the electromagnetic natural background. In order to strengthen or refute the hypothesis of possible precursors, a numerical model was made based on the Pollino Massif seismic velocity model (Napolitano et al.,2020) and the electric resistivity curves for the same area. Spectral ratios between electric and seismic data have also been compute to evaluate the site-response then compared with other monitoring stations in Southern Italy.

Here we present observations and preliminary results collected from this analysis.

Keywords: seismic-electromagnetic, electrokinetic, fluids.

Life-cycle seismic reliability of aging bridges under chloride-induced corrosion in a changing climate

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Structural deterioration processes adversely affect over time the seismic reliability of aging bridges (Biondini and Frangopol, 2016). For reinforced concrete (RC) bridges, chloride-induced corrosion is particularly harmful. In addition, the detrimental effect of corrosion processes are exacerbated by climate change (Nava et al., 2023, 2024, Nasr et al., 2022). In fact, experimental studies show that an increase in both temperature and relative humidity leads to increase the concrete diffusivity. Moreover, a gradual reduction in the concrete resistivity along with an increase in temperature leads to increase the corrosion rate, that is highest for relative humidity values ranging from 65% to 85%. Furthermore, over time the corrosion rate increases due to the increase of chloride concentration and decreases due to the formation of corrosion products. It is hence important to investigate the impact of climate change effects on the life-cycle structural reliability of RC bridges exposed to corrosion, particularly if they are located in earthquake-prone regions (Chirdeep et al., 2023).

This study presents a novel framework for the life-cycle seismic reliability assessment of RC bridges under chloride-induced corrosion considering the impact of climate change. Chloride diffusion simulation and corrosion modelling are developed based on cellular automata (Biondini et al., 2004). The proposed diffusion and damage models are based on the extension of a general formulation established in previous works for life-cycle assessment of RC structures under corrosion by adapting cellular automata to account for the evolution over time of the environmental parameters that influence the initiation and propagation of corrosion, i.e., temperature and relative humidity, in a changing climate scenario.

The proposed framework is applied to the life-cycle seismic reliability of a RC bridge considering the effects of uncertainty in the mechanical and environmental damage stressors. Non-linear structural analysis is carried out at both sectional and system levels considering different climate change scenarios and the results are compared to the outcome of the assessment carried out considering the historical climate. Life-cycle seismic reliability is finally investigated based on time-variant non-linear static analysis of the bridge. The results obtained in this study allow to quantify the detrimental impact of climate change on life-cycle seismic reliability of RC bridges and highlight the importance of considering appropriate corrosion models taking into account climate change effects.

Keywords: life-cycle seismic reliability, climate change, cellular automata.

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Monitoring seismic hazard with satellite geodesy in Italy: first steps for the integration of GNSS and European Ground Motion Service data

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The potential role of satellite geodesy techniques for seismic hazard assessment, with a particular focus on GNSS and InSAR, has been widely investigated in the last decades. These technologies can detect differences in ground velocity of less than one millimetre per year, and could therefore be suitable to highlight the accumulation of tectonic strain.

While conventional strain field estimation is performed from a two-dimensional planimetric point of view, a novel approach was introduced by incorporating the independent a-priori tectonic knowledge of the study area to pre-select the directions along which strain accumulation signs should be searched (Panza et al., 2018, Crespi et al., 2020). This method was applied to the earthquakes of Amatrice (2016) and Emilia (2012), analyzing the ground velocity estimated from GNSS station data along two transects of interest. Despite the promising results obtained, the spatial density of GNSS stations was too low to provide a detailed description of the velocity profile along the transects. In this sense, combining GNSS and InSAR techniques could greatly improve these analyses. The recent European Ground Motion Service (EGMS) constitutes an ideal dataset to pursue this objective. In the present work, we evaluated the suitability of EGMS data for seismic hazard assessment. To achieve this, we defined transects covering known high seismic hazard regions of Italy, following the scheme outlined in Crespi et al., but greatly improving both the spatial resolution along the transects and their inter-distance, leveraging the high spatial density of InSAR measurement points. Starting from the work presented at EGU (Giaccio et al., 2024), we evaluated the velocity profile of each transect along the satellite line of sight and we retrieved displacements eastward and upward, considering SAR acquisitions from ascending and descending orbits.

The results confirm the possibility of retrieving high-resolution velocity profiles from InSAR data, displaying a velocity accuracy at millimetre/year or even better and good continuity, thus underlying the importance that a European public service like EGMS holds for both research and hazard monitoring purposes.

Keywords: seismic hazard, satellite geodesy, EGMS.

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Multi-hazard resilience-driven bridge management of aging bridge networks and role of adaptive recovery scenarios on seismic resilience

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Engineering structures and infrastructure systems are exposed to aging and deterioration processes and may face various natural hazards throughout their service life (Biondini and Frangopol 2016). Bridges, in particular, are highly vulnerable components of transportation networks, especially when subjected to natural disasters like earthquake sequences and riverine floods. These disasters highlight the critical role that bridges play in maintaining infrastructure functionality. The ongoing increase in greenhouse gas emissions, particularly carbon dioxide, is widely considered the primary driver of global warming and climate change, which pose significant threats to various structures, including bridges. Research has shown that climate change is responsible for an increase in the frequency and severity of hydrological extremes. Intensified future design floods are observed to increase the likelihood of scouring around river-crossing bridge piers. Additionally, global warming and climate change accelerate the aging and deterioration of materials and structural components. In light of this, life-cycle resilience metrics able to capture the capability of infrastructure facilities to sustain the effect of damaging events and recover the pre-event functionality, taking into account the effects of aging and deterioration processes, are of essence (Biondini et al. 2015).

Given these considerations, a probabilistic resilience-based prioritization framework is proposed for bridges and bridge networks exposed to mainshock- aftershocks (Jafari et al. 2024c) and considering aging and deterioration process (Jafari et al. 2023). This framework is further extended to apply to bridge networks facing multiple hazards, such as seismic sequences, floods, and corrosion processes, in a changing climate (Jafari & Biondini 2024a). The proposed approach exploits multi-objective optimization to identify optimal solutions for retrofitting and prioritizing repair activities (Jafari & Biondini 2024a). The application of this framework to bridge transportation networks demonstrate a cost-effective enhancement of resilience through strategic management of rehabilitation activities. To this purpose, it is worth noting that resilience is influenced not only by the recovery time, i.e., the rate of recovery, but also by the recovery trajectory, which establish the effectiveness of the recovery process. The recovery time and trajectory are determined by how well recovery plans are managed, taking into account financial, human, and equipment resources, as well as the effective cooperation of managers from various responsible organizations, leading to the optimal prioritization of bridges. The recovery trajectory is crucial for economic and social impacts, as recovery plans with identical recovery times but different recovery trajectories can affect these dimensions of resilience

differently. Additionally, the trip patterns and user behaviors within the bridge network evolve throughout the recovery process as connectivity between previously disconnected regions is restored. There is a notable gap in research regarding the adaptive recovery process with varying recovery times and trajectories, especially in relation to user behavior patterns and the resulting direct functional and indirect economic and social losses. Development along these lines can be found in Jafari & Biondini (2024b). The impact of different recovery strategies on bridge network resilience, considering dynamic travel demand and

Keywords: bridge networks, multi-hazards, life-cycle resilience.

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Next generation probabilistic volcanic hazard for Mt. Vesuvius

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Volcanic hazard at Vesuvius was traditionally based on the analysis of individual size classes of eruption. Size classes were defined on the base of the selection of one or two specific reference eruptions, selected among the ones that occurred in conditions similar to the present one, that is, after a rather long period of quiescence. Several works have demonstrated that, in order to produce an unbiased quantification of the hazard, it is required to consider both inter- and intra-class variability, as well as to include into the hazard quantification the potential impact of the temporal modulation in volcanic activity, like the switch between open and close-conduit conditions. Here, we present the ongoing efforts to overcome these limitations, in order to produce a procedure toward a new generation of hazard quantification.

Keywords: volcanic hazard, Vesuvius.

On-site earthquake early warning: application to Northern California

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Earthquake early warning systems are greatly effective to initiate fast real-time seismic risk mitigation actions. The goal of an EEW system is to issue real-time warnings as soon as an earthquake strikes and before potentially damaging seismic waves reach the target we want to protect. In an on-site EEW system, a single sensor (or a small array of sensors) is usually deployed near a target to be secured. The stand-alone design of on-site systems makes them suitable for sites located close to active faults areas. In this study, we show the performance and the accuracy of the on-Site Alert level system (SAVE hereinafter) on Berkeley and USGS Northern California seismic networks. SAVE makes use of the early P-wave amplitude, which is converted to the expected Peak Ground Velocity through a log-linear regression. Ultimately, the system output provides expected shaking intensity at the site, according to regional scaling laws that link P-wave amplitude to peak shaking (i.e. Modified Mercalli Intensity). The off-line test we performed on a wide range of California earthquakes recorded by BK and NC networks shows encouraging results in terms of intensity estimation, with a standard prediction error of 0.5 Δ MMI within three seconds from first event detection. Moreover, lead time increases with distance, with an averaged value of 10 seconds for stations at 50 km and more than 20 seconds for stations at 150 km. We were able to evaluate system performance in terms of Successful Alert (SA): $MMI_{pred} > MMI_{threshold}$ & $MMI_{obs} > MMI_{threshold}$; Successful No-Alert (SNA): $MMI_{pred} \leq MMI_{threshold}$ & $MMI_{obs} \leq MMI_{threshold}$; False Alert (FA): $MMI_{pred} \geq MMI_{threshold}$ & $MMI_{obs} < MMI_{threshold}$; Missed Alert (MA): $MMI_{pred} < MMI_{threshold}$ & $MMI_{obs} \geq MMI_{threshold}$, where MMI_{pred} is SAVE prediction of intensity, MMI_{obs} is true intensity at the site and $MMI_{threshold}$ is an intensity threshold that user can set in order to maximize the total number of SNA and SA. SAVE has the potential to provide onsite warnings in addition to the existing ShakeAlert network-based early warning system already operating in Northern California.

Keywords: earthquake early warning, seismology.

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Radionuclides behavior in hydrothermal volcanic systems: Preliminary investigations at high and low gas flux emission sites

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Studies over long periods at many active volcanic systems in the world revealed that radionuclides measurements in volcanic plumes provide useful indications of degassing processes in terms of volume of degassing magma, timescales of magmatic processes, chemical composition and depth of the reservoirs. In this study, we describe the preliminary results obtained from two radiometric surveys carried out between January and April 2024 at Pisciarelli (Campi Flegrei caldera, Italy) and Stephanos crater (Nisyros island, Greece), sites characterized by high and low gas flux emissions, respectively. Radioactivity measurements were collected through a scintillation gamma-ray detector in order to find potential correlations between volcanic gas (i.e., CO₂ and H₂S) and radionuclides concentrations at ground level and in atmosphere. We provided scans at four different altitudes from the ground, aiming to disentangle the contributions of the radionuclides (i.e., ²²²Rn, ²²⁰Rn, etc.) transported by the gas species diffused in the air from those contained within the rock and soil. Different volumetric profiles and 2D maps of gamma rates and gasses concentration have been plotted considering short (60 seconds) and long (600 seconds) acquisition times in multiple field spots for each scan altitude.

Keywords: radionuclides, volcanic gas dispersion, gamma-ray spectroscopy.

Recent improvements to the volcano-tectonic framework of the Campi Flegrei caldera using structural, stratigraphic, morphotectonic, and geophysical data: implications for the current unrest and seismo-volcanic hazard scenarios

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Silicic calderas usually display complex unrest behaviour as they feature collapse structures strongly influencing the following evolution, often coupled with ground deformation and monogenetic volcanism. In densely urbanized areas, these characteristics pose significant challenges to crisis management and decision-makers. This is the case of the Campi Flegrei caldera in southern Italy, where heightened ground deformation and seismicity have occurred in the last few years. These phenomena have accompanied the volcanic activity of the last 10 ka and preceded the last historical eruption.

Here, we present a review of the advancements in the comprehension of the volcano-tectonic architecture performed in the last decade based on several studies employing stratigraphic, structural, morphotectonic and geophysical techniques, including the submerged portion. The eruptive history and the structure of the volcano are shaped by the Upper-Pleistocene tectonic activity and the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) eruption at 39 ka, which is responsible for the main morphological scarps as testified by both continental and offshore structural data, as well as geomorphological studies. The outermost caldera rim encloses the western part of the city of Napoli and part of the Pozzuoli Gulf, which has been precisely mapped, confining the older volcanism beyond the caldera rim. The Neapolitan Yellow Tuff (NYT) eruption at 15 ka partially reactivated the pre-existing CI rim. The post-15 ka volcanism has focused along the caldera rim and in the NE sector, where the main hydrothermal manifestations occur. The volcanic events of the last 10 kyr are coupled with ground deformation (i.e., dome-shaped resurgence), which shares a pattern similarity to the one of the instrumental era, regardless of the total displacement during uplift and subsidence phases. Moreover, the record of continental, transitional and marine pyroclastic and volcanoclastic deposits includes exceptional evidence of seismic-induced ground liquefaction that occurred also during the last epoch of activity. The long-term (10 kyr) deformation history has been detailed at the exposed La Starza marine succession and merged with the offshore seismo-stratigraphic record. On-land structural surveying has been joined with high-resolution Digital Elevation Models of the Campi Flegrei caldera before the aggressive urbanization of the last decades, and offshore data allowed to improve the structural map, significantly different from that of the late 90s. With this in mind, some considerations on the current unrest can be made, as the seismicity and hydrothermal manifestations are taking place along the mapped faults.

The next research objectives are the compilation of seismic hazard maps based on the collected structural data, to compute the maximum seismic moment on the known faults, and to provide seismic-induced liquefaction susceptibility maps. This information aims at bridging the gap between geological and instrumental records furnishing reference hazard levels pivotal for the correct management of seismo-volcanic crises at Campi Flegrei.

Keywords: Campi Flegrei, volcano-tectonics, volcanic unrest.

Regional-scale physics-based numerical simulations of multiple ground shaking scenarios in the Irpinia region (Southern Italy) for seismic risk assessment

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In the framework of the Work Package WP7 - Task 7.2 of RETURN Project, focused on the development of a methodology for the estimation of dynamic risk maps for multi-objective intervention strategies, efforts have been made to identify a benchmark case study for the physics-based numerical simulation (PBS) of a major earthquake and of its aftershocks at regional scale. As a matter of fact, PBS of seismic wave propagation in complex 3D geological configurations have become a promising and feasible approach to provide region-specific ground shaking scenarios and site-specific ground motion time series in those conditions where recordings are still scarce, such as in the proximity of the seismic source or for regional-scale hazard and risk assessments.

In this study, the Irpinia area (Southern Italy), one of the highest seismic hazard regions in Italy hit by the devastating Mw6.8 November 23rd 1980 earthquake (the strongest instrumental earthquake in the history of Italy), is selected as case study to generate 3D physics-based ground shaking scenarios for multiple shocks and, starting from these scenarios, to investigate the interaction among different hazards (e.g. earthquakes, landslides), vulnerabilities and exposures

(infrastructure networks, urban aggregates) in a dynamic context. The simulations are performed by the open-source high-performance numerical code SPEED - SPectral Elements in Elastodynamics with Discontinuous Galerkin (<http://speed.mox.polimi.it/>), developed at Politecnico di Milano by the Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering and the Department of Mathematics. SPEED is conceived to perform the physics-based numerical simulation of the three-dimensional seismic wave propagation in heterogeneous Earth media including, in a single computational domain, the seismic source, the propagation path and local site response features (Mazzieri et al. 2013).

A large-scale (150 km x 110 km x 22 km) 3D numerical model of the Irpinia area has been constructed, verified and validated. The validation of the model has been accomplished by the simulation of the 1980 historical earthquake and the comparison with the available recordings. A set of parametric analyses has been performed to check the sensitivity of several input parameters on the simulated results, regarding the frequency resolution of the mesh, the size of the computational domain, the kinematic seismic source and the subsoil model. As regards the source, two distinct finite-fault source models have been investigated: a single-fault model and a multi-segment fault model with three main rupture episodes nucleating at about 0, 20 and 40 s.

Numerical simulations, enriched in the high frequency range to generate broadband predictions for engineering aims, were found to be in reasonable agreement with available recordings (albeit limited in number and in quality because of traditional analog type), in both time and frequency domain, and with empirical ground motion models. The velocity wavefield and ground shaking maps show a realistic pattern, pointing out, in particular, directivity effects in the North and North-West direction in the proximity of the main causative fault.

Starting from the simulation of the 1980 earthquake, realizations of plausible aftershocks, following the mainshock of moment magnitude $M_w=6.8$, with M_w ranging from about 5.2 to 6.3, are addressed in order to simulate a seismic sequence. The output of these simulations, in the form of ground shaking scenarios for multiple seismic events, will be used as input for the study of the phenomena related to other risks, such as land- and flow-slides or Nathec events, and for life-cycle risk-based analysis of bridge network and critical infrastructure in a dynamic context.

Keywords: earthquake ground motion, physics-based numerical simulation, seismic risk.

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Seismic attenuation in the Southern Apennines: two examples from Val d'Agri (Basilicata) and Gargano (Apulia)

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Southern Italy can be considered as a natural laboratory for studying seismic attenuation. For this purpose, we have chosen two specific areas: the High Agri Valley, located in the axial portion of Southern Apennine chain, and the Gargano Promontory, sited in the foreland area.

Agri Valley

We performed a study of the Q coda parameter (Q_c), which provides information about both the physical state of the crust (possible presence of fluids, or thermal anomalies, or ductile rock volumes) and heterogeneities in the crust. Indeed, it takes into account both the contribution of scattering and anelastic attenuation experienced by seismic waves in their propagation. The investigated area has a strong seismogenic potential and, in the last decades, a low magnitude natural seismicity has been recorded. In addition, two anthropogenic seismicity clusters are documented, related to the exploitation of the Val d'Agri oilfield and to the effects of the water table oscillations of the Pertusillo lake. We selected a dataset of about 1800 events ($0 < M_L < 3.3$) acquired from 2001 to 2015 by the stations belonging to both the trigger-mode monitoring network managed by ENI Oil Company and the Italian National Seismic Network

managed by INGV. Using the coda decay method, we estimated $Q_c(f)$ by using different time windows for the envelope fitting. We developed a method aimed at automatically finding the end-time of the coda envelope, avoiding the manual and subjective criterion of selection of the end of coda. Compared with other tectonic regions worldwide, in the High Agri Valley $Q_c(f)$ is very low at all the investigated frequencies. Indeed, the Q_0 , that is the Q_c at 1 Hz, ranges between 8 and 57. Even at 16 Hz, the highest estimated Q_c value is lower than 400. To highlight the possible relation between spatial attenuation anomalies and seismicity distribution a 3D imaging of $Q_c(f)$ will be performed by adopting sensitivity kernels.

Gargano Promontory

We applied the extended coda normalization method to obtain the P waves attenuation parameter Q_α in the Gargano Promontory (GP, Southern Italy). We used a dataset of 190 local earthquakes (hypocentral distance up to 70 km), having a magnitude $1.0 < M_L < 2.8$ and recorded since 2015 to 2018 by 19 stations belonging to the OTRIONS and the INGV seismic networks. Q_α is dependent on the frequency through the power law $Q_\alpha(f) = (21 \pm 3) f^{(1.02 \pm 0.13)}$. Since Q_β is already known for the area, we compared Q_α with Q_β , inferring that $Q_\beta/Q_\alpha > 1$ at all the frequencies (except for $f=1$ Hz where $Q_\beta/Q_\alpha \approx 1$), denoting a partially fluid-saturated crust. Using a back-projection technique we obtained 3D images of Q_α . Q_α slightly increases with depth. The shape of Q_α isolines seems to be well correlated with that of some tectonic structures of GP.

In fact, along the Candelaro fault, Q_α decreases from NW to SE at 2 km of depth. Moving towards the fault, Q_α decreases, assuming low values ($Q_\alpha < 200$) close to it. Moreover, a low Q_α area ($Q_\alpha = 200$) is detected down to 12 km at the edge between the Candelaro and the Mattinata fault. A low Q_α area borders the south side of the Sannicandro fault up to 7 km of depth. Instead, in the south-east segment of the Mattinata fault, between Monte S. Angelo and Manfredonia, a high Q_α area is found at 7 km of depth. We conclude that the geographical distribution of the P-wave attenuation parameter shows a good correlation with the most important tectonic elements known in the GP, thus suggesting a structural control on the distribution of Q_α .

Keywords: seismic attenuation, Southern Italy.

Self-calibrated laser induced breakdown spectroscopy for in situ monitoring of volcanic ash

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Volcano monitoring and hazard assessment benefit greatly from the real-time study of fine ash in volcanic plumes, which are composed of magma fragments released from the crater during explosive eruptions. Numerous analytical methods can be applied to obtain the chemical characterization of the juvenile pyroclastic material generated in volcanic plumes. Among them, the most appropriate and easily applied to advanced applications in extreme environments is Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS) (De Giacomo et al., 2022).

In this first part of our work, we present the elemental composition of suspended volcanic ash obtained by using LIBS experiments based on a self-calibrated technique. Different sizes of volcanic ash samples from different locations were suspended in the air by laser-induced shockwaves in a dedicated chamber to replicate the conditions of dispersed volcanic ash in the atmosphere. At the same time, a parametric study was conducted to determine the best experimental conditions for recording useful plasma emission spectra for each ash size. The quantitative analysis was then carried out via a self-calibrated analytical methodology, including Calibration-Free (CF) LIBS, that is based on the calculation of the spectral radiance of a uniform plasma in local thermodynamic equilibrium (Bousquet et al., 2023). An added asset to our analysis technique was a CF-LIBS soft that accounts intrinsically for self-absorption, since the latter modifies the intensity of spectral lines and thus leads to an underestimation of the elemental fraction (Hermann, 2015). In order to deduce the apparatus response from the ash

spectrum itself and eliminate the need of standard calibration lamps, an intensity calibration of the spectra based on the measurements of Fe lines intensities was also used in this work (Taleb et al., 2024).

The obtained results demonstrate the potential of real-time measurements of elemental fractions in volcanic ash with a good agreement with the literature composition. Now, we are planning the construction of a compact instrument that can be installed on drones for on-flight CF-LIBS measurements.

Keywords: LIBS, volcanic ash.

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The new seismic catalogue of the Gargano area with the OTRIONS seismic network

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The OTRIONS seismic network (FDSN code OT) is a local network installed in the Apulia region (Southern Italy) and managed by the University of Bari Aldo Moro and INGV (National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology). The objective is to investigate the seismic activity in the Gargano area (Northern Apulia) and the Salento area (Southern Apulia). This network started to operate in 2013 and in 2019 the network migrated on EIDA (all details can be found in the work of Filippucci et al., 2021). A first catalogue of the seismicity, referring to the period from 2013 to 2018, was released in 2021. It contains events both manually and automatically detected using SeisComP3 software (Helmholtz-Centre Potsdam).

After ten years of operation, the focus lies on the microseismicity that characterizes the Gargano area and on compiling a new seismic database related to the period from April 2013 to December 2022. This work has been conducted by using CASP (Complete Automatic Seismic Processor), a software for automatic event detection, picking, and location (Scafidi et al., 2019). CASP operates on a remote server managed by RECAS-Bari, the computational infrastructure jointly managed by INFN and UniBa. CASP and NonLinLoc software (Lomax et al., 2000) were set specifically for the Gargano area and by implementing its 1D P- and S-wave velocity model (de Lorenzo et al., 2017).

The recorded seismic events were organized in two catalogs: an automatic catalog, obtained from CASP's automatic location and a revised catalog obtained by a manual revision of P- and S-wave arrival times. To evaluate the reliability of CASP algorithm, a comparison between the two catalogs (automatic and manual) was performed. The final revised catalog revealed a

significant increase in the number of events detection performance with respect to the earlier version derived from the previous software SeisComP3. Furthermore, the results show that the choice of the CASP parameters allows us to lower the minimum magnitude threshold of the recorded microseismicity in the Gargano area. The seismicity distribution suggests a deepening trend of earthquake foci moving northwards in the area.

Finally, another algorithm is being tested during this study: the application of PhaseNet deep neural network for earthquake detection (Zhu and Beroza, 2018). Preliminary test of this algorithm showed that the number of the detected events can be further increased with respect to CASP.

Keywords: earthquake, Otrions, catalogue.

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The Solfatara Earthquake 20/5/24 Md4.4

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On May 20, 2024, at 18.10 UTC (20.10 Local Time) the Md 4.4 Solfatara earthquake struck the Campi Flegrei caldera in southern Italy, and it was followed by a Md 3.9 event in the same area and hundreds of smaller magnitude events. The joint analysis of the mainshock (aftershock fault mechanisms and relocated aftershocks constrains a normal faulting mechanism involving a fault bordering the western limit of the Solfatara crater at about 2.7 km depth. The fault strike is NNW oriented and dips SW with a dip of about 40°. The modelling of displacement spectra provides a rupture radius of 400 m and stress drop of 6 MPa as measured from the spectral corner frequency. Time-domain measurements of P and S pulse amplitude/width show a little larger rupture radius of about 600 m, and consequently a smaller stress drop of 4 MPa. Average slip estimates range between 8 and 10 cm. The strong ground motion has been analysed in terms of response spectra, attenuation vs distance and ground shaking maps. A PGA of 0.35 g has been measured near the epicenter, with a major peak of the response spectra at 0.1-0.2 sec. Peak ground motion attenuates rapidly with distance. PGA reduces by 50% with respect to the maximum less than 2 km from the epicenter and reduces by 90% with respect to the maximum in less than 6 km from the epicenter.

Also, the grid-search method is applied, where theoretical predictions are obtained by using a Campi Flegrei-specific GMPE and are corrected for the Cd directivity factor corresponding to the sampled rupture model. The estimate of the rupture length (1.0 km), direction (N261°E) and speed ($V_r=0.7 V_s$) are inferred from the inversion of Peak Ground Velocity data (PGV) (frequency band 0.5-10 Hz) measured at stations within 20 km epicentral distance. The rupture direction shows a dominant down-dip rupture propagation along the NW-SE striking,

W dipping plane. Given the fault normal mechanism, this is consistent with an in-plane sliding mode with a shear stress acting parallel to the fault and perpendicular to the rupture front.

Regional (PRESTo) and on-site (SAVE) earthquake early warning systems provided a successful alert for a M4+ and IMM V+ about 3 sec after the first P-wave arrival. The overestimates of magnitude and intensity are likely due to the inclusion of the S-wave within the used P-wave time window of analysis.

Keywords: Campi Flegrei, seismicity.

Three-dimensional magnetotelluric inversion applied in the northern sector of the Irpinia fault system (Southern Apennine)

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Twenty-five broad band magnetotelluric (MT) soundings were carried out in the framework of previous project in a sector of the Southern Apennines including the seismogenic areas of the main shocks of the 1930 and 1980 Irpinia earthquakes. These soundings cover an area of 80x60km, even if the soundings are still not uniformly distributed. A three-dimensional inversion was done thanks to the parallel version of the code ModEM3DMT (Kelbert et al. 2014).

A model space explored making several run using different values for starting parameters. All these modelling include topography and bathymetry. After best values seeking was considered the model obtained assuming a starting resistivity of 100 ohm.m and minimum cell size of 3 km. This model represents a good starting point for further refinement of the resistivity model that could be improved with an extension of the surveyed area and a reduction of minimum cell size, thus model resolution.

Good matches were found between model features and geological information taken from other scientific works, like seismic events in the considered volume. Is worth to note that even the relatively wide cell size the resistivity model images a local resistive zone under "Monte Forcuso 1" borehole (CO2 gas pocket), thus confirming the MT sensitivity to fluid detection. The resistive basement well depicts the deep carbonate platform depicting the geometry of hypocentral area of the two above mentioned seismic events.

Next step is the quantitative comparison with seismic tomographic models in the same volumes.

Keywords: magnetotelluric, 3D inversion, Southern Appennine.

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Using repeating microearthquakes to infer medium velocity variations in response to water injection at the Geysers geothermal field

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In this study, we investigate the spatiotemporal variations in the velocity of the shallow crustal medium at the Geysers geothermal field, California, using repeating earthquakes (repeaters) identified through hierarchical agglomerative clustering of waveforms from 55,653 earthquakes recorded between 2006 and 2016 at 30 stations near the Prati-9 and Prati-29 injection wells. Over 500 repeaters were identified, primarily occurring after the renewal of the fluid injection operations of the well Prati-9 in November 2007. The number of repeaters notably increased between 2010 and 2013, coinciding with a significant water injection period at Prati-29.

Time shifts measured by cross correlating the coda waves of pairs of repeaters were used to estimate the medium velocity variations over time. Repeater pairs nucleated at depths of 3-4 km showed a relative velocity decrease dv/v of approximately -0.1% (monthly rate) at stations within 5 km of the injection wells. Conversely, time shifts measured at stations located 7.5 km or more from the wells indicated a slight velocity increase, with a monthly dv/v rate of about 0.01%. This observed spatiotemporal pattern of velocity variations is likely due to changes in pore pressure increase/decrease, associated in turn with the increase/decrease of the injection rate at two wells Prati-9 and Prati-29 during the same period.

Keywords: geysers geothermal field, medium velocity variations, repeating earthquakes.

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Validation of Nonlinear Finite Element Analysis of Corroded RC/PC Beams based on Experimental Tests

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Structures and infrastructure systems are at risk of aging and deterioration processes. Life-cycle-oriented design, assessment, maintenance, and management of deteriorating structures and infrastructural facilities, such as bridges, should rely on structural analysis frameworks capable to account for time-variant structural performance (Biondini and Frangopol 2016). Although life-cycle models are well established for some of the most detrimental damage processes, such as corrosion, robust validation and accurate calibration are difficult tasks because of the limited availability of information about long-term performance of in-service structures (Biondini and Frangopol 2018). Gathering data from both inspection of existing structures and experimental tests is therefore of essence for a successful implementation in practice of life-cycle methods. This study is motivated by these needs and provides a contribution to computational modelling and experimental validation of nonlinear finite element analysis of reinforced concrete (RC) and prestressed concrete (PC) structures, with emphasis on life-cycle assessment of bridges under corrosion.

Structural modelling is developed with different levels of complexity based on RC/PC beam finite elements accounting for the nonlinear stress-strain constitutive laws of the materials, i.e. concrete, reinforcing steel, and prestressing steel, and bi-dimensional finite elements for plane stress analysis formulated in accordance with the Modified Compression Field Theory. The proposed models are validated on the results of experimental tests on corroded RC/PC beams available in literature, as well as on the outcomes of ongoing full-scale load tests on PC bridge deck beams conducted within the BRIDGE|50 research project (Anghileri and Biondini 2022, 2023). BRIDGE|50 has been established jointly by Politecnico di Milano and Politecnico di Torino, together with public authorities and private companies, for a wide experimental campaign on a viaduct dismantled after a 50 years lifetime (Biondini et al. 2021).

In this project, a group of 29 PC deck beams, including 25 I-beams and 4 U-box beams, and 2 PC pier caps have been stored in a testing site. The experimental activities include non-destructive diagnostic tests, full-scale load tests up to collapse, and concrete cores and steel bar specimens collected for laboratory tests (<http://www.bridge50.org>). The full-scale load tests

on the deck beams are performed under three- and four-point bending with different values of the shear-span ratio to investigate both flexural and shear failures (Savino et al. 2023). The large amount of data collected from these experimental tests are suitable for statistical processing and are used to inform validation and calibration of life-cycle computational models and implementation in practice of life cycle design, assessment, maintenance, and management of aging structures and infrastructure systems under uncertainty.

Keywords: life-cycle, non-linear structural analysis, experimental testing.

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VS4 ‘Environmental degradation’

A MaxEnt framework to model the spread of benthonic Alien Invasive Species

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The swift proliferation of Alien Invasive Species (AIS) within the Mediterranean Sea underscores the urgent need for predictive models capable of accurately forecasting its future spread in the light of climate change. Using high-resolution oceanographic and environmental data from the IPCC-AR5-RCP8.5 scenario, alongside occurrence data from citizen science, literature and a long-term monitoring program as independent test set, we model the current and future distribution of *C. cylindracea*, one of the most dangerous AIS in the Mediterranean Sea, at spatial resolution of 1/24 degree and yearly time resolution

from 2000 to 2050. The modelling approach, based on MaxEnt, assumed no adaptation and involved a "present scenario" based on average 2000-2020 conditions for training. We evaluated 1240 model configurations and selected the most reliable one by introducing two novel performance metrics, in addition to common ones, through an enhanced model validation that exploits the abundance data present in the test set. Extrapolation Risk

Analysis was performed to assess model's transferability to new conditions and map prediction's uncertainty. Projections were made for a "future scenario", average 2030-2050 conditions, and annually to create suitability maps over time. Our findings indicate a successful training process, as suggested by response curves that are consistent with

the known ecophysiology of the species. The novel metrics enabled the identification of models that more accurately reflect the species' abundance patterns. All models agree on a general shift toward lower probability of occurrence in the future scenario. Analysis of the annual suitability maps suggests a plateau-like invasion kinetic (sometimes referred as natural fluctuation model) in the currently suitable areas, with no sign of suitability increase in the near future. The framework proposed allows to address data biases, estimate prediction uncertainty, and distinguish models with inflated performance metrics. The newly introduced performance indicators are promising tools, in particular for studies that prioritize model transferability. The confidence in model reliability allows to push further the projection exercise to generate and study suitability time series, opening up to a completely new class of analysis in the context of Machine Learning Ecological Niche Modelling process.

Keywords: Alien Invasive Species, MaxEnt, Climate Change.

An integrated approach for mining waste remediation and metal recovery

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Mining activities have significantly contributed to the social and economic development of Sardinia; however, they have left a heavy legacy in terms of environmental degradation. Abandoned mining sites are typically characterized by severe land disruption due to the presence of excavations, waste dumps, tailings dams and tailings basins. These factors have not only caused significant landscape alterations but also led to high levels of soil and water pollution (Edraki et al., 2014).

In the context of environmental remediation requirements and the implementation of circular economy principles, focused on diversifying raw material supply sources, mining waste represents a significant peculiarity due to the quantities produced, chemical-physical characteristics, and valorization prospects. From this perspective, waste management assumes not only environmental but also economic significance. Indeed, due to the progressive depletion of deposits, the high metal content, and the growing demand for raw materials, old waste deposits can be considered important reserves of useful species, reducing the need for extraction from new deposits and limiting waste production (Bellanfante et al., 2013, Lèbre and Corder, 2015).

In Sardinia, 151 abandoned mining sites have been recorded, containing approximately 70 Mm³ of mining waste. These sites represent, on one hand, a potential environmental risk and, on the other, a potential source of secondary raw materials. The focus of this study is the application of mineral processing techniques aimed at determining a treatment circuit for the tailings taken from the tailings dam of Montevecchio Levante in southwestern Sardinia. This site, which contains an estimated volume of about 6 Mm³ of tailings, falls into the highest class of ecological and health risk identified by ISPRA.

The activity focused on the application of the flotation process, the same process that historically generated the waste in question, for the recovery of sphalerite (ZnS) and the reduction of heavy metal concentrations, in combination with preliminary classification and grinding processes. Flotation is a widespread industrial practice for recovering secondary raw materials, but it represents a novelty if aimed at environmental remediation (Manca et al., 2021). The applied process enables the production of a commercially valuable concentrate with a high zinc content (> 50%), as well as a final residue with excellent environmental characteristics, making it reusable on-site for backfilling (Manca et al., 2014) or in other production contexts (Lottermoser, 2011). Additionally, chemical analyses of the products have demonstrated the possibility of concentrating, in addition to zinc, elements classified as critical, including cobalt, gallium, germanium, and rare earth elements, which are essential for the manufacturing of high-value-added products.

Tailings reprocessing is, therefore, both an environmental risk reduction operation and a useful ore recovery operation. The proposed solutions have been designed taking into account the technical, economic and environmental aspects that should guide toward the development of approaches to mitigate the environmental damage that characterizes abandoned mining areas and to fully exploit the economic potential of this type of waste in a long-term perspective.

Keywords: soil remediation, tailings, flotation.

Advanced nanoremediation for the effective removal of recalcitrant mixtures of persistent pollutants from groundwater

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Groundwater contamination poses a significant threat to human health and ecosystems, necessitating effective remediation strategies. Zerovalent iron microparticles (mZVI) and nanoparticles (nZVI) have emerged as powerful solutions, offering significant opportunities for in situ groundwater cleanup. Their nanoscale size provides a high surface area-to-volume ratio, enhancing their reactivity with various contaminants. This makes nZVI particles particularly effective in reducing contaminants through chemical reduction and sorption processes. Their unique reactivity is further enhanced by their ability to be injected in aqueous slurries directly into contaminated aquifers, enabling targeted source treatment and plume remediation.

nZVI-based treatments are increasingly applied for in situ groundwater remediation as they effectively remove various contaminants, including chlorinated solvents, metal ions, PAHs, PCBs, and pesticides. However, some contaminants, like 1,2-dichloroethane (1,2-DCA) and 1,2-dichloropropane (1,2-DCP), are resistant to this treatment, posing significant challenges for remediating aquifer systems with complex contaminant mixtures.

Optimizing the reactivity of zero-valent iron and managing particle injection are critical for large-scale implementation. Depending on the site's characteristics, micro and nanoparticles can be used as-is or modified to enhance their effectiveness. Common modifications include:

- Addition of biodegradable stabilizing agents to improve suspension stability and distribution during injection.
- Surface functionalization with trace catalysts to enhance electron exchange, speeding up reaction kinetics and broadening the range of treatable contaminants.
- Sulfidation by forming an inorganic sulfur-based layer on particle surfaces to increase reactivity towards specific contaminants and prolong the iron's lifespan by partially inhibiting corrosion in water.

In this study, different types of nZVI particles were tested through laboratory experiments to evaluate nanoremediation's applicability for treating a site contaminated with a complex mixture of persistent chlorinated solvents. Specifically, the study area is affected by groundwater contamination by chlorinated organic compounds at concentrations of thousands of $\mu\text{g/L}$. The contamination includes compounds treatable with zerovalent iron, such as PCE, TCE, and PCM, and pollutants highly resistant to nZVI treatment, like 1,2-DCA and 1,2-DCP.

Laboratory batch tests compared the effectiveness of nZVI-based products for decontaminating groundwater samples from the study site. The products tested included standard zero-valent iron nanoparticles (nZVI), sulfidated nZVI (nZVI-S), and IronGel Plus (DeltaNova), an innovative nZVI-based reactant containing catalyzed nanoparticles. IronGel Plus consists of a viscoelastic biopolymeric gel with reactive nanoscale zero-valent iron particles (d50

< 100 nm), functionalized with a food-grade metallic catalyst to enhance their reactivity and effectiveness against contaminants. The effectiveness of the tested reagents in reducing the target contaminants over time was evaluated by determining the degradation kinetics of different compounds in contact with the reactive materials.

Experimental results demonstrated the effectiveness of standard nZVI in removing most chlorinated organic compounds, except for 1,2-DCP and 1,2-DCA. Very fast degradation of chlorinated ethenes, including cis-1,2-DCE and vinyl chloride, was observed. However, nZVI was ineffective in the dehalogenation of 1,2-DCA and 1,2-DCP. Sulfidated iron (nZVI-S) showed similar results to unmodified nZVI for PCE and TCE, with no significant degradation of cis-1,2-DCE, VC, 1,2-DCA, or 1,2-DCP. Both nZVI and nZVI-S partially and temporarily formed dichloromethane from PCM and TCM degradation. Complete removal of all chlorinated solvents, including those resistant to zero-valent iron treatment, was observed with IronGel Plus, without forming other intermediates or by-products.

This study confirmed that nZVI is a powerful reducing agent for the reductive dechlorination of most chlorinated solvents and highlighted the importance of surface modification for tuning nanoparticle reactivity. For the specific site investigated, IronGel Plus was the most effective reagent for dechlorinating all contaminants in groundwater, including 1,2-DCA and 1,2-DCP (removal > 99%).

The selection of the most suitable surface modification should come from a meticulous analysis of the site-specific contamination, especially with complex pollutant mixtures. Despite unmodified nZVI's effectiveness for chlorinated ethylenes, it is almost ineffective for 1,2-DCA removal and can lead to temporary formation of undesired intermediates with chlorinated methanes. Similarly, nZVI-S is viable only when vinyl chloride and cis-1,2-DCE are not the main target contaminants. To confirm laboratory-scale results, the effectiveness of IronGel Plus will be further evaluated in an upcoming field pilot test.

Keywords: groundwater remediation, nanoremediation, aquifer.

Beyond the SDG 15.3.1: A self-adjusting algorithm using Google Earth Engine to assess key land degradation status relevant to the Italian case study

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Land degradation (LD) is a critical global challenge that significantly reduces soil ecosystem services, alters terrestrial vegetation dynamics, and leads to the decline and/or loss of biodiversity in both terrestrial and coastal ecosystems. A significant policy initiative to combat land degradation emerged from the United Nations 2030 Agenda. Specifically, SDG target 15.3 was adopted to address desertification, restore degraded land and soil, and achieve a land degradation-neutral world. To facilitate this goal, SDG indicator 15.3.1 was established by the UNCCD to monitor the “proportion of land that is degraded over the total land area”. This indicator serves as a basis for planning actions and investments to reverse land degradation. The proposed indicator is indeed a valuable tool for obtaining a clear spatial representation of soil and land conditions over time. However, increasing evidence suggests that the SDG indicator 15.3.1 approach has inherent reliability issues, potentially leading to contestations and misleading policy guidance (Xoxo et al., 2022).

In light of these concerns, the objective of the proposed work is to develop a procedure to enhance the reliability of SDG 15.3 by improving some critical components of the SDG indicator 15.3.1. This research presents an initial overview of an innovative and scalable approach with the objective to monitor land degradation at various scales (e.g., regional, national, global) using earth observation information.

To this end, a self-adjusting algorithm was built on the GEE platform to visualize, assess, and define land degradation changes and causes, at the pixel level, over a period of 19 years (2000 - 2019). Multispectral (Landsat 7&8, Sentinel-2) imagery and hyperspectral (Hyperion EO1) dataset were evaluated and compared, for their ability to meet the objectives of the study. Hereby, maximum annual and mean seasonal time-series of the Leaf Area Index (LAI) and the Enhanced Vegetation Index 2 (EVI2) were used to assess productivity metrics across Italy and were corrected considering the changing climatic conditions. Subsequently, we investigated the use of the Land Use and Cover Area frame Survey (LUCAS) soil data to calibrate soil organic carbon models employing machine learning algorithms, in order to ensure a time-series change analysis of the ground carbon at a higher spatial resolution. The research provides two primary products which compromise: (i) a mapping of the degradation status; and (ii) an assessment of the type of degradation.

Overall, this innovative approach aligns the employment of finer resolution data for a better investigation on land degradation processes within a national context.

Keywords: hyperspectral imagery, degradation status, LUCAS.

Cellulose-based nanostructured sorbent materials for fresh- and seawater decontamination

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The increasing and urgent need for water and wastewater purification from a wide array of pollutants demands the development of more effective and safe technologies. In this context, the creation of manufactured nanomaterials (MNMs) for efficient water treatment is gaining significant interest due to their promising adsorption capabilities. However, MNMs also raise concerns about their potential (eco)toxicity and the uncertainty regarding their eventual fate. Therefore, adopting a safer-by-design approach is recommended for developing new MNMs, combining high decontamination efficiency with confirmed eco-safety (Corsi et al., 2023).

A vital initial step in this process involves selecting the appropriate starting materials for MNM production.

In this context, in the last decade nanocellulose (NC) has attracted more and more attention, due to its remarkable mechanical and thermal properties, its enhanced surface area, and the possibility to modify its backbone by selectively introducing new functional groups, and consequently additional properties. Moreover, NC can be also obtained by cleaving the hierarchical structure of cellulose fiber, opening to the opportunity to valorise waste-derived cellulose sources, including the paper mill recycled pulp and agricultural biomass, in accordance with the virtuous principles of circular economy

Herein we provide an overview of our ongoing research on nanocellulose, simply derived from biomass as a renewable source, as a sustainable and eco-safe building block for developing new MNMs with high adsorption performance for water treatment.

2,2,6,6-Tetramethylpiperidinyloxy (TEMPO)-oxidized cellulose nanofibers (TOCNFs), which have been proved to be safe for aqueous environment (Rusconi et al., 2024; Esposito et al., 2023; Esposito et al., 2024) have been cross-linked in the presence of branched polyethyleneimines for producing nanostructured cellulose-based materials, known as cellulose nanosponges (CNS). These systems, characterized by highly attractive properties, including a large exposed surface area due to their porous network, have proven to be extremely effective for both fresh- and seawater decontamination from a wide range of contaminants, including heavy metals and organic pollutants (Fiorati et al., 2020). Moreover, the possibility to couple them with a filtering fine-mesh net suggested their use to remediate contaminated freshwater sludges (Guidi et al., 2023).

Keywords: water treatment, nanomaterials, cellulose.

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Degradation of Bioplastic in Marine Water by microorganisms: chemical and spectroradiometric analyses to assess a future protocol

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The production of bio-based polymers is continuously increasing as a potential substitute for petroleum-based plastics. However, degradability studies mostly focus on native polymers, while information on the environmental degradability of bio-based commercial products is primarily related to composting facilities, resulting in a lack of data under natural conditions. It is known that the marine environment is the most vulnerable to plastic pollution. According to the literature, the degradation process of bioplastics in the sea occurs due to microorganisms present in the water column. Therefore, a laboratory experiment was conducted to explore the capability of marine microorganisms to degrade commercially produced polylactic acid (PLA)-based materials under controlled marine conditions. To recruit biomass from the marine environment, scaffolds of native PLA polymers have been immersed in the sea for three months. Once the biofilm formed on the surface of the scaffolds, it was inoculated into microcosms containing sterilized seawater, PLA bags, PLA caps, and native PLA, respectively. Control microcosms were prepared using only biopolymers and seawater. After 60 and 120 days (hereinafter indicated as “time step”), 15 mL samples were collected from each microcosm to research the eventual presence of hydrolysis products (e.g. Lactic acid), which would indicate microbial degradation activity on the biopolymer. Specifically, lactic acid was analysed using SPE extraction followed by determination with an orbitrap technology.

The solid samples of the commercial polymers, collected at each time step, were spectrally characterised by conducting an indoor laboratory experiment. The samples have been positioned within a white box and illuminated using two lamps simulating the solar irradiance. The spectral signatures have been acquired via the FieldSpec 4 Hi-Res spectroradiometer by ASD (Analytical Spectral Devices), able to acquire the reflectance from 350 to 2500 nm.

The analyses highlighted that although the microorganisms remained active according to vitality tests, the commercial PLA caps and PLA bags did not appear to be degraded by microbial action, as neither hydrolysis products nor significant variations in the spectral signature were identified. Interestingly, hydrolysis products (lactic acid and dilactide) were identified in the microcosm containing the native polymer, indicating that the microorganisms selected from the marine environment are indeed capable of attacking PLA. This result demonstrates that the investigative strategy developed is suitable for studying the potential degradation of PLA in a

marine environment. Therefore, the lack of degradation observed in commercial polymers suggests that these materials are more resistant to degradation, possibly due to additives used during the production process to impart specific mechanical properties necessary for their intended use. While further investigation is necessary, this study raises new concerns about the actual environmental impact of these materials, underscoring the need for continued investigation into the behaviour of biopolymers in the marine ecosystem.

Keywords: spectroradiometric analysis, LC, MS, bioplastics.

Effects of exposure to CO₂ and H₂S on the performance of the Mediterranean seagrass *Posidonia oceanica* in a volcanic vent

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Although seagrasses are expected to thrive in future acidified oceans by overcoming low CO₂ diffusion into plant tissues, the co-occurrence of environmental stressors may affect their growth. Volcanic CO₂ vents are often associated with toxic gases and metal-rich fluids representing ideal sites to assess the effects of multiple stressors. We evaluated the response of *Posidonia oceanica* growing near shallow CO₂ vents characterised by H₂S spill-out by comparing meadow structure and phenology to an area with no gas emissions. Seagrass descriptors at meadow, shoot and leaf level indicated that *P. oceanica* experienced stressful conditions at the vent area, in clear contrast to the flourishing features of *P. oceanica* previously described at CO₂ vents with no evidence of toxic inputs. Furthermore, the reduction in both leaf $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ and growth at the vent area indicates that sulphide intrusion occurs and affects seagrass growth performance, dampening the expected beneficial effects of high CO₂ levels.

Keywords: climate change, ocean acidification, Panarea, multiple stressors, sulfide, seeps.

Electrochemical techniques for the removal of pollutants and microplastics in waters and soils

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Electrochemical-based approaches for the depollution of waters, wastewaters and soils have been the subject of intense research for the past few years thanks to their ability to degrade undesirable organic compounds or metals via oxidation and reduction. Since the electrochemical treatments are energy-driven and use electrons as “green reactants”, are often defined environmentally friendly, especially when they are powered by renewable energy sources. These potentialities fit well with our research activity in the framework of WP 4.5 - Prevention and remediation. Regarding the treatment of waters polluted with emerging contaminants, preliminary experiments have been performed applying the electrochemical treatment to synthetic solutions containing different kind of microplastics. In particular, water containing polyethylene (PE) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) microplastics with average particle size of 150-250 micrometres have been treated by photoelectro- and electro-chemical oxidation techniques. Commercial Ti grids coated with mixed metal oxides or TiO₂ nanotubes were used as anodes in electro-chemical and photoelectro-chemical oxidation tests, respectively. Considering that solution containing MPs are suspension of organic particles rather than homogenous solutions, the indirect oxidation mediated by active chlorine species generated from the oxidation of chloride ions was studied. Preliminary results of photoelectrochemical treatment will be presented: in this case the oxidation is mainly due to ·OH radicals and reactive oxygen species generated on the semiconductor surface. Different cell configurations have been tested, both in batch and in continuous mode. The oxidation of MPs was assessed by analysing the mass loss of MPs over time: a weight loss of 74% was measured after 30 days of treatment. During the electrochemical tests, samples were withdrawn for UV-Vis analysis, in order to evaluate the trend of active chlorine. Reaction products, along with total organic carbon (TOC) analysis, were measured during both electro- and photoelectro-chemical degradation. At the end of the process, the synthetic solutions were filtered to recover the residual microplastics that have been then thermal treated at 70 °C for 48 h; the MPs have been subsequently analysed to evaluate variations in weight, shape, and surface structure by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR). The presence of hydroxyl groups and the reduction in the characteristic peaks of microplastics highlighted by FT-IR results indicates an effective degradation of MPs.

The remediation of polluted soils has been faced coupling the electrochemical approach with the bioremediation technique. Soil microbial fuel cells (SMFCs) are electrochemical devices at which anode, cathode or both are colonized by an electroactive biofilm able to convert the pollutants in the soil and to obtain electricity. In this work SMFCs test have been performed using the herbicide 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid and phenol as model pollutants. In the adopted

configuration, the anaerobic anode is buried in the soil and connected via external circuit to the cathode suspended at the top of the soil sample. The frequency of consumption and feeding cycle in the SMFC operating under fed-batch conditions has been assessed with growth curves and polarization/Power curves. Sorption isotherms and remediation tests have been performed with different cell configurations, and different size of the cell: both 10x10 cm and 100x50 cm SMFCs have been tested to gain information about the scalability, as well as different number and position of the anode and cathode. The remediation was assessed measuring the residual concentration of herbicide obtained for different time of treatment. Samples of soil were withdrawn from the SMFCs in different reaction zones; namely near the bioanode, near the biocathode and in the middle. The residual herbicide concentration was characterized by Soxhlet extraction using acetonitrile and was quantified by HPLC measurements. For comparison, also the natural degradation of the herbicide and phenol were studied.

Keywords: electrochemical treatment, Soil Microbial Fuel Cells.

Enhanced remediation of marine sediments using anionic, non-ionic and mixed surfactants: role of operational conditions

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Sediment is one of the environmental matrices that can be affected by chemical pollution. Due to the close exchange between sediment and the aquatic environment, contaminants can be absorbed or released by sediment, making it both a sink and a source of pollutants. Among chemical pollutants, total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) plays a crucial role since oil leakage is common. Noteworthy, TPH may pose risks to human health and the environment and, over the years, it has been associated with significant contamination (Liu et al., 2021).

Therefore, remediation techniques are pivotal to reducing such risks by removing environmental contaminants. Among the proposed technologies, sediment washing represents a promising ex-situ treatment, where pollutants are extracted from sediments by means of a washing solution, eventually augmented with chemicals. Therefore, contaminants are transferred from the sediment to the solution and subsequently removed. Referring to petroleum hydrocarbons, literature studies revealed that surfactants play a crucial role since they can enhance the mobilization and dissolution of oil contaminants into water through the reduction of air/water surface tension, oil/water interfacial tension, and micellar solubilisation (Liu et al., 2021). Sediment washing can achieve high removal efficiencies, limiting the deterioration of physical-chemical properties of sediment and microbial activity while leading to reduced operating costs. Over the last years, Tween 80 and Sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonate (SDBS) are amongst the surfactants that have aroused significant interest in removing petroleum hydrocarbons. Tween 80 is a non-ionic surfactant. SDBS is an anionic surfactant. Noteworthy, previous research investigated the effectiveness of SDBS and Tween 80 in removing petroleum hydrocarbons both alone (Liu et al., 2021) and as mixed surfactants (Zhang et al., 2010), with promising results. However, further research is necessary, since very little is known about their effectiveness in dealing with contaminated sediment, whose properties can significantly differ from soils. Therefore, the aim of the present study was to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the removal efficiency of TPH from marine sediments through a sediment washing treatment using two surfactants, Tween 80 and SDBS, both individually and to form mixed surfactants.

The marine sediments used for the washing tests were obtained from Augusta Bay (Italy), a contaminated site of national interest. The dried sample was then crushed using a mortar and sieved with a first sieve having a mesh size of 2 mm and, subsequently, with a sieve having a mesh size of 0.63 μm . The experimental campaign lasted about three months. Preliminary, washing

tests were carried out with distilled water only as blank control (test A). Additionally, 3 sets of washing tests (B, C, and D) were conducted at different surfactant concentrations. All tests were conducted with a sediment-water (S:W) ratio 1:4 (w/v). All measurements were performed in duplicate to ensure data reliability. Surfactant concentration was always above the CMC of SDBS and Tween 80. Indeed, CMC of SDBS and Tween 80 is 0.612 mM (212.57 mgL⁻¹) and 0.012 mM (13.1 mg L⁻¹) at 25°C, respectively (Di Trapani et al., 2023).

Each test involved the contact between a sediment sample and a washing solution with different surfactant concentrations. Each Pyrex glass bottle contained 10 g of sediment sample and 40 mL of washing solution. The bottles were subject to mixing for 24 hours at 100 rpm using an orbital shaker.

After the agitation phase, the samples were allowed to settle for 2 hours and then air-dried for at least 96 hours, depending on the external temperatures. The TPH measurement in the solid phase was carried out according to the procedure proposed by ISPRA (2011). After extraction and purification on Florisil, the procedure involves analysis by GC-FID (Di Trapani et al., 2023). The results obtained from the washing tests showed that the TPH extraction yields significantly improved when the two surfactants were used, both individually and as mixed surfactants, compared to the washing test with only water. In addition, the removal rates of hydrocarbons improved as the surfactant concentration increased.

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Keywords: mixed surfactant, sediment washing, batch test.

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Fate, transport, and bioaccumulation of contaminants: modeling tools for coastal- marine environments

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The marine environment is often the ultimate sink for anthropogenic pollutants, and coastal areas can act as repositories of persistent pollutants that accumulate in the sediment and can be remitted in the long term. Some pollutants, like mercury, persist in the environment for a long time after the sources have been removed. Direct exposure to harmful levels of pollutants, bioaccumulation, and biomagnification can threaten wildlife and human well-being (Schwarzenbach et al., 2010). Numerical modeling provides valuable support for understanding pollutants' fate, transport, and bioaccumulation across environmental compartments by integrating information from different sources into a holistic mathematical framework. We developed and applied modeling tools at different scales to add insights into mercury (Hg) dynamics in the Adriatic Sea and the Venice Lagoon.

Hg dynamics in the Adriatic Sea were simulated using the coupled three-dimensional model OGSTM-BFM-Hg (Rosati et al., 2022), which integrates a hydrodynamic transport model and a biogeochemical model with a model simulating the key processes of marine Hg cycling. The model dynamically reproduces the concentrations of Hg species at different depths of the water column and in the plankton compartment, and is run with a horizontal resolution of about 6.5 km. The modeled Hg concentrations in seawater and in different phyto- and zoo-plankton functional groups were averaged for the entire basin and used as input for a food web bioaccumulation model. The latter is being developed by adding the Ecotracer module (Walters and Christensen, 2018) to an ecosystem model of the Adriatic Sea recently implemented using the Ecopath with Ecosim suite (EwE; www.ecopath.org), which describes the food web of the Adriatic Sea with 73 functional groups characterizing in detail the fishing activities and has been fitted to 20 years of ecological and fisheries data. All data on Hg concentration in the Adriatic biota measured since 2005 has been compiled for calibration and validation of the bioaccumulation model.

Hg dynamics in the Venice Lagoon were simulated at higher spatial resolution using the coupled model SHYFEM-Hg. This finite element model uses an unstructured mesh that allows the reproduction of complex bathymetry and is therefore particularly suitable for coastal areas. Due to the shallow water of the Venice lagoon, and the significant enrichment in Hg in the sediment due to historical pollution, special emphasis was placed on integrating processes related to the benthic-pelagic exchanges in this model. Model results highlight high spatial and temporal variability in Hg concentrations driven by the resuspension and transport of sediment from the most contaminated areas of the lagoon, and suggest beneficial effects of benthic vegetation on water concentration of Hg.

A single-species bioaccumulation model for the clam *Ruditapes philippinarum* has been developed by integrating uptake and excretion dynamics for Hg and MeHg into an existing clam bioenergetic model (Solidoro et al., 2000) and will be applied to simulate the evolution of Hg concentrations in clams from different aquaculture sites of the lagoon, using as input the concentrations of mercury species modeled with Shyfem-Hg model.

Keywords: mercury, model, marine.

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Geochemical characterization and ecotoxicological evaluation of Sarno River stream sediment and waters: an integrated study.

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During May and June 2024, stream sediment and water sampling was carried out across the territory covered by the Sarno River basin in Campania. A total of 25 sampling stations were located along the major branches of the water course, including its main tributaries (i.e., Solofrana and Cavaiola).

The sampling campaign was aimed at:

- the geochemical characterization of the sampled media (both water and sediments) and the comparison of the actual potentially toxic metals (PTEs) concentrations with data from previous studies (Albanese et al., 2013)
- evaluate the ecotoxicological risk of water and sediments by a toxicity test battery with model organism belonging to different trophic levels and biological complexity.

Specifically, after on-site wet sieving, sediment sampling was carried out by collecting the grain size fraction < 2 cm, avoiding, as much as possible, points where organic matter was particularly relevant (i.e., dark layers). In some cases, due to the absence of stream waters (especially along the Solofrana River), only dry sediments were collected.

Accordingly, where possible, stream waters were collected before any other activity to avoid an increase in turbidity due to the presence of suspended solids. Water pH, conductivity and dissolved oxygen were measured on-site using a pre-calibrated XS REVio portable Multiparameter.

All the collected material was transferred to the Environmental Geochemistry Laboratory (EGL) at the Department of Earth, Environment, and Resource Sciences (DiSTAR) at the University of Naples Federico II to be prepared for further processing.

Water samples (kept at an average temperature of 4° Celsius) were split into two aliquots to determine, as soon as possible (i.e., within two days from collection), their chemical composition and evaluate its potential adverse effects in the ecotoxicology laboratory at ENEA C.R. Portici, respectively.

The test battery was based on the availability and sensitivity of model organisms: bacteria (acute test with *Vibrio fisheri*); algae (chronic test with *Raphidocelis subcapitata*); crustacea (acute and chronic test with *Daphnia magna*).

Sediment samples were split into three aliquots: one dedicated to geochemical characterization (in charge of the Environmental Geochemistry group at DiSTAR), one dedicated to ecotoxicological evaluation (in charge of the group of SSPT-IMPACT at Italian National Agency

for New Technologies, Energy, and Sustainable Economic Development – ENEA C.R. Portici) performed after preparation of the elutriate (ASTM D3977-97) by using the same water test battery; one to be stored as is, after natural drying, for future studies or validation purposes.

At EGL, chemical analysis has been completed for all collected water samples using a Palintest 7500 photometer using standard methodologies (APHA, 1995). Specifically, the concentration of free, total, and chelated copper (Cu), iron (Fe), aluminum (Al), ammonia (as N), ammonia (as NH₃), ammonia (as NH₄), magnesium (Mg), nitrite (as N), nitrite (as NO₂), phosphate (as P), phosphate (as PO₄), chromium VI (Cr VI), zinc (Zn), sulfate (SO₄), potassium (K), nickel (Ni), fluoride, nitrate (as N), nitrate (as NO₃), manganese (Mn) were determined.

Statistical and geospatial analysis of preliminary results on water show:

- a higher concentration of some analysed PTEs (Cr and Cu) and aluminium in the upper part of the basin (Solofrana River) downstream of an industrial purification plant serving an historical regional tanning hub.

- a variable trend of ammonium, nitrates, magnesium, and potassium concentrations with higher values in correspondence with flat areas characterized by intensive agriculture and a low degree of mixing of surficial water.

Further planned activities are:

- Chemical analysis on sediments: samples will be dried at a temperature < 40° Celsius and possibly analysed using aqua regia acidification followed by ICP-MS determinations.

- The ecotoxicological risk will be estimated for each site by Toxicity test Battery integrated Index-TBI (Manzo et al., 2008) that synthesizes the overall toxicity results and provides insights into the combined effects of chemical mixtures on organisms in the environment.

All the obtained result will be integrated to generate an updated vision of the environmental state of the Sarno River basin in consideration of the contamination levels assessed for the investigated matrices and their potential effects on the local ecosystem.

Keywords: Sarno river, metal contamination, ecotoxicology.

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Identification and classification of macro- and microplastics dispersed in terrestrial and marine environment by hyperspectral imaging

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The aim of this research is to develop innovative strategies for identifying macro- and microplastics dispersed in terrestrial, marine, and coastal environments by innovative fast, flexible, non-destructive hyperspectral imaging (HSI) technology coupled with chemometrics. Having a fast and efficient method for classifying polymers in macro- and microplastics is crucial for environmental monitoring. Current techniques for characterizing microplastics (MPs), such as FT-IR and Raman spectroscopy, are tedious and time-consuming. Recently, HSI has been proposed as a rapid and robust solution (Serranti et al., 2018; Fiore et al., 2022). HSI combines classical spectroscopy with digital imaging, enabling the detection of the spectral signature of each pixel in the acquired image across different wavelength ranges (i.e., visible, near infrared, short-wave infrared, etc.). The output of the acquisition is a data hypercube characterized by two spatial dimensions and one spectral dimension. Available HSI devices can recognize macro- and microplastics greater than 150 μm and can be coupled with automatic particle counting and measuring (size and shape parameters). Furthermore, innovative procedures are being developed to identify and classify MPs directly within various matrices (e.g., sand, soil, etc.), thus avoiding complex and time-consuming pretreatment procedures. A methodological study was conducted to develop an HSI analytical protocol for characterizing MPs, testing different setups: 1) two spatial resolutions (150 and 30 μm), 2) two wavelength ranges (1000-1700 and 1000-2500 nm), and 3) three different classification models (PLS-DA, ECOC-SVM, NNPR). The study focused on the three most common polymers (polyethylene, polypropylene and polystyrene) in MPs from coastal and marine environments. The results demonstrated that MPs > 500 μm are correctly identified by the three selected classifiers using both spectral ranges and spatial resolutions. For MPs < 500 μm , the following recommendations are suggested:

- A spatial resolution of 150 μm /pixel can effectively identify MPs > 250 μm .
- A spatial resolution of 30 μm /pixel can effectively identify MPs > 150 μm .
- The NIR range can be used for identifying MPs > 250 μm , while the SWIR range is preferred for MPs between 150 and 250 μm .

The best classification model depends on the spatial resolution:

- For MPs > 500 µm, a resolution of 150 µm/pixel (reducing acquisition and processing time) and classification by PLS-DA are suggested.
- For MPs < 500 µm, a resolution of 30 µm/pixel and classification by ECOC-SVM are recommended.

Furthermore, innovative HSI-based analytical procedures were applied to different case studies in collaboration with different research groups involved in the project:

-Case Study 1: Classification of Mater-Bi® bioplastics in anaerobic sludge by SWIR hyperspectral imaging, in collaboration with UNIROMA1-DICEA project partner (Capobianco et al., 2024).

-Case Study 2: In situ macroplastic litter classification by ground-based hyperspectral sensor on coastal areas (Torre Guaceto, Brindisi, Italy), in collaboration with UNIBA project partner (Bonifazi et al., 2023).

-Case Study 3: Microplastic litter classification on sandy beaches at laboratory-scale by different spectroscopic techniques (Vulcano Island, Italy), (Cocozza et al., 2023; the poster is winner of the Best Poster Award).

-Case Study 4: Microplastic litter identification by HSI on sandy beaches at laboratory-scale (Torre Guaceto, Brindisi, Italy), in collaboration with UNIBA project partner (Bonifazi et al., 2024).

-Case Study 5: Microplastic litter identification by HSI within marine sediments at laboratory-scale (Mar Piccolo, Taranto, Italy), in collaboration with UNIBA project partner.

-Case study 6: Microplastic litter identification by HSI from the water column at laboratory-scale (Port of Genoa, Liguria region, Italy), in collaboration with UNIGE project partner.

Keywords: microplastics, hyperspectral imaging, environmental monitoring.

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In situ stabilization of mine heaps by microbially assisted phytoremediation

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Mining exploitation can have significant negative impacts on the environment and human health, especially as a consequence of abandonment and defaulting management of sites (Kossov et al., 2014). This is the case of Ingurtosu mine site (Italy, SW Sardinia), that was one of the largest and most productive mines of sphalerite (ZnS) and galena (PbS) in Sardinia. The peak of productivity was the period between the 19th and 20th centuries, and the plant closed in 1969. The scarce prevention during the extraction activity and the following closure, led to a considerable environmental impact, the most for the deposition of mine tailings directly in the environment without any containment measure. As described in Caboi et al., 1993, big quantities of Pb, Zn, Cd and others heavy metals are leached every day by the rivers, especially the ones that are forrowing mine heaps. Today the Ingurtosu mines is still an environmental issue and it is part of the Geological and Mining Park. In 1997 it entered in the UNESCO network of Geo-parks.

After the experiment of the European Project UMBRELLA 2009-2012 and the following project SMERI (2014-2016), where a field trial was set up on the mine wastes in order to investigate phytoremediation assisted by Plant Growth Promoting Microorganisms (PGPM) (Sprocati et al., 2014) a field implementation started in 2024 under the project RETURN, Vertical Spoke 4, WP5, task 4.5.4.

The research is focusing on the interactions among the rhizosphere minerals, the microbial community, and the native plants with the final aim of improve the revegetation and stabilitation of the tailings. A new plant species is also investigated, *Helichrysum microphyllum* (Willd.) Cambess. subsp. *tyrrhenicum* Bacch., Brullo and Giusso, a Cyrno-Sardinian endemic plant that spontaneously grows on mining-impacted sediments because of its natural metal tolerance. Moreover, the addition of zeolites is considered as a soil amendment in support of the up-to-date native microbial inoculum.

This new experiment has the potential to elucidate the ecological links between plants, soil, and the microbial community, and confirm the strength of low-cost and sustainable bio-remediation technologies.

Keywords: mine tailings, bioaugmentation, ri-vegetation.

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Investigating primary producers buffer effect against mercury pollution in two marine invertebrate species

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Human activities have significantly deteriorated marine environments with contaminants. Oxygen release by photosynthetic organisms might enhance marine animals' aerobic performance in challenging conditions, such as ocean warming. However, our understanding of its buffering effects against pollution is limited. This pilot study explores the potential of oxygen supersaturation to mitigate mercury pollution, simulating primary productivity. Experiments were conducted on two commercially relevant species, such as the sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus* and the clam *Ruditapes philippinarum*. Adults of both species were collected from the Venice lagoon and then exposed to the combination of 2 levels of oxygen saturation (90% as control, 160% representing daily supersaturation) and 2 concentrations of mercury (0 and 1 µg/L, as mercury chloride) for 7 days. At the end of the exposure, different biomarkers, indicative of oxidative stress and immunosurveillance, and mercury bioaccumulation were evaluated in both species, while physiological and behavioral traits were assessed for *P. lividus* only. Results indicated potential differences in the responses of the two species to mercury under hyperoxic conditions, highlighting that animals' reactions to environmental factors could be species-specific. Notably, mercury bioaccumulation seems lower in clams under hyperoxic conditions than those in normoxic once. In sea urchins, female gonads' mercury levels appear higher than in males. Lastly, no significant effects have been detected on sea urchins' physiological and behavioral traits. The study is part of the RETURN Extended Partnership, funded by the European Union Next-Generation EU (National Recovery and Resilience Plan – NRRP, Mission 4, Component 2, Investment 1.3 – D.D. 1243 2/8/2022, PE0000005).

Keywords: pollution, marine invertebrates, primary producers.

Isolation of aerobic and anaerobic bacterial consortia from a contaminated aquifer able to degrade 1,2-dichloroethane

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Chlorinated Aliphatic Hydrocarbons (CAHs) are persistent and toxic environmental pollutants. In contaminated groundwater, CAHs can be biodegraded by anaerobic Organohalide Respiring Bacteria (OHRB), in the dehalorespiration process mediated by reductive dehalogenase enzymes (Hug et al., 2016). Nevertheless, aerobic oxidative processes can also co-occur, mediated by haloalkane dehalogenase enzymes, or cometabolically (Munro et al., 2017). The aim of this work is to detect and eventually isolate microorganisms or consortia able to degrade 1,2-dichloroethane, one of the most persistent CAH in aquifer contaminated by chlorinated hydrocarbons. Anaerobic consortia were enriched in anaerobic microcosms set up from contaminated groundwater with appropriate mineral media with (or without) lactate as electron donor to stimulate dehalorespiration. Aerobic consortia were enriched in aerobic microcosms with (or without) volatile hydrocarbon mixture to stimulate cometabolic or direct degradation. Bacterial degradation ability was evaluated by release profile of chloride in microcosms. Illumina 16S rRNA gene sequencing revealed the enrichment of anaerobic dechlorinating taxa, including known OHRB *Dehalococcoides* and *Desulfuromonas*. The catabolic genes *rdhA* involved in reductive dechlorination were detected in metagenomic DNA from microcosms by probing with specific primers. Aerobic consortia included *Ancylobacter* and *Starkeya* known as 1,2-DCA degraders and other members of unknown role (Munro et al., 2016). The catabolic genes *dhIA*, involved in hydrolytic dichlorination, were detected in metagenomic DNA from aerobic microcosms. Both anaerobic and aerobic 1,2-DCA degrading consortia can be exploited for bioremediation purposes in site.

Keywords: chlorinated hydrocarbons, bioremediation, microcosms.

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Large-Scale Monitoring of Land and Soil Degradation Due to Coppicing Clearcuts Management from PRISMA, Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 Satellite Data

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Chestnut ecosystems are of high significance, as a land component, in the mountainous regions of the European Mediterranean basin. Chestnut forests distributed in the Campania region (central Italy) are often subjected to intensive management practices such as the coppicing treatment. Clearcuts coppicing management in chestnut plantations showed evidence of removal of the organic residues from the soil surface as a result of the trunk dragging, leading to soil erosion and land degradation. Moreover, the fragility of the volcanic ash soils in the mountain areas in Campania is highlighted especially towards erosion and landslide. Taking into consideration the alarming situation, continuous monitoring of erosive areas due to coppice management is fundamental, mainly using soil imaging spectroscopy considering the increasing availability of satellite imaging data.

In this regard, the research explores the use of the multi-temporal PRISMA hyperspectral imagery and Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 multispectral datasets for the development and testing of approaches for: (i) bare soil presence, indicating where and when a pixel was detected as bare surface in a representative forest area; (ii) assessing clearcuts areas in chestnut forests, caused by coppice treatments rather than other bare soil occurrence causes (e.g., wildfires); and (iii) monitoring the impacts of chestnut management on land and soil degradation.

To investigate this expectation, a test was carried out at the regional level for the identification of clearcuts zones in Italy following two approaches: Firstly, bare soil reflectance data were obtained from an experimental area in central Italy (Campania) using PRISMA, Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 satellites images. Based on the forest fire map of the area of interest, clearcuts delineation was assessed separating fire pixels from clearcuts pixels. Subsequently, various methods for semi-automatic clearcut mapping were tested by pixel- and object-oriented

approaches. Finally, the monitoring of the impacts of chestnut management on land and soil degradation and the identification of eroded areas were conducted.

Our results indicate that multitemporal bare soil composites allowed, in relative terms, the assessment and monitoring of chestnut clearcuts zones, and the identification of eroded areas. The outcomes highlight the feasibility of the methodology in detecting sites with different resilience grades and the importance of developing alternative sustainable management practices avoiding trunks dragging.

Keywords: hyperspectral, coppice, soil erosion.

Macro and Micro Litter distribution in marine and coastal sediments: highlights from ongoing research activities

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The analysis of macro and micro litter in coastal and marine environments represents an ongoing scientific challenge worldwide. According to the international definition, marine and beach litter include all anthropogenic, manufactured, or processed solid items discarded, disposed of, or abandoned in the marine environment, including all such material brought indirectly to the ocean by rivers, sewage discharge, waves, tides, currents, and winds (GESAMP, 2019). Litter sources are multiple, both land- and sea-based, and therefore litter items have been documented in all existing coastal and marine environments (e.g., beaches, dunes, abyssal plains, and submarine canyons, among others).

Recently, several studies have been focused on the assessment of litter items in marine sediments, since they represent a preferential accumulation sink. Due to their dimension (>2.5 cm), macro litter items on beaches (beach litter – BL) can be easily identifiable by in-situ surveys, while the identification and classification of micro litter (i.e., microplastics – MPs) in sediments is still a challenge.

In this study, we present ongoing research activities aimed at the analysis of the distribution of BL and MPs in different sites located along the Apulian coastal sector, both on the Adriatic and the Ionian side and including respectively natural and urbanized areas (e.g., Torre Guaceto beach, close to Brindisi, and the Mar Piccolo basin of Taranto). To this aim, tailored sampling procedures and innovative analysis approaches have been proposed and tested.

In particular, a specific flight protocol has been developed to carry out unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) photogrammetric surveys suitable for the indirect analysis of BL along beaches. Indirect analyses include GIS-based and automatic approaches (Rizzo et al. 2023; Sozio et al. 2023). In both cases, high-resolution georeferenced orthomosaics obtained from the post-

processing of the images acquired by UAVs are required. In the first case, specific geodatabases are built through the manual visual screening of the orthomosaics. The databases are assembled by compiling the attribute table of the relative shapefile, reporting for each identified item its coordinates, the international code, and the material of which it is composed. In the second case, the automatic image analysis is computed by exploiting the potentiality in the segmentation and classification tasks of a specific Machine-learning algorithm. Ongoing activities are focused on increasing the accuracy of the tool by performing tailored training phases. Indirect BL analyses are aimed at integrating and supporting the in-situ monitoring activities that, despite ensuring precise and detailed items' identification, require high human efforts and turn out to be quite time-consuming (Rizzo et al. 2021). Furthermore, the use of a ground-based hyperspectral imaging (HSI) sensor has been tested at Torre Guaceto Beach for in-situ macroplastic litter classification (Bonifazi et al. 2023).

Concerning the microplastics (MPs) analysis, tailored procedures have been defined to collect sandy beach samples and marine sediments at different water depths in the shoreface and offshore. MPs identification task is performed by both standard and innovative methods. The latter are based on the exploitation of HSI working in the short-wave infrared range (1000-2500 nm) for the MPs classification directly within the matrix, avoiding complex and time-consuming pretreatment procedures (Bonifazi et al. 2024), and the application of a procedure that envisages the use of olive oil for MPs separation.

Preliminary results highlight that plastic represents the most abundant material identified along the investigated beaches and that BL items tend to accumulate in the upper part of the backshore with density values up to 1.24 items/m² (Rizzo et al. 2023) Furthermore, MPs detected in the analyzed samples are mainly represented by PP, PS, PE, and textile fibers (Cofano et al. 2023).

In compliance with the objectives of sustainable development, our investigations aim to develop rapid analysis methods to support the effective management of coastal areas and to reduce litter accumulation in marine and coastal ecosystems.

Keywords: beach litter, microplastics, coastal monitoring.

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Microplastics: from the detection to the characterization of their effects into the environment

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The large plastic consumption combined with inadequate waste management contributes to dispersion of microplastics (MPs, size <5mm) in all environmental compartments. MPs affect abiotic and biotic properties of various matrices (e.g. soil, water), for instance by altering edaphic fauna and plants (de Souza Machado et al., 2018). Different methods can be employed for MPs detection/characterization, resulting in high variability of literature data.

This contribution reviews the RETURN project’s achievements regarding environmental pollution by conventional MPs and bio-microplastics (bio-MPs). Various advanced methodologies were developed and fine-tuned depending on the targeted samples. Dedicated studies were also carried out to assess the effects of MPs/bio-MPs on soil quality and plant growth to identify potential environmental risks and hazards arising from the uncontrolled dispersion of such pollutants.

Innovative, fast, non-invasive hyperspectral imaging (HSI) combined with chemometrics and machine learning was used to analyze macroplastics and MPs/bio-MPs. The HSI devices used are capable of identifying/classifying plastic particles >150 µm and can be coupled with automated particle counting and measurement. Innovative procedures were developed and are being further improved to classify microplastics in different matrices, bypassing complex and

time-consuming pretreatment that may also cause material losses and poor detection inaccuracies.

Standard techniques (FTIR and micro-Raman) and HSI-based methods were applied during the project to identify MPs in beach and marine sediments from the Adriatic and Ionian sides of the Apulia Region. Beach litters (BL) on sandy beaches were also identified and classified by both direct in situ surveys and indirect approaches based on manual and automatic screening of images acquired by unmanned aerial vehicles photogrammetric surveys. Preliminary results highlighted that plastics represented the most abundant material in BL in the investigated beaches. BL items tended to accumulate in the upper part of the backshore (surface density up to 1.2 items/m²).

The HSI-based approach was also tailored to the identification of residual bio-MPs in digestate from anaerobic degradation of different bioplastic products. The technique was firstly tested in the short-wave infrared range on artificial samples constituting the training set, i.e. shredded bioplastic fragments in two size fractions (<500 and 500–1000 µm) on a filter paper covered with digestate. Principal Component Analysis was applied for data exploration, followed by Partial Least Square-Discriminant Analysis for particle classification. The method was validated on digestates after 30 days of Mater-Bi bioplastics degradation. The possibility to monitor bio-MPs particles >150 µm for digestate quality assessment was demonstrated.

A time-effective and non-disruptive Laser Direct InfraRed (LDIR)-based methodology was developed for MPs analysis in wastewaters. The method allowed particle counting and simultaneous physical and chemical characterization (MP recovery=96±4%). MPs removal efficiencies of 80-90% were estimated for the monitored wastewater treatment plants, depending on the process units. As a function of wastewater composition, plastic particles of various nature were detected, evidencing a prevalence of cellulosic materials.

Another detailed characterization technique based on micro-FTIR spectroscopy was applied for MPs analysis in three groundwater bodies (two karst caves and two monitoring bores of an alluvial aquifer). Water and groundwater invertebrates were collected and analyzed using fluorescence microscopy and micro-FTIR. Cellulose, polysaccharides and PET were the most abundant polymers. Evidence of microplastics ingestion by groundwater fauna is a warning sign.

Further efforts were devoted to understand the effects of MPs/bio-MPs on soil quality to identify potential environmental risks and impacts. The effects were evaluated through experiments in mesocosms with control soils added with 1-2% of MPs and bio-MPs in which lettuce plants were grown or earthworms were incubated. The analyses on the MPs-treated soils, covering both abiotic and biotic characteristics, showed that bio-MPs can impact soil quality. In particular, those in contact with plants display inhibited microbial activity while those with earthworms show stimulation.

Further studies investigated the impact of MPs on plant species. One involved the *Spirodela polyrhiza* water plant and evidenced a decrease in photosynthetic efficiency, starch concentration, alterations in plant ionome, and oxidative status in the presence of MPs. DNA analysis also showed MP-induced epigenetic modifications. The effects of MPs in soils were also investigated on tomato plants, showing that MPs negatively impacted crop productivity and fruit quality. The effect of MPs was also investigated on *Azolla filiculoides*, highlighting a decrease in photosynthetic efficiency, element content alterations, root tissue obliteration, and morphological changes in *Anabaena azolla* heterocyst.

In conclusion, advanced methods were developed for the analysis of MPs/bio-MPs in solid and aqueous matrices, evidencing heterogeneous contamination levels in samples and emphasizing the importance of fine-tuning the methodological approach based on the expected content and characteristics of MPs/bio-MPs. Evidence of both direct and indirect effects related to the presence of MPs/bio-MPs in the environment (e.g. soil, plants, biota) were suggested.

Keywords: earthquake, Otrions, catalogue.

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Monitoring microplastics in wastewater treatment plants

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Microplastics (MPs), i.e. plastic particles lower than 5 mm in size, represent a contaminant of growing concern due to their potential negative effects on ecosystems and organisms (Koelmans et al., 2022). Literature reports demonstrated that wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) exert high MPs removal efficiencies (up to 88–97%, depending on the process units implemented). Sewage sludge retains most of MPs removed in the treatment chain (water line), thus constituting a potential source of MPs pollution, especially if it is valorized in agriculture (Sun et al., 2019). Knowing the MPs behaviour in WWTPs is pivotal to design technological solutions able to mitigate their release into the environment. The absence of reference methodologies represents a limit for MPs monitoring purposes. In fact, different sampling, pretreatment and analysis methods can be applied, thus leading to a high variability of literature data.

In this perspective, this study aimed to develop an innovative, time-effective and highly automated Laser Direct InfraRed (LDIR)-based method for the detection and characterization of MPs in wastewaters. LDIR uses the latest quantum cascade laser (QCL) technology, combined with fast-scanning optics, to provide high-quality images and spectral data in the range of 975-1800 cm⁻¹, allowing both counting and comprehensive chemical and physical description of plastic particles.

The experimental and analytical procedures were firstly developed with artificial samples, i.e. aqueous dispersions containing 10 mg/L of standard MPs produced in the size range 38-106 μm from common items in ABS, HDPE and PET. The methodology validation was carried out by exploiting more conventional techniques (e.g. ATR-FTIR and Mastersizer). The methods were then applied to characterize the MPs content in the inlet and outlet sections of two large WWTPs in Tuscany: WWTPA, treating municipal wastewaters, and WWTPB, treating both municipal and industrial (textile) wastewater, the latter collected to the plant by a separate sewer system. In this regard, average daily composite samples of influent (IN), effluent (OUT), and industrial inlet from separate sewer (IN-SS) for WWTPB, were analyzed to estimate the removal efficiencies promoted by the monitored WWTPs. Preliminary tests were performed to determine the minimum sample volume to be processed depending on the expected MPs content.

The pretreatment method was fine-tuned as follows, achieving MPs recovery rate of $96\pm 4\%$: (1) sample concentration by vacuum-filtration (5 μm mesh size) and filter backwashing with ultrapure water, (2) chemical digestion via Fenton reaction, (3) density separation treatment (60 wt% ZnCl_2 solution); (4) MPs extraction by vacuum-filtration (5 μm mesh size) and filter backwashing with ethanol. Small aliquots (on the order of μL) of the dispersions of MPs in ethanol were analyzed by Agilent 8700 LDIR. Chemical identification of MPs was performed via real-time library matching. Size distribution and morphological characterization (i.e. classification into fibers, fragments, pellets and spheres) of the detected MPs were acquired based on the numerous dimensional and shape-related parameters provided by LDIR. Blank control samples were processed to evaluate the MPs cross-contamination. No alteration/degradation of MPs caused by Fenton reaction was observed, thus underlining the robustness of the applied pretreatment protocol.

Based on the results of LDIR analysis for IN and OUT samples, average MPs removal efficiencies from 80 to 91% were estimated for the monitored WWTPs. Large quantities of MPs were hence removed along the wastewater treatment chains and not discharged in receiving water bodies. Depending on the nature of the processed wastewater (i.e. municipal vs. industrial), various polymers were detected in IN and OUT, with a high abundance of cellulosic materials in all analyzed samples. In this regard, it should be considered that the LDIR spectral analysis classifies both natural and semi-synthetic/chemically modified cellulose particles (the latter used, for example, in artificial textile fibers) as “cellulosic”. It is worth noting that large amounts of PA, cellulose-derived and PU fibers, reasonably attributable to the textile nature of the industrial discharges, were collected to WWTPB by the separate sewer. In IN and OUT samples from WWTPA, MPs were mainly in the form of fragments (> 40%). Spheres were not found in the analyzed samples, thus suggesting that the detected particles were secondary MPs. Both WWTPs proved to be less effective in removing fiber-like MPs and particles in the size range 30-50 μm , in agreement with literature data (Sun et al., 2019).

In summary, the feasibility of applying robust, time-effective and highly automatized LDIR-based methods for the analysis of MPs in wastewaters was demonstrated. To be emphasized the possibility to acquire multiple size- and geometry-related parameters useful for modelling purposes (e.g. to study MPs behaviour in sedimentation units), which could support the design of targeted technological solutions for MPs removal.

Keywords: microplastics, laser direct InfraRed, wastewater.

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Multidisciplinary approach to investigate impact of MPs in soil

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MPs have become emerging pollutants in terrestrial ecosystems. In particular, agricultural ones represent the most vulnerable to their accumulation and consequently exert direct effects on plants and animals. The purpose of the research was to evaluate the effects of conventional microplastics (P-MP) and bio-microplastics (B-MP) on two model organisms *Lactuca sativa* sp. and *Eisenia fetida*. Experiments were set up in mesocosms with control soils (C) and with 1 and 2-% of both types of MPs in which lettuce plants were grown and, separately, earthworms were tested. Leaf functional traits and morphological parameters of plants were assessed and short-term and long-term toxicity tests with *E. fetida* were carried out according to ISO 11268-1-2:2012. For each rate (negative control and MPs-treated soils), the percent mortality and the percent loss/increase in biomass of the adults after fourteen days, and the number of offsprings produced after another period of fourteen days were provided. Subsequently, three

sexually mature earthworms per treatment (n° total= 15) were collected and processed for routine histopathology. Section were stained with Haematoxylin-Eosin (H-E) for morphological evaluation of body wall of *E. fetida* and with Alcian Blue-Periodic-Acid Schiff's (AB-PAS), for histochemical evaluation tissue of mucins. by histological techniques to identify possible microscopical alterations. All studied functional traits of plants grown in the treated soils showed significant differences between plants grown with B-MPs at 1% and 2% compared with C, instead of those growth with P-MPs where no significant differences were detected. Regarding mortality and biomass loss of *E. fetida*, no significant differences were found. In addition, the reproduction test results regarding the number of juveniles at the end of the prolonged exposure period (56 days) for all treatments showed no significant differences from the C condition. Instead, significant results were shown on a per-individual basis, in fact H&E stain revealed histological alterations in both segments of all treated groups compared to C samples. Specifically, P-MPs group showed, at 1%, muscle fibres nearly disintegrated, expansion of endomysial spaces and presence of abundant brown pigments in the circular muscle and at 2% degeneration of the epithelial cells and intramuscular infiltrate of haemocytes. B-MPs at 1- and 2% groups showed hyperplasia of epidermal layer exhibiting an almost complete disintegration and degeneration of the epithelial cell lining. AB-PAS stain revealed an increase of mucus production on the body surface in both segments of all treated groups compared to C samples. Specifically, cases from both P-MPs showed an increase of neutral mucins, while cases from both B-MPs showed an increase of acid mucins.

In conclusion, both model organisms experience effects from the MPs. In particular, it would seem that plants, probably exposed for a longer period of time, experience greater stress in the presence of the different percentages of B-MPs than P-MPs. Similarly, earthworms also show a state of inflammation probably due to the ingestion of B-MPs.

Keywords: microplastics, eco-toxicity, soil community

Novel wildfire simulation modeling and wildfire risk mitigation strategies

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Wildfires are a growing concern globally, particularly in regions with dense and flammable vegetation. The ability to predict and manage wildfires can be strengthened by simulation models that can accurately reflect real-world conditions. Field data collection focusing on Canopy Cover (CC), Canopy Base Height (CBH), and Tree Height (TH) is critical for validating spatial input data in wildfire simulation models. While effective for field or basin-scale analysis, this approach poses significant challenges when extended to larger, structurally

diverse areas. To overcome these limitations, remote sensing technology is increasingly utilized to estimate canopy fuels, providing a scalable method for data collection over extensive areas.

Comprehensive tables of static parameters, such as fuel maps and topography, are essential for each modeling approach and institution. These parameters help in creating accurate and reliable simulations that can be used for planning and response activities. Additionally, understanding the application scopes of different fuel models is necessary to grasp their range and limitations, ensuring that the right model is applied to the right scenario.

Based on these considerations, a comparative analysis of several wildfire propagation models, including Propagator (Trucchia et al., 2020; Perello et al., 2024), Tiger (Giannino et al., 2017), FlamMap (Finney, 2006), and Level Set Models (Alessandri et al., 2024), will be conducted. Each of these models has specific strengths and limitations. For instance, PROPAGATOR can perform simulations across the entire Italian territory, thanks to the availability of a national AI-informed fuel map. However, it lacks the capability to model the transition of surface fires into intense crown fires, which limits its effectiveness in representing the impact of fuel treatment on risk reduction. On the other hand, TIGER can accurately represent the combustion process but requires detailed local knowledge of vegetation structure parameters, making it difficult to upscale to a national level. Similar limitations are observed in Flame Map and the Level Set Model, both of which require local fuel map classification.

To address these limitations, a unified benchmarking framework for Italian wildfire case studies will be established. This framework aims to identify the main areas of improvement and integration across different models. By comparing the strengths and weaknesses of each model, we can develop a more comprehensive and effective approach to wildfire simulation and risk mitigation.

The final objective of this work is to provide a comprehensive framework that anticipates the potential impacts of a fire, starting from early detection and local meteorology through an innovative IoT network that triggers the simulation of the fire. The use of UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) is also considered for monitoring the initial stages of a fire. UAVs can provide continuous, high-resolution data on fire evolution, significantly improving the input data for the modeling chain. This approach enhances the accuracy of simulations and provides valuable real-time information for decision-makers.

Optimization techniques will be used within this framework to identify priorities for prevention strategies and to develop optimal intervention strategies for firefighting activities. By leveraging advanced technologies and comprehensive data analysis, we aim to improve the effectiveness of wildfire management strategies, ultimately reducing the risks and damages associated with wildfires.

In conclusion, integrating field data collection, remote sensing technology, and advanced wildfire propagation models presents a promising approach to enhancing wildfire simulation and risk mitigation strategies. By establishing a unified benchmarking framework and leveraging innovative technologies such as IoT networks and UAVs, this work aims to provide a comprehensive solution for anticipating and managing wildfire impacts. The ultimate goal is to improve the effectiveness of prevention and intervention strategies, thereby reducing the risks and damages associated with wildfires.

Keywords: wildfire simulation, remote and proximal sensing, fuel maps.

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Removal of organophosphorus compounds from aqueous solutions using Neapolitan Yellow Tuff: A preliminary study

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Adsorption processes are commonly employed in wastewater treatment to remove a wide range of pollutants. Organophosphorus compounds are widely utilized as insecticides and acaricides. Chlorfenvinphos ([2-chloro-1-(2,4-dichlorophenyl) ethenyl] diethyl phosphate) and Diazinon (O,O-diethyl O-[4-methyl-6-(propan-2-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl] phosphorothioate) are

commonly taken by the body through the ingestion of food products treated with the pesticides. Once absorbed they are widely distributed in the body and are in several body fluids Wagner et al. (1990), Klaassen et al. (2000).

This project represents a preliminary study aimed at the removal of such pesticides from aqueous solutions using a sedimentary rock largely available in the Campi Flegrei area (Naples, Italy), known as Neapolitan Yellow Tuff (NYT).

The efficacy of pollutants removal was evaluated by adsorption isotherms at room temperature in 0.01 M NaClO₄ at pH 5.5, a value representative of the pH of surface waters.

Isotherms were conducted to establish the affinity of target pollutant toward solid phase.

Kinetic data were analyzed using various models, including the pseudo-first and second-order models, as well as the intraparticle diffusion model Ho et al. (1999). Dynamic modelling results indicated that the process follows the pseudo-second-order kinetic model.

The adsorption process will be further studied as a function of pH, temperature, and ionic strength, which will provide information regarding the mechanism of absorption.

Keywords: pesticides, adsorption, Tuff.

Squalius cephalus exposed to PFAS downregulates Prdx4 gene expression in kidney

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Recently, the scientific community's attention has focused on emerging contaminants, as they are increasingly detected in several environmental matrices. Little is known about their transport, persistence and toxicity. Therefore, their potential impact on the physiology of freshwater animals requires further investigation. Among these xenobiotics, perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are known to determine some toxic effects on organisms, in particular, some studies showed their role in increasing the risk of oxidative stress. If not counteracted by the antioxidant system, the reactive oxygen species (ROS) overproduction can cause cellular damage due to the oxidation of macromolecules, such as lipids and proteins. Moreover, ROS can interfere with the correct lipid cell metabolism. In this study, we evaluated how chronic

environmental exposure to the two most harmful PFAS (PFOA and PFOS) affects the physiology of *Squalius cephalus*, a freshwater fish of the Veneto region. The kidney was analyzed, as one of the main organs responsible for PFAS elimination and one principal site for their accumulation. Our data show that low PFAS contamination is sufficient to increase protein oxidation; conversely, even high PFAS levels do not determine lipid peroxidation. In addition, Prdx4 gene expression highlighted a down-regulation, probably related to a physiological response important for increasing the lipid accumulation in the cell to prevent protein damage caused by PFAS.

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Keywords: peroxiredoxin 4, oxidative stress, antioxidant defences.

Stress granules as emerging biomarkers of PFAS environmental monitoring using *Squalius cephalus* as a bioindicator

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Perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are contaminants known to the scientific community for their persistence and toxicity in several environmental matrices, including freshwater streams. Our research aims to evaluate the effect of chronic environmental exposure to PFAS on the physiology of freshwater animals, both vertebrates and invertebrates, with particular reference to the involvement of stress granules (SGs). The latter are non-membranous cytoplasmic foci whose formation is stress-regulated and occurs with the overexpression of mRNA binding proteins, such as TTP, TIAR and G3BP, to temporarily block the translation of specific mRNAs inside SGs, thus allowing eukaryotic cells to regulate the global synthesis of anti-stress proteins rapidly.

Our study takes on a local perspective, as we have initiated the structural and functional characterization of the TTP protein in *Squalius cephalus*. Our aim is to study its gene expression in specimens sampled in freshwater streams in the Veneto region, a significant area for PFAS pollution research, at different pollution levels.

Using primers designed on TTP sequences of phylogenetically related fish species, we amplified part of the coding region, obtaining an amplicon of approximately 600 bp. Cloning into *E. coli* and subsequent sequencing returned a sequence of 565 nt, encoding 187 aa of a protein with 97.3% identity to TTP from the teleost *Abramis brama*.

Our future research plans are comprehensive and include gene expression studies using quantitative real-time PCR and in situ hybridization. These studies will be conducted in *S. cephalus* organs involved in xenobiotic accumulation and detoxification processes, such as the intestine, liver, kidney, and gills. This approach will provide a deeper understanding of the effects of PFAS on these organs and the potential of SGs as biomarkers for environmental monitoring.

Keywords: stress granules, PFAS, *Squalius cephalus*.

The One-health approach applied to micropollutants in the water environment: assessing the risk from sources to humans to plan monitoring and mitigation strategies

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Micropollutants, encompassing a diverse array of synthetic chemicals, such as pharmaceuticals, personal care products, pesticides, Per- and Poly-Fluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS), alkylphenols, and Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs), are increasingly detected in water systems globally. Despite their trace concentrations (ng/L - µg/L), micropollutants exert significant adverse effects, potentially disrupting ecosystems, compromising drinking water safety, and posing risks to human health. However, many sources of uncertainty are present, due to knowledge gaps in micropollutants release, occurrence, fate in the environment and toxicity effects. For instance, besides municipal and industrial wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), combined sewer overflows (CSOs) and WWTP bypass exacerbate micropollutant contamination during rain events (Ianes et al., 2023, 2024). Equally, agricultural activities contribute

significantly, with pesticides and fertilizers leaching into water bodies. Reuse of reclaimed wastewater in irrigation can transfer micropollutants to crops, posing human health risks (Penserini et al., 2023). Not less important, the materials in contact with drinking water can be an additional source of micropollutants (Cantoni et al., 2021).

Given the widespread and ubiquitous presence of micropollutants, the management of water quality in integrated urban water systems is a challenging task, in which it is fundamental to identify the primary pollutant sources, the pathways of their spread, and the receptors (ecosystem and/or human health), to properly allocate monitoring efforts and mitigation strategies. Hence, an effective management requires an integrated approach, involving comprehensive monitoring and fate modelling frameworks.

This research aims to explore the potential of integrated risk assessment procedures for prioritizing contaminants and compartments to be monitored in urban water systems, and determining the mitigation strategies that minimize the overall expected risk.

The developed risk assessment procedure includes three steps. Firstly, the analyzed system boundaries were defined, to consider the compartments and the contaminants involved, from sources to the final endpoint (environment or human health). As for the exposure assessment step, micropollutants concentration data were collected from the literature for each compartment of interest, to provide outputs of general validity and not case study specific. Additional modeling of micropollutants transport was used to predict their fate. Then, in the hazard assessment step, micropollutants toxicological characterization was retrieved from literature. Finally, in the third step (risk characterization), exposure and hazard assessment steps were combined to quantitatively estimate environmental or human health risk in different compartments (Cantoni et al., 2021; Penserini et al., 2022).

For environmental risk, the Risk Quotient was estimated as the ratio between environmental concentration and the Predicted No-Effect Concentration. For human health risk, the Benchmark Quotient was calculated as the contaminant exposure concentration, typically originating from crop or drinking water consumption, divided by its reference dose.

Uncertainty analyses were included to account for knowledge gaps, input data uncertainties and temporal-spatial variabilities, through Monte-Carlo simulations, by building the probabilistic distributions of the input variables to provide confidence levels for risk estimations.

Three systems within the integrated urban water systems were conceptualized, assessing the following risks:

1) Environmental risk to receiving surface water in which several PAHs are discharged from integrated wastewater systems during both dry- and wet-weather.

2) Human health risk contribution of tap water and crops consumption due to the presence of bisphenol A (BPA) and nonylphenol (NP) in both drinking water and irrigation water.

3) Simultaneous estimation of environmental and human health risks for pharmaceuticals from the indirect reuse of reclaimed wastewater.

Quantitative risk estimation supports the ranking of different mitigation strategies based on their risk reduction potential (Cantoni et al., 2024). In the first case study, CSOs result to pose the highest risk to surface water, followed by the WWTP bypass, and the WWTP effluent, indicating that mitigation strategies should be prioritized on CSOs. In the second case study, the human health risk for BPA was significantly higher than the one for NP, and crops consumption

determined a higher risk compared to tap water. Thus, interventions on soil and irrigation water, especially targeting BPA, would be more effective in reducing the overall risk. In the third case, a One Health approach is proposed: while human health risk from pharmaceuticals in reclaimed wastewater was substantially lower than the warning threshold, the environmental risk significantly contributes to the overall risk. Hence, special attention would be recommendable in terms of regulatory measures or additional targeted monitoring campaigns.

Results underscore the importance of implementing the risk assessment to the integrated urban water systems to address the complex challenges posed by micropollutants spread. By integrating comprehensive source monitoring, fate modelling tools, and quantitative risk assessment methodologies, it is possible to support the decision-making process in safeguarding water quality and protecting human health.

Keywords: contaminants of emerging concern, integrated urban water systems, risk assessment.

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Use of Toxicity Battery Index in prioritizing sites characterized by chemical contamination. A first application in Campania (Southern Italy) coastal areas

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The Toxicity test Battery integrated Index (TBI) compiles results from a suite of ecotoxicological tests into a single effect value, allowing for a synthetic reporting of the ecotoxicological risk at contaminated sites (Manzo et al. 2008). This method provides insights into the combined effects of chemical mixtures on organisms in polluted environments. The primary goal of this study is to employ TBI within a multi-hazard assessment framework to evaluate ecosystems contaminated with complex chemical mixtures. By jointly assessing ecological risk and ecotoxicological risk, the study aims to prioritize the substances that significantly influence ecological risk and the sites that are most exposed to hazardous chemical mixtures. The framework was applied to coastal water bodies in the Campania Region, known for widespread presence of potentially toxic elements (PTEs). The study involved the sampling of water and sediment from 27 coastal sites (September - October 2020 and June - July 2021) the analyses of the PTE occurrences, including As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Mo, Ni, Pb, U, V, and Zn in water, and As, Be, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Hg, Mn, Ni, Pb, U, V, Zn, Al, and Fe in sediments. The assessment identified a priority mixture of five elements (As, Cd, Cu, Ni, Zn) and evidenced sites

at risk, particularly near the mouths of the Volturno, Sarno, and Sele rivers. Results were in line with data from previous studies (Manzo et al., 2022). However, discrepancies between ecological risk and ecotoxicological risk suggest the need for a more in-depth analysis of exposure and effects in the site-specific conditions. These differences imply that factors beyond PTEs, including other pollutants and their interactions, may contribute to the observed toxicity. Moreover, climatic anomalies (e.g., oxygen and pH variations) may also play a significant role. The study underscores the complexity of assessing ecotoxicological and ecological risks in environments with different contaminants. To achieve a more comprehensive understanding of ecological risks at investigated sites, it is essential to identify additional pollutants influencing toxicity, understand the interactions between various contaminants, and consider the effects of climatic parameters on pollutant behavior and toxicity. By addressing these factors, we can develop more accurate and holistic risk assessments and enhance remediation strategies.

Keywords: ecotoxicology, risk, coastal areas.

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TS1 ‘Urban and metropolitan settlements’

A scalable procedure for evaluating multi-risk interactions: updating seismic vulnerability of buildings based on roof ash loads

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Assessing multi-risk is essential for accurate risk management and resilient planning. It helps predict cascading effects, such as how one hazard might amplify another, leading to more severe impacts. Natural hazard interactions include one hazard triggering the occurrence or affecting the rate of another (e.g., earthquakes followed by tsunamis or aftershocks) as well as the change in vulnerability of the exposed elements caused by the occurrence of two hazards close in time. An example is the load dependent modified vulnerability due to ash loads. In fact, ash loads can significantly increase the seismic vulnerability of buildings by adding extra weight, which strains structural components and can lead to collapse during an earthquake. Assessing this interaction is crucial in risk analysis to accurately predict the compounded effects of volcanic ash and seismic activity. This understanding ensures that building designs and retrofitting efforts adequately address both hazards, ultimately enhancing safety and resilience in affected areas.

In the field of multi-risk assessment, index-based approaches are highly useful as they provide a comprehensive, quantitative measure of various risks combined. By integrating multiple hazards into a single index, these methods facilitate the identification of areas with the highest cumulative risk, enabling targeted intervention and resource allocation. They simplify complex data into actionable insights, making it easier for policymakers and emergency planners to prioritize mitigation strategies. Additionally, these approaches enhance communication and understanding of risk levels among stakeholders and the public.

In this study we propose a methodology to comprehensively assess multi-hazard risks interactions at vulnerability level. Initially, a multi-risk index is created that integrates hazard, vulnerability, and exposure information for multiple hazards. The weight of hazard is determined by the physical dynamics of the phenomenon, that of exposure is influenced by the geometrical and typological characteristics of the building stock, and that of vulnerability arises from the impact of these parameters on vulnerability assessments from previous studies, which are based on their discriminative power through a hierarchical classification (Del Gaudio et al., 2018; Del Gaudio et al., 2021). At this stage, the index does not account for any interactions between vulnerabilities. This step ensures a baseline understanding of the overall risk profile for different municipalities. Using the multi-risk index, municipalities potentially most affected by multi-hazard risks are identified and selected as case studies for further analysis, focusing resources on the areas that need them most. A load-dependent vulnerability model is developed firstly determining seismic vulnerability based on non-linear response (pushover) of building response of mechanical model of building. This procedure is repeated using a Monte Carlo Simulation technique, introducing random variables to define fragility curves (Del Gaudio et al., 2017). Subsequently, load-dependent fragility curves are updated considering the potential roof failure due to ash loads and the influence of the ensuing additional loads in the non-linear response of building subjected to lateral loads. Finally, the multi-risk index is updated to incorporate the new vulnerability interactions. This step ensures that the index now reflects the compounded effects of multiple hazards at the vulnerability level, providing a more holistic and accurate risk

assessment. This refined approach aids in better resource allocation, mitigation planning, and enhancing community resilience against multiple hazards.

Keywords: multi-risk, load-dependent vulnerability.

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Analysis of Dissipative and Low-Dissipative structures through to the Loss-Based Earthquake Engineering

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Eurocode 8 allows force-based seismic design and safety assessment of buildings as if they were indefinitely linearly elastic. However, to implicitly account for their inelastic deformation capacity, Eurocode 8 allows the reduction of the design values of seismic forces through the seismic behavior factor (q).

If a plastic analysis is performed, dissipative members are designed to undergo plastic deformation dissipating energy. This design procedure should consider the damaging for those dissipative members and then the impact on the expected annual loss due to their replacement and/or retrofitting.

The paper provides a closed-form equation to identify the cost required by a dissipative building, designed according to the capacity design approach, to be economically competitive respect to a low-dissipative building, designed to remain in elastic field.

Keywords: loss-based earthquake engineering, low dissipative structures, dissipative structures.

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Climate change in the urban settings: effects on the general and on the occupational population

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As reported by the World Health Organization, global temperatures and heat waves will increase (in terms of frequency and intensity) over the course of this century. The long-term effects of exposure to high temperatures can cause physiological stress by aggravating respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. The acute effects of heat waves, on the other hand, more often lead to an increase in population mortality. In this regard, it is important to underline how the increase in temperatures affects the entire population, but how, at the same time, only some groups are more exposed (e.g. particular types of workers) or more vulnerable to physiological stress (e.g., the elderly, infants and children, pregnant women).

To analyze the effects of climate change comprehensively, two different literature reviews are currently in preparation, focusing on the evaluation of the effects of climate change on (i) the general population and (ii) the occupationally exposed population.

- Climate change and health effects in the general population: a systematic review and meta-analysis with focus on urban settings.

We searched for scientific literature using three different databases (Scopus, Web of Science, and PubMed). A search query, incorporating a list of keywords, was set up for each database. A total of 26,862 papers were initially identified. After removal of 4,850 duplicate the total number of identified articles was 22,012. The articles will be subjected to a two-tier screening process involving (i) title evaluation, and (ii) abstract evaluation. We will select articles focusing on the evaluation of climate change effects on the general population in Europe. Inclusion and exclusion criteria are the following: scientific papers written in English, excluding conference proceedings, review articles, book chapters, case studies, toxicological studies, and animal studies. Phases i-ii (i.e., screening of the papers by title and abstract) will be conducted independently by different authors to minimize potential operator dependent bias. The reporting of this will adhere to the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) criteria guidelines, ensuring a systematic and transparent approach to the review process and reporting.

- Climate change and health effects in the occupationally exposed population: an umbrella review.

The search of literature relating to the evaluation of the effects of climate change on the occupational population was also performed using three different databases (Scopus, Web of Science, and PubMed). A total of 2.005 articles were identified, with 874, 496, and 635 papers retrieved from Scopus, Web of Science, and PubMed, respectively. After removal of 555 duplicate entries the total number of screened articles was 1.450. Screening of the title and abstract led to the elimination of 1383 and 22 articles, respectively. We selected systematic reviews investigating effects of climate change on the occupational population.

Exclusion/inclusion criteria of the articles were: scientific review papers written in English, excluding conference proceedings, book chapters, case studies, toxicological studies, and animal studies. Screening of the articles by title and abstract was conducted independently by two different researchers to minimize potential operator-related errors. We will adhere to the PRISMA and PRIOR criteria guidelines, ensuring a systematic and transparent approach and reporting. Next steps include (i) finalization of the umbrella review; (ii) review of studies reporting practices for risk prevention in the occupational setting (iii) focus on effects and preventive strategies in the urban setting.

Keywords: Climate Change; urban; general and Occupational Population.

Fragility curves For Masonry-infilled RC buildings subjected to pyroclastic density currents

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Pyroclastic density currents (PDCs) are a multiphase mixture of hot volcanic gases and pyroclastic particles of different sizes and properties. Due to their sudden onset and destructive power, PDCs have been recognized as one of the primary causes of fatalities during volcanic eruptions. In addition to the significant threat represented by the capacity of these currents to bury large areas under thick layers of pyroclastic deposits in a short time, the high concentration of fine ashes, and the lethal temperature, an additional threat is represented by their dynamic pressure and the capacity to incorporate and transport loose rocks that can produce heavy damage to structures as well as triggering structural collapse.

Especially in densely urbanized areas, the correct assessment of building vulnerability to PDCs is essential for accurately predicting the potential impact of PDCs on the built environment. This assessment could represent a suitable tool to support either the emergency planning phase or the implementation of disaster mitigation strategies during peacetime.

To achieve this objective, we propose utilizing the STICK model, originally developed for assessing the seismic performance of reinforced concrete (RC) buildings under earthquake ground motions, to generate damage fragility curves for RC buildings exposed to the dynamic pressures induced by PDCs during explosive volcanic eruptions. The STICK model, a simplified Multi-Degree-of-Freedom model consisting of lumped masses at the story level connected by nonlinear shear springs placed in series, has been adapted within a tailored probabilistic framework to accurately simulate building responses to PDC-induced dynamic pressures, accounting for potential variations in pressure profiles resulting from the out-of-plane collapse of infill panels. This study wants to provide a first update to existing literature studies addressing the ultimate capacity assessment of RC buildings under PDCs.

Keywords: pyroclastic density currents, reinforced concrete, fragility curves.

Identifying buildings' envelope vulnerabilities against natural hazards to reduce risk to the urban system

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Building envelope elements are exposed to a range of natural hazards, including geophysical, chemical, and meteorological factors. These hazards can lead to the degradation and potential collapse of building elements, posing significant risks to the functionality and safety of buildings and their surroundings. Consequently, property managers and public authorities must understand the impact of these factors to prevent their consequences. Despite the importance of this issue, studies specifically examining the vulnerability of building envelopes are limited. National-scale data indicate that certain building envelope elements, such as cornices, plasters, and roof coverings, are particularly susceptible to damage. This susceptibility depends on the technological characteristics and physical condition of the elements. Therefore, it is crucial to identify less vulnerable technological solutions against specific hazards and proactively monitor the physical condition of these elements. Studies conducted so far have identified the natural hazards to which building envelopes are most exposed and the consequent damage mechanisms. This has allowed the development of a preliminary list of vulnerability factors, which are characteristics that increase the susceptibility of building envelope elements to damage. This result represents the first step in assessing the vulnerability of building envelopes and the associated building risk. The application of the results achieved is underway, including the formulation of an above-building scale vulnerability index that considers the characteristics, physical conditions, and relevance of the building envelope elements in terms of building risk. The risks arising from the damage to building envelope elements are quantified by considering potential harm to people and property, economic losses, and obstruction of escape routes.

Keywords: vulnerability factors, building risk, natural hazards.

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Interpreting Urban Resilience Capacity: a comprehensive catalogue of spatial indicators

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Resilience is a critical concept in urban studies and planning, as cities encounter increasing challenges and stressors such as climate change, natural hazards, rapid urbanization, and biodiversity loss. In urban contexts, we can apply the concept of “urban resilience” contextualizing it as a multifaceted concept that encompasses the ability of cities to withstand and recover from acute shocks and chronic stresses (Meerow et al., 2016). Furthermore, resilience is seen as a powerful and transformative concept that has the potential to reframe planning practices and interventions (Giovannini et al., 2020). By incorporating the concept of transformative resilience into planning practices and interventions, a more comprehensive and forward-thinking approach to promoting resilient urban environments can emerge. This perspective lays the groundwork for practical applications and interventions aimed at building and enhancing urban resilience.

Starting from these concepts, an initial analysis was carried out on existing approaches to measuring urban resilience. This analysis identified some limitations, such as a lack of standardized indicators and a focus on specific urban components rather than the entire urban system. To address these limitations, the research proposes a framework for evaluation that aims to overcome traditional methods, which mainly focus on specific risks and lack a holistic and comprehensive perspective. The complex nature of resilience makes it necessary to include all the different dimensions of an urban system in order to define a resilience evaluation framework (Sharifi & Yagamata, 2016). These dimensions include: i) the built environment, ii) environmental, iii) economic, iv) social and v) institutional dimension. Moreover, the framework builds upon the concept of “resilience capacities”, such as Robustness, Redundancy, Diversity, Integration, Transparency, Flexibility, Reflectiveness, Resourcefulness, which are a city’s inherent strengths that enable it to respond effectively to disruptions (Ribeiro & Gonçalves, 2019). The resulting framework uses specific indicators within each dimension to evaluate a city’s overall resilience capacity. The selection of indicators is crucial and should consider the application type, the territory characteristics and local conditions, data availability and reference scale.

While the initial set of indicators derived from the literature database provides a valuable foundation, it focuses on Scopus-indexed literature. The research acknowledges the initial limitations of the indicator set, such as its underrepresentation of cultural aspects. It proposes expanding the data sources beyond academic literature to include local databases

and grey literature for a more comprehensive evaluation. Finally, the research emphasizes the importance of testing the framework on real-world case studies to further refine its effectiveness in supporting decision-making and planning for resilient urban development.

Keywords: urban resilience, spatial planning, progress indicators.

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Models for the assessment of seismic vulnerability of buildings and their applicability in a multi-risk approach

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This work is developed within WP3 of Transverse Spoke 1 “Urban and Metropolitan Settlements”. According to RETURN taxonomy, vulnerability is the propensity or predisposition to be adversely affected by an adverse event. This is a crucial part for risk and multi-risk assessment since, as it is well known, risk depends on hazard, vulnerability, and exposure.

This work is focused on models and methods for the assessment of the seismic vulnerability of buildings, a part of the gray infrastructure of the urban system characterized by both physical and functional vulnerability. Analytical, empirical, mixed, and judgment-based vulnerability models are investigated. Discrete (indicators) and continuous (fragility and vulnerability curves) metrics of vulnerability are discussed. These topics are presented in a general-purpose framework but, based on the literature, potential peculiarities of residential, educational, hospital, industrial, and cultural heritage buildings are also discussed.

Finally, state- and age-dependent seismic vulnerability models are presented, as they allow considering seismic vulnerability of buildings in a multi-risk assessment framework.

Keywords: vulnerability, seismic, buildings.

Multi-Risk Analysis in the City of Genoa: Classification of Residential Buildings and Demographic Data for Vulnerability and Impact Assessments

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Genoa is a polycentric, dense, stratified, and socially heterogeneous city. For this reason, it is an interesting case study for multi-risk analysis at a territorial scale. Within the framework of TS1 (Urban and Metropolitan Settlements), an in-depth study on the historical evolution of Genoese residential buildings and the configuration of its social fabric is being developed, with the aim of carrying out a multi-risk assessment starting from seismic hazards and including other hazards such as floods and heatwaves.

The analysis of the evolution of the built environment in the City of Genoa was conducted to classify recurring building types and then associate them with specific structural characteristics for seismic vulnerability purposes. This information allows for a more accurate taxonomy (Lagomarsino et al., 2024) compared to that derived from ISTAT data, which characterizes residential buildings in census sections based on material, construction age, and number of floors. The work is based on the CARTIS methodology (Zuccaro et al., 2023), which enables a detailed characterization of building structural types at urban scale through extensive bibliographic, cartographic, and archival research, as well as expert interviews. The result is a division of the city into 13 homogeneous compartments based on urban development and prevalent typologies.

The classification of the built environment, limited to residential buildings only, identified seven distinct types based on historical evolution characteristics:

1. Medieval Aggregate House: Load-bearing structure in masonry with limestone blocks, lime and sand mortar, masonry vaults on the ground floor, and wooden floors.
2. Renaissance Villa and Palace: Load-bearing structure in split or mixed limestone masonry, lime and sand mortar, masonry vaults on the ground floor, and wooden floors.
3. Block: Load-bearing structure in split or mixed limestone masonry, lime and sand mortar, wooden floors.
4. Courtyard House: Load-bearing structure in split or mixed limestone masonry, reinforced concrete, and mixed infill masonry with stone and bricks. Wooden or brick-cement floors.
5. Popular Apartment Building: Low houses with load-bearing structure in limestone blocks or bricks. Tall houses with reinforced concrete frame, infill in limestone masonry or bricks. Brick-cement floors.
6. Modern Apartment Building: Load-bearing structure in reinforced concrete, infill in limestone masonry or bricks. Brick-cement floors.
7. Row House: Load-bearing structure in reinforced concrete, infill in limestone masonry or bricks. Brick-cement floors.

Following the proposed historical analysis, an effort was made to understand current social, economic, and cultural dynamics that could influence the impact on the population of the different considered hazards (earthquake, flood, heatwaves). Therefore, the built environment analysis was followed by a population analysis, starting from GIS representations of demographic data extracted from ISTAT. The analysis conducted so far has revealed a city divided into two opposites, a division also reflected in the built environment expansion: an affluent and commercial area to the east, and a working-class and industrial area to the west. The historical center and the areas of Sampierdarena, Cornigliano, Pontedecimo, and Lagaccio host the majority of foreign residents, with larger households and a generally younger population. In particular, the historic center shows an almost total absence of the population over 74 years old. The eastern area, on the other hand, has an older population, higher education levels, and smaller households.

The exposure and vulnerability analysis was conducted in a GIS environment by integrating various informational layers. Taxonomic attributes were derived from image interpretation (Google Street View) and on-site surveys. The seismic vulnerability of residential buildings will be associated with the different building types using the heuristic-macroseismic method (Lagomarsino et al., 2021) and, for masonry buildings, with the mechanical-analytical DBV-masonry model (Cattari et al., 2021).

Within the RETURN group of the University of Genoa, there are skills that will allow further study of other natural hazards, particularly: pluvial flood (Arianna Cauteruccio), river flood (Silvia De Angeli), heat waves and extreme wind actions (Giuseppe Piccardo, Federico Canepa), landslides (Rossella Bovolenta, Ilaria Ferrando).

Keywords: urban risk, seismic and social vulnerability, residential buildings.

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Towards the integration of circular economy (TS1) and sustainability (VS4) principles into a framework to identify the contaminated site remediation reducing risks

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The risk assessment associated with contaminated sites is a regulated procedure under Article 242 of Legislative Decree 152/06, which allows the determination of site-specific environmental health risks for particular target on the site, considering one or more exposure pathways. The environmental and health risks arising from contaminated sites are widespread and particularly impactful in Italy, where more than 16,000 remediation procedures (Araneo et Bartolucci, 2021) are underway for areas that pose potential risks to the environment and the surrounding population. Among these, there are 42 Sites of National Interest (SIN), which, due to their extent and levels of contamination, are managed directly by the Ministry. These sites cover a total land area of just under 150,000 hectares, representing 0.49% of Italy's territory.

According to Article 242 of Legislative Decree 152/06 and community regulations, it is crucial to identify the best intervention techniques at sustainable costs (B.A.T.N.E.E.C. – Best Available Technology Not Entailing Excessive Costs) to remediate these contaminated areas. Naturally, when choosing the remediation intervention to apply, it is essential to consider sustainability comprehensively and thus analyse also the environmental and social impacts, as the dig-and-dump solution has been practiced for too long and isn't sustainable. Ex-ante sustainability assessments to guide interventions towards solutions not only for reducing health and environmental risks but also aimed at being as sustainable as possible and adhering to circularity principles are respectively addressed in two tasks of different Spokes, described below.

Indeed, during the development of Return, a strong synergy was identified between the themes addressed by Spoke VS4 and TS1, whose deliverables will be integrated to create a single decision-making framework with the aim of guiding the choice of intervention strategy towards remediation solutions that are not only sustainable but also attentive to the application of circular economy principles. Specifically, this involves the integration of Tasks:

- 4.5.4 “Sustainable remediation technologies for contaminated site, brownfield and mining sites recovery and regeneration” from Spoke VS4 and
- 5.4.4 “Towards a circular metabolism for urban and metropolitan settlements” from Spoke TS1.

Regarding the development of a model for identifying sustainable remediation technologies and interventions within VS4, a study is being developed that outlines and evaluates innovative technologies for the treatment of contaminated soils and sediments that

have low impact. Guidelines are being developed with the identification of useful indicators to support the most sustainable choices.

Instead Task 5.4.4 of WP4 deals with risk mitigation in urban and metropolitan areas through the adoption of circular strategies. Circular Urban Metabolism links two closely related concepts, the first is circular cities and the second is urban metabolism. These concepts aim to promote the transition to regenerative resource management, thus moving away from a linear approach toward circular management of input and output flows in order to reduce environmental, as well as economic and social impacts.

Circular Urban Metabolism evaluation in multi-risk urban and metropolitan contexts, also involves the field of contaminated sites remediation that are often an integral part of a vulnerable urban area but also a part of territory and citizens historical memory. The application of circular principles, in association with national and international technical standard recently published for measuring circular processes in organizations (UNI/TS 11820, ISO/WD 5902), are very important in order to define strategies and actions for measuring a specific circular process through specific indicators. Such elements should be applied to critical urban contexts requalification in order to find the best remediation technologies that are more sustainable but also more circular in resources' management.

Circularity must be applied leading to benefits that are sustainable from an environmental, social and an economic point of view. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate sustainability and circularity jointly.

Knowledge concerning the application of the circular economy may be useful in order to develop a new methodology applicable to the remediation of contaminated decommissioning sites. The main goal is to develop a method with sustainability and circularity indicators that can be useful to guide toward increasingly sustainable and circular remediation choices even though Italian regulations currently do not reward the application of innovative technologies over dig&dump.

Keywords: circular economy, sustainability, contaminated sites.

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Urban Living Lab to Co-design the transition of Site of National Interest (SIN): first exercises applied to Bagnoli (Naples)

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Urban Living Labs (ULL) are physical and virtual environments where innovative planning and design measures and strategies for urban and metropolitan settlements are co-created, co-designed, and co-evaluated to support the green and sustainable transition. ULLs involve local stakeholders, communities, and experts to share knowledge about the impact and perception of risk in multi-risk scenarios and to support the design process in all phases toward Circular Urban Metabolism.

This work presents the initial results of a multidisciplinary and collaborative exercise between Tasks "5.4.4 - Towards a Circular Metabolism for Urban and Metropolitan Settlements" and "5.5.2 - City-Scale Exercise for Risk Scenarios Evaluation" (WP4 and WP5 of Transversal Spoke 1). This exercise was applied to the area of Bagnoli, which was declared a Site of National Interest (SIN) by ministerial decree on 08/07/14 in 2014. In Italy contaminated Sites of National Interest - SIN - have been identified at a national scale, by law, for reclamation purposes based on site characteristics, quantity and hazardousness of pollutants, the extent of the environmental impact in terms of health and ecological risk, and the detriment to cultural and environmental heritage. SINS are areas of unique environmental value identified, by law, according to the quantity and the risk of pollutants, and the impact on the environment also in terms of ecological and health risks. The SIN of Bagnoli, spanning 249 hectares on land and 1,453 hectares at sea, was chosen among the 42 Italian Sites of National Interest due to its complex multi-risk conditions resulting from overlapping anthropic, environmental, and natural risks.

Keywords: Urban Living Lab, Contaminated Sites of National Interest - SIN, Circular Urban Metabolism.

TS2 'Multi-risk resilience of critical infrastructures'

A resilience-based decision support system for wildfire risk management, prevention, and land protection

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Wildfires represent frequent disasters in Italy due to its territorial traits, as it stands among the Mediterranean regions where such events prevail, particularly during the summer months. However, over recent decades, the impacts of climate change have accelerated these risks, resulting in heightened wildfire frequency and severity. Furthermore, the widespread occurrence of soil degradation has compounded the vulnerability of ecosystems, increasing the likelihood of wildfires (Nazir et al., 2024). In wildfire risk management, territorial knowledge plays a crucial role and is evaluated within a Decision Support System (DSS) geared toward prevention strategies and emergency responses. A DSS includes a suite of tools, procedures, and software designed to aid individuals or organizations in the decision-making process by providing pertinent information, conducting data analysis, and offering modelling tools. It is essential for informed decision-making both before and after disaster events, capable of incorporating region-specific legislative requirements, as advocated by Terribile et al. (2024).

The innovation within the current framework revolves around establishing a resilience-based DSS capable of sourcing data from resilience indicators of critical infrastructure to manage and mitigate risks such as wildfires. The effectiveness of the DSS relies on the quality of the data it receives, necessitating a holistic understanding of complex systems to design the tool effectively within a decision-making framework. This comprehensive approach involves modelling wildfire hazard and its effects on critical infrastructures, in terms of resilience reduction. Emphasis is placed on understanding wildfire behaviour due to the criticality of the underlying processes governing fire spread. Consequently, a profound grasp of wildfire scenarios and the requisite parameters to accurately simulate fire evolution across diverse vegetation types within a territory is imperative for effectively feeding the decision support algorithm. Furthermore, integration with knowledge of past wildfires proves critical in comprehending their territorial distribution and the infrastructure impacted. By examining parameters such as fire line intensity and fuel characteristics, the research yields insights into the dynamics of wildfire propagation, highlighting the necessity for accurate input data and the enhancement of territorial resilience and management.

The examination of the specific data pertaining to climate, vegetation, and land configuration reveals key factors that modulate fire risk, thereby laying robust foundations for devising targeted preventive strategies. Given the influence of meteorological conditions, particularly wind, on wildfire propagation, geostatistical modelling assumes fundamental importance for analysis and modelling of regionalized phenomena (Berardi et al., 2023). Probabilistic modelling of these phenomena is pivotal for comprehending their spatial and temporal variability.

A central element in this process is the variogram function, which describes the dissimilarity between points in a spatial field as a function of their distance. The variogram is essential for the modelling and interpreting spatial data, capturing continuity characteristics and the structure of spatial variability. For estimating meteorological variables, the non-stationary geostatistical estimator is applied. This method allows the analysis to adapt to local variations in spatial properties, improving the accuracy of the estimates.

Once the estimation algorithm for meteorological variables is defined through a geostatistical model, characterizing the ignition probability model for specific points becomes crucial. This facilitates prior identification of points in a territory necessitating monitoring and enables effective emergency response planning. To achieve this, a Poisson distribution-based modelling approach is proposed, offering a well-defined procedure that analyses historical wildfire data and can serve a predictive function within a resilience-based framework. Time-dependence emerges as a key aspect of emergency management, enabling the recalibration of infrastructure in the event of a wildfire and facilitating the identification of alternative routes and solutions, thereby assisting infrastructure managers in ensuring service continuity. The imperative for the Decision Support System to operate continuously, even during the pre-event management phase under ordinary conditions, is highlighted. Equipped to identify all potential hazards present in the territory, particularly those associated with infrastructure, the system activates emergency procedures when critical events occur, encompassing all relevant policies and procedures. This research underscores the significance of parameter modelling in assessing wildfire risks, suggesting a flexible and adaptable methodological framework suitable for diverse contexts, in alignment with the objectives of resilience modelling and multi-risk management.

Keywords: disaster risk management; wildfire resilience modelling; decision support system.

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A risk-based framework for emergency management of bridges

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The collapse of bridges can result in significant economic losses, transportation disruptions, and potential loss of human lives. Various factors can contribute to bridge failures, with local scouring around the foundation being identified as the predominant cause for bridges spanning over watercourses [1]. Scour is the removal of bed material near bridge foundations and has been identified as a leading factor in numerous bridge collapses globally [1-3]. Therefore, assessing the risk of scour for bridge foundations is crucial for optimizing resource allocation and developing maintenance and emergency plans. The use of sensor and communication technologies allow monitoring scour depth at critical bridge locations, considering the effect of consecutive flood events [4]. However, monitoring an entire infrastructure network is not economically feasible, therefore it is preferable to install scour sensors at specific piers of critical bridges [4].

This project seeks to develop a probabilistic framework for the risk-based emergency management of a network of riverine bridges prone to scour. The proposed approach leverages the correlation between the water flow at the bridge locations to infer information about non-monitored bridges from monitoring data collected at key bridges. The proposed framework is based on the use of a Bayesian Probabilistic network (BPN) to model the conditional dependencies among the scour depths at the bridges in the network. The Bayesian network is constructed using two primary equations: the Manning equation for calculating the flow depth directly upstream of bridges and the HEC-18 pier scour equation for determining the scour depth at a particular pier. In the development of the proposed BPN, model uncertainties are defined as updatable nodes [4, 5]. The uncertainty in each of the input parameters used in scour calculations and, consequently, in the BPN is characterized by a probability density function (PDF) defined by the distribution type (normal, lognormal, etc.) and the distribution properties (mean, standard deviation, etc.) [6]. The proposed probabilistic framework is applied to a network of four bridges spanning the Mincio river in Italy, with only one bridge equipped with a scour monitoring system. A Monte Carlo simulation is employed to estimate the prior probability density functions (PDFs) of the upstream flow depth and the scour depth at each pier of each bridge. Subsequently, the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm will be utilized to conduct Bayesian learning and update the root nodes of the proposed Bayesian Network. The updated physics-based models will be employed to evaluate the structural reliability of the bridges in the network, taking into account the remaining capacity of the scoured bridges and the external loads (demands) acting on them. By using information on the reliability of bridges in the network and evaluating the direct and indirect costs linked to various management strategies, decision-makers will be able to determine the most effective maintenance and management approach.

Keywords: bridge network, flood, monitoring.

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A simplified approach to the risk assessment of infrastructures subjected to snow avalanches

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The large number of infrastructures in Italian territory subjected to snow avalanches requires a model to the assessment of risk with respect to natural events. Considering the risk concept as a combination of hazard, vulnerability, and exposure, the proposed model is based on the classification of each of these three factors, within five levels (high, medium-high, medium, medium-low, low). The first factor, avalanche hazard, depends on the “likelihood of avalanches”, intended as the chance of an avalanche releasing within a specific slope and return period. In this sense, it will be defined on the basis of avalanche hazard maps. On the other hand, the vulnerability level of the infrastructure is mainly affected by its “robustness”, intended as the capability of the structure against disproportionate collapse when subjected to extreme loading condition, e.g. natural hazard. The exposure level is defined depending on the use of the infrastructure. When the level of each factor is determined, it is possible to assess the level of risk of each infrastructure under investigation within the above-mentioned five categories. It is worth noting that this decomposition allows a clear identification of the factors affecting the risk level, thus enabling its effective management as well as assisting institutional decision-makers in the prioritization of appropriate mitigation strategies. As a matter of fact, the proposed model can be applied to different types of systems (buildings, infrastructures, ecc...), thus providing a consistent tool to a homogeneous assessment of risk with respect to snow avalanches, at a given territory scale.

Keywords: snow avalanches, risk assessment.

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A two-phase procedure to model historical vulnerabilities against NaTech: Lightning-triggered events in industrial critical infrastructures

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Climate change trends could significantly increase annual damage to industrial infrastructure in Europe while the Sendai Framework advocates for bolstering resilience against natural hazards, as a principle for safeguarding critical infrastructure. This infrastructure, spanning various sectors, provides indispensable services to society but is vulnerable to the impacts of natural disasters triggering technological accidents (Krausmann et al., 2017). The understanding of these vulnerabilities is crucial for mitigating losses in lives, livelihoods, and the environment.

Historical analysis plays a pivotal role in evaluating the likelihood and consequences of NaTech events (Ricci et al., 2021). Focusing on lightning-triggered NaTech events, which presents a critical trade-off based on their frequency and catastrophic consequences in the process industry (Renni et al., 2010), this study presents a methodology to model the NaTech vulnerabilities of industrial infrastructure, employing advanced methodologies to address data scarcity and incompleteness (Moriguchi et al., 2023).

Phase 1, focuses on source selection, dataset setting, and technical criteria definition. A dataset of 689 lightning-triggered NaTech events was compiled from open-source industrial accident databases as a principal output (Castro Rodriguez et al., 2023). Rigorous inclusion criteria were defined, aligning with NaTech research and international standards.

Moving to phase 2, it involves event characterization and modeling techniques facing the uncertainty of data. During the characterization (Phase 2-part 1), was verified that 80% of lightning-triggered NaTech resulted in significant incidents, predominantly in the Chemical and Petrochemical sectors during regular plant operations. “Storage equipment” and “electric and electronic devices” were the most vulnerable items among the damaged categories, with fire being the predominant final scenario.

On the other hand, phase 2-part 2 encompassed the application of modeling techniques to increase vulnerability awareness. The event tree analysis with reduced datasets contributes to understanding the complexity of the logic events pathways from the triggering natural factor and branches that lead to increasingly specific potential consequences. Bayesian network algorithms were applied to model conditional relationships between the variables in the identified event tree (lightning damage sources, states of damages, infrastructure, and triggered scenarios). Conditional probability tables (CPTs) were derived, and the relative frequency (belief) was obtained for the five functional variables considered in the model, after treating the uncertainty for the unknown records.

The novel insights obtained through this methodological procedure, allow to consider in a probabilistic perspective the uncertain historical data available, providing an important additional view that contributes to strengthening the decision-making process to face the industrial vulnerability against NaTech events (Castro Rodriguez et al., 2024).

Keywords: process industry, lightning strikes, NaTech.

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Advances in landslide susceptibility assessment at regional scale

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Landslides represent a severe geohazard in many countries. The availability of inventories depicting the spatial and temporal distribution of landslides is crucial for assessing landslide susceptibility and risk for territorial planning or investigating landscape evolution. For the Italian territory, several landslide hazard and risk maps, from regional to national scale, were produced. This was possible thanks to the availability of the IFFI dataset, a unique long-time landslide inventory collected and maintained by ISPRA institute. However, the real usefulness of this inventory is rather limited due to their common spatial inhomogeneity or use of different mapping methods and classification criteria.

Despite the evolution in the last years of the techniques used to assess the natural hazard susceptibility at national scale such as statistical models, AI based models (i.e. Convolutional Neural Networks) and others, was impressive, the results are still limited by the quality of the data used, in particular, of the landslide inventory used. Actually, other geodatabases from local to regional scale are available such those of the “Hydrological Districts”, a public authority in charge of regulating territorial planning, under the safeguard against landslides and floods. They cannot cover the entire Italian territory, nevertheless, locally, they could represent an improvement in precision and accuracy with respect to the national dataset available, mainly due to the higher scale of resolution than the IFFI one.

In this work, we present an innovative approach to assess landslide susceptibility, from local to municipal scale, based on regional landslide inventories. Using a data-driven machine learning technique, we propose to train a single model on a landslide inventory consisting of a composition of regional inventories selected to be representative of the national scenario. The weighted model is now able to predict landslide susceptibility in any Italian study area. The entire analysis has been done using the STGEE tool for Google Earth Engine and the SZ-plugin for QGIS. The data used and processed are freely available and downloadable.

The approach proposed has been tested in the framework of RETURN project, a PNRR project.

Keywords: Landslide, susceptibility, statistic model.

An integrated monitoring network to assess the coastal landslide risk

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Coastal retreat is the landward displacement of shoreline because of marine erosion, cliff failures or flooding. Usually, it is contrasted by protection works constructed on very specific sites, to solve concrete and urgent problems. Most of them constitute a temporary remedial without a general erosion management plan, while coastal erosion management must be organized at fully scales (i.e. at a large, regional scale) in which the dynamics of the whole coastal system must be represented. Cliff failures are predominantly linked with the lithology, the structure of the rocky mass as well as the weather conditions and the wave action. The factors, intrinsically affecting the stability of cliffs, are the lithological, stratigraphic, structural, and morphological settings and the hydrogeology and the mechanical properties of the rocky mass. The external factors are represented by impact of sea waves, currents, and tides, as well as meteorological agents, the biological activity of marine micro and macro-organisms and the human activities.

These phenomena pose severe hazard to infrastructure (Figure 1) and can cause extensive damage when interacting with the anthropized environment and the elements at risk (Lentini et al., 2021). The identification of risk areas is therefore essential, and it is a preliminary step to assess the coastal landslide risk. In the case of cliff, the basic factors controlling erosion are the force of waves at the base of cliffs and the mechanical strength of rock masses (Lentini et al., 2021). Additional factors are reduction in rock strength owing to weathering by sea spray, tidal action, temperature variations and material fatigue caused by cyclic loading of the wave action. The stability of the coastal cliffs is normally analyzed similarly to that of the rocky slope, by geo-structural analyses and stress-strain modeling, with a pseudo-static analysis of the action of wave motion incident at the cliff toe. Nevertheless, cliff failures are predominantly linked with the lithology, the structure of the rocky mass, as well as, to the weather conditions and the wave action. So, in the coastal area, the analysis about the morphological evolution and instability, that affect the cliffs, requires understanding of the complex framework of interactions between the internal characteristics of the coastal system and the external stresses, including sea wave action and weathering. For this reason, methods to assess cliff erosion must take into consideration the possibility to include these aspects in the estimation of the rocky cliff stability. With this aim, new methods can be elaborated considering a modification of the classification system based on the Slope Mass Rating Index (SMR), through the integration of additional parameters such as wave action and rock mass conditions.

To analyze the destabilizing effect of the waves on the cliff, it is also necessary to examine the frequency of the wave motion, since just the not very energetic but extremely continuous waves cause the erosion of the coastal slopes, also associated with mechanisms of failure, due to cyclic stress of the rocky mass. For this purpose, measures like the ambient noise and strong-motion records can be used to analyze the dynamic behavior of the cliff. Ambient noise can be extracted from random noise through appropriate techniques, such as Horizontal-to-Vertical Spectral Ratio (HVSr).

The interpretation of these measures, related to the effect of the wave pulse and propagation on the cliff, can be supported by the mechanical characterization of the rocky mass, to individuate a correlation between the dynamic response of the cliff to the wave action and the

structural properties of the rocky mass. These methodologies were applied to a lot of areas prone to landslides, often consisting in shallow movements induced by rainfall. Among these, the municipality of Gioiosa Marea (Sicily, South Italy), where the road network is frequently interested by traffic disruptions due to landslides, has been considered a target for the calibration of the models (Gatto et al., 2023).

The proposed study aims to develop a procedure useful for the identification of intervention priority in the case of infrastructures, and to provides a basis and a practical guide for the improvement of the efficiency of the transport infrastructures.

Keywords: integrated monitoring network, coastal landslide risk, Slope Mass Rating Index (SMR).

Application of Geomatics Techniques for Surveying and Structural Monitoring of Artificial Cavities

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Accurate surveying of caves is vital for understanding their formation, current condition, and potential hazards, particularly in challenging environments with limited accessibility and poor visibility. This study explores the application of geomatics techniques, including Terrestrial Laser Scanning (TLS), SLAM-based Mobile Mapping Systems (MMS) (Idrees, M., 2016; DeWaele, J., 2018), and digital photogrammetry (Teppati Losè, L. 2021), to create three-dimensional models of artificial caves.

The artificial caves of Gravina in Puglia are part of a unique geological and cultural heritage characterized by deep valley incisions with steep walls. These caves have been historically utilized for various purposes, including dwellings, wine cellars, and rainwater cisterns. Over time, the interaction between human settlement and geological features has created a complex network of subterranean spaces. Accurate mapping and documentation of these caves are necessary to evaluate their structural integrity and potential hazards, especially given their precarious state and the risks they pose to overlying structures and populations.

Three different techniques were employed for the survey: TLS using the Leica RTC360, SLAM-based MMS using KAARTA Stencil 2, and digital photogrammetry using the spherical camera Insta360 One RS 1-inch edition. The TLS provided high-precision data with an acquisition speed of up to 2,000,000 points per second and a range of up to 130 meters. The SLAM-based MMS offered a more portable and cost-effective solution with an acquisition speed of up to 300,000 points per second and a range of up to 100 meters. The digital photogrammetry approach, using a 360-degree camera, allowed for quick and comprehensive data collection with minimal capture time.

The survey campaign conducted in May 2023 focused on an anthropic cavity known as the "Cantina del Principe". Data acquisition involved 15 static TLS scans, a 4-minute MMS scan, and a 3.5-minute video recording with the 360-degree camera. The TLS data served as a ground truth for assessing the accuracy and quality of the SLAM-MMS and spherical photogrammetry point clouds. Post-processing of TLS data yielded a highly accurate point cloud with an ICP registration error of 0.003 meters.

Cloud-to-Cloud (C2C) analysis was performed to compare the point clouds obtained from MMS and spherical photogrammetry with the TLS reference model. The results showed an RMSE of 3.18 cm for the MMS point cloud and 11.3 cm for the spherical photogrammetry point cloud. The digital photogrammetry approach faced inconsistencies in model reconstruction due to inadequate image coverage or higher traversal speeds during video acquisition.

The study highlights the potential of SLAM-based MMS for rapid and cost-effective data acquisition, offering significant portability and autonomy. Digital photogrammetry also proved

to be a viable alternative, providing comprehensive data collection capabilities. However, the TLS system, despite being more expensive and less portable, provided the highest precision and accuracy.

Future research should focus on optimizing these techniques for enhanced hazard assessment and structural monitoring in challenging underground environments. The three-dimensional models generated can also facilitate finite element geomechanical analyses, providing insights into the stability of the cavity-structure system and aiding in the preservation and management of this invaluable subterranean heritage.

Acknowledgements

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Keywords: underground survey, 3D data analysis, artificial caves.

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Assessment and monitoring of critical reinforced concrete infrastructure affected by chloride-induced corrosion

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Corrosion poses a significant challenge in the development and execution of risk analysis and mitigation plans for existing infrastructure. Assessing its economic impact reveals significant figures: technical reports estimate an annual direct cost of corrosion for United States highway bridges at 13.6 billion USD, while indirect costs to users, including traffic delays and loss of productivity, are estimated to be ten times higher according to life-cycle analyses. This underscores corrosion as more than just an economic concern, as it can lead to catastrophic failures, often in conjunction with other factors, as recent incidents have demonstrated.

Coastal regions, in particular, deserve careful attention due to their rapid growth and urbanization, which have required the construction of extensive transportation networks vulnerable to chloride-induced atmospheric corrosion. Deterioration resulting from corrosion in these areas can compromise infrastructure performance and reliability, exacerbating the risk posed by other hazards such as earthquakes or tsunamis.

This contribution aims to introduce advanced tools for the structural assessment and monitoring of critical reinforced concrete infrastructure affected by chloride-induced corrosion. Initially, the development of probabilistic corrosion hazard maps for reinforced concrete bridges in coastal regions is proposed to facilitate their numerical and experimental evaluation. These maps will aid in resource allocation and prioritization for in-situ surveys and structural monitoring campaigns. Additionally, ongoing efforts to utilize advanced technologies for structural monitoring of corroded reinforced concrete elements will be discussed, including laboratory tests exploring the feasibility of 3D laser vibrometry and digital image correlation.

Keywords: corrosion, digital image correlation, laser vibrometry.

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Comprehensive collection and preliminary comparative analysis of observed and modeled wave data along the entire italian coastline

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The availability of high-resolution and accurate wave data is crucial for proper assessment of coastal flooding. Therefore, in the framework of Spoke TS2 of WP3/DV 3.1.c "Mapping of Coastal Flooding Induced by Extreme Wind Waves," a comprehensive analysis of available wave time series—including observations, hindcast, reanalysis, and projections—will be conducted to map coastal flood areas resulting from extreme events. Furthermore, a high-resolution case study will be developed by simulating inundation along a specific stretch of the Tyrrhenian coast in Calabria.

As part of the ongoing work in WP3 – TS2, significant effort has been devoted to collecting meteocean data observed by wave and oceanographic stations distributed along the entire Italian coastline. This includes historical time series from wave buoys managed by the National Wave Measurement Network (RON – ISPRA), research centers, regional agencies, and port authorities. The collected data will be compiled into a technical report, featuring performance metrics and technical graphs illustrating the wave climate.

Reanalyzed and projected data series, both past and future, used in the analyses have been interpolated to points closest to the wave buoys. These series are made accessible through Copernicus in collaboration with ECMWF, via the Climate Change Service Dataset (C3S). The reanalyzed series are derived from the ERA5-Reanalysis dataset (Hersbach et al., 2020), offering global coverage from 1940 to the present. Another dataset provided by C3S focuses on coastal wave climate, detailing surface ocean wave parameters over a European domain, providing insights into wave climate response to climate change in the northwestern European shelf and the Mediterranean Sea.

To assess the impact of climate change on ocean surface waves, the SAW wave model, implemented by ECMWF, was utilized for numerical simulations across three different climate scenarios: the present-day (historical) climate, covering 2001 to 2017, as represented by another ERA5-Reanalysis product (Pörtner et al., 2019). Furthermore, wave time series have been projected for future scenarios using the "Representative Concentration Pathways" (RCP) 4.5 and 8.5, spanning 2041 to 2100.

The collaboration between Spoke VS1-Water and Spoke TS2 - Multi Risk Resilience of Critical Infrastructures has enriched the database of forcing data available for coastal flood risk analysis in Spoke TS2. Specifically, the Meteocean Research Group at the University of Genoa developed two comprehensive hindcast datasets of wave climate using the Wavewatch III model. The "Hindcast Regular" dataset features a regular 10 km grid providing consistent spatial

resolution (Mentaschi et al., 2015), while the "Hindcast Unstructured" dataset offers variable and detailed resolution at a local level.

Additionally, a multi-model ensemble of wave climate projections was developed based on twenty-neurocordal models, combining global and regional climate models with a temporal resolution of 6 hours and a spatial resolution of approximately 12.5 km. These wave climate simulations cover a baseline period (1970-2005) and a future high-emission scenario RCP8.5 (2006-2100).

Model data provide consistent information on wave climate and are essential to have a better understanding of the past and possible future projections, making them crucial for flood risk assessment along the Italian coast. However, the comparison between observations and model results is crucial to validate their accuracy. In the initial phase, the performance of the modeled data was evaluated against the observed data from wave buoys, which serve as a benchmark for model accuracy. Statistical indices used in the analysis revealed slight discrepancies between observations and hindcast data, indicating that the model outputs require adjustments.

In the next phase of the work, bias correction techniques will be applied to the wave climate, addressing the complexity arising from temporal and spatial wave variability (Lira-Loarca, et al., 2023). This procedure will be implemented for both reanalyzed and hindcast model data and projections.

The model time series were extrapolated to points closest to the wave buoys. As an initial step, the performance of the modeled data against the observed data from the wave buoys, used as a benchmark for model accuracy, was evaluated. An initial analysis of the modeled data performance in reanalysis and hindcast was conducted using statistical indices applied to each available buoy. In the next phase of the work, bias correction techniques will be applied to the wave climate, addressing the complexity arising from temporal and spatial wave variability (Lira-Loarca, et al., 2023). This procedure will be implemented for both reanalyzed and hindcast model data and projections.

Keywords: meteocean data, wave climate analysis, bias adjustment.

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Development of industrial rack fragility models to support industrial seismic risk assessment

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The earthquakes that struck Italy highlighted the significant seismic vulnerability of steel pallet racks. Despite this, these racks remain the most widely used industrial storage system due to their high cost-effectiveness, flexibility of use, and ease of assembly. To correctly estimate the impact of a seismic event on industrial sites, it is imperative to investigate the vulnerability of these components. This study aims at accurately estimating the direct and indirect damage that may result from their failure, as well as at enhancing job security in industrial buildings.

Steel pallet racks require particular attention because they are not conventional structures. Many specific factors impact their seismic vulnerability, such as the high slenderness of steel profiles; the use of semi-rigid connections that impart high deformability, especially in the longitudinal direction; local, distortional, and global buckling phenomena; high live loads; and the limited ductility of steel profiles in Class 3 or 4. Furthermore, many racks currently in use in Italy, predate current seismic standards and were designed only for static loads, making them inadequate to withstand even limited inertial forces. Despite the awareness of this vulnerability and the widespread use of these systems, their seismic fragility has yet to be investigated in a comprehensive manner.

This ongoing study aims to determine the seismic fragility of these structures to enable more accurate enterprise risk assessment and the development of effective retrofit strategies. Nearly 30 of the most common types of unbraced pallet racks are analyzed using nonlinear 3D models and nonlinear time history analysis (TH), by applying 268 bidirectional ground motions for a total of 7236 TH analyses performed. A MATLAB code was developed to automatically generate the geometries of the selected racks, then implemented into Finite-Element (FE) models within the OpenSees software framework.

Specific engineering demand parameters (EDPs) are identified, along with threshold values that signify various damage states (DSs) of increasing severity. Four primary EDPs are considered: i) a comprehensive strain parameter (including both axial and flexural strain) for the uprights (ϵ^*); ii) the maximum drift between load levels in the down-aisle direction (θX); the maximum rotations iii) of beam-to-column nodes (ϕ_{btc}) and iv) of base connections (ϕ_{base}). Fragility is also assessed according to additional EDPs, which quantify the dropping of certain volumes (in %) of pallets and the yielding of certain amounts (in %) of beam-to-column connections. In addition, two intensity measures (IMs) are used in this study, S_a and PGA.

Keywords: seismic fragility, steel pallet racks, nonlinear dynamic analysis.

Experimental investigation design for validating tsunami action models on structures/infrastructures according to standard codes

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Recently, numerous scientific researches are focused on evaluating vulnerability and mitigating risks associated with tsunamis, drawing on different areas of expertise, technical documentation, and protocols crucial for effective tsunami preparedness and response. Particularly, FEMA P-646 (2012) provides comprehensive technical guidelines for designing structures resilient to tsunami forces. This document encompasses the identification of pertinent tsunami loads, the establishment of design criteria, methodologies for calculating tsunami forces, and the characteristics of structural systems appropriate for vertical evacuation during tsunami events. Regular updates ensure that FEMA P-646 (2012) reflects the latest advancements and best practices. Moreover, numerous design provisions from FEMA P-646 (2012) are incorporated into ASCE/SEI 7-16 (2017), a publication by the American Society of Civil Engineers, which offers an extensive framework for defining minimum loads, hazard levels, associated criteria, and performance objectives for buildings and structures in tsunami-prone regions.

Over the past few decades, numerous experimental studies, Moon et al. (2014), Wüthrich et al. (2018) and Chuang et al. (2020), have been conducted to investigate wave pressures and forces on building structures, aiming to address the knowledge gap on tsunami impacts. The consequences of tsunamis depend largely on factors such as ocean bathymetry, coastal topography, hydrology, geology, as well as the type and characteristic of structures impacted.

In this study, the experimental investigation design for validating tsunami action models on various structures and infrastructures according to standard codes is presented. The laboratory setup consists of a 2D wave phenomena reproduction channel located in the Maritime Engineering laboratory of the University of Palermo. The channel measures 40 meters in length, 2 meters in width, and 1.90 meters in depth. It is equipped with a modern piston-type wave-maker designed by HR Wallingford, enabling the production of regular, irregular, and solitary waves. Level measurements are conducted using a series of resistive gauges, while velocity measurements are obtained through ADV-type gauges (Acoustic Doppler Velocimeter).

The building model will be situated approximately 35 meters horizontally from the wave maker on a sloped plane designed to replicate the coastal shoreline. Sensors attached to building models will measure the time histories of pressures acting on the faces impacted by waves. Furthermore, scaled structural models will be connected to a triaxial load cell able of

measuring orthogonal forces in the x, y, and z directions, as well as moment components (M_x , M_y , and M_z).

Keywords: tsunami, experimental investigation, action models.

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Flood Prone-Area Mapping Through Advanced Machine Learning Techniques and Geomorphic Data Integration

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Flood events rank among the most destructive natural hazards, necessitating comprehensive risk management strategies to mitigate their impact on human health, the environment, cultural heritage, and economic activities. In this context, various approaches have been developed for identifying flood-prone areas (Manfreda et al. 2015; Samela et al. 2017; D'Angelo et al. 2022), but there is still a need to enhance their capabilities due to dynamic changes in landscape and infrastructure.

In recent years, remote sensing observations have been a proliferation that can support dynamic and continuous mapping of flood-prone areas by integrating the most updated information (Albertini et al., 2022). This study explores the potential of the Random Forest model, utilizing 24 factors such as slope, elevation, precipitation, land use/land cover, HAND, GFI, and others as input data (Kaya and Derin, 2023). The variables were analyzed by measuring their importance and impact on the methodology, avoiding high correlations between them, ensuring relevance, and avoiding redundancy. The method considered optimizing the model, to improve the accuracy and reduce the complexity. Calibration and validation of the model employ Copernicus Emergency Management Service maps from Sentinel satellites coupled with regional maps of historical flood events.

Results highlight that not every combination of factors produces a coherent prediction. 7 sets of factors were evaluated. The high accuracy was obtained by adopting a range of 7 to 9 variables, where the third and fourth sets obtained the higher accuracy (AUCROC, 0.94). Furthermore, the effective delineation of flood-prone areas was obtained with the first set (GFI, Rainfall, Elevation, Lithology, Organic Matter, Land use/Land Cover, NDVI) with an accuracy equal to 0.926. The study demonstrates that minimal information (between 0.1% and 10%) suffices for optimal model performance.

The study covered the entire territory of Italy, resulting in a flood-prone map at a 90m resolution, compared with flood maps provided by national agencies and obtained through traditional hydraulic models (Lastoria et al. 2021).

Keywords: flood-prone areas, Machine Learning, GFI.

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FOCA: the Italian FLOod and Catchment Atlas

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In recent years, the development of national databases featuring geomorphoclimatic watershed attributes has gained significant attention. Notable examples include the CAMELS datasets (which have been compiled for countries such as the United States, Chile, Brazil, Australia, the United Kingdom, Switzerland, France, Germany, Sweden, and Czechia) now unified under the Caravan initiative, as well as LamaH-CE and BULL. Italy has lagged in this regard, primarily due to the dismantlement of its national hydrographic service (now replaced by 21 different administrative agencies) and to problems related to data availability.

To address this gap, we created the Italian FLOod and Catchment Atlas (FOCA; Claps et al., 2024), a comprehensive dataset encompassing 631 gauged Italian river basins. This dataset integrates hydrological data from the "Catalogo delle Piene dei Corsi d'acqua Italiani" (Claps et al., 2020) with over 100 attributes related to geomorphology, soil, land cover, NDVI, climate, and extreme precipitation.

FOCA stands out due to its adherence to three main criteria in data selection: a) national spatial coverage; b) the absence of regional or local distortions; c) and adequate spatial resolution. Local data sources were prioritized to ensure high-quality information, resorting to global datasets only when necessary. This approach allows FOCA to provide a comprehensive and accurate portrayal of Italy's watershed characteristics.

A key feature of FOCA is its extensive set of geomorphological descriptors, computed using the *r.basin* algorithm of GRASS GIS. These descriptors underwent rigorous quality control, ensuring their reliability and usefulness for various hydrological analyses. Additionally, FOCA includes extreme rainfall characteristics, derived from the Improved Italian - Rainfall Extreme Dataset (I2-RED; Mazzoglio et al., 2020). This dataset comprises rainfall extremes measured by over 5000 rain gauges from 1916 to the present, making it a valuable resource for understanding extreme precipitation patterns.

The inclusion of basin boundaries in FOCA further enhances its utility, enabling users to integrate additional descriptors using their models or datasets. This flexibility supports a wide range of environmental and hydrological applications, particularly those focusing on flood studies. With FOCA, it is now possible to undertake nationwide basin-scale hydrological applications, leveraging high-resolution quality-controlled data to address flood-related issues.

Keywords: attributes, basin, hydrology.

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Impact of detention dams on flood frequency distributions: the case study of Ottenstein dam (Austria)

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During the last decades, the growing number of hydrological extremes has raised economic losses and risk perception worldwide. In this context, climate change and anthropic activities are likely accelerating the occurrence of floods (Merz et al., 2021).

Detention basins can be effective tools for attenuating peak discharges (UDFCD, 2016). However, the proper design of a detention system is extremely challenging due to its impact on the hydrological response of the basin.

With this aim, new analytical-probabilistic approaches have been developed to interpret the functional relationships between inflows and expected outflows from dams (Eagleson, 1972). In particular, Manfreda et al. (2021) defined a theoretically derived probability distribution (TDD) of the peak outflows from in-line detention basins. This framework was further explored by Albertini et al. (2022) to design a flood detection system in a river basin in southern Italy.

The objective of this work is to investigate the effect of flood control structures on the downstream flood frequency curves using the approach of Manfreda et al. (2021). The case study is the Ottenstein dam on the river Kamp in Lower Austria. The reservoir has a live storage area of 51 million m³ and its connected catchment has an area of 889 km². The normal operating level is not exceeded during floods due to two spillway crests, equipped with automatic gates. However, in this work, a simplified schematisation of the dam was considered; in particular, the water regulation level has been set roughly at the level of the crest spillway.

As reported in Manfreda et al. (2021), it is possible to derive the peak outflow associated with an incoming flood peak. In particular, the outflow is null as long as the reservoir is filled up to the regulation level, and thereafter, it is controlled by the crest spillway. In this last configuration, it is possible to use the linear reservoir concept for the water volume accumulated above the crest in order to estimate the peak outflow. The inverse function of the linear reservoir equation can be used to analytically compute the theoretically derived probability distribution (TDD) of the peak outflow from the detention basin.

The proposed framework has been tested with regard to the case study of the Ottenstein dam, comparing the theoretically derived distribution with the results obtained from a numerical simulation and the observed flood data. In particular, the cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of the TDD have been compared to the empirical CDFs, estimated by means of the plotting position approach applied to the observed flood peaks (upstream and downstream of the dam).

The results show a good agreement between the obtained TDDs and the observed data, mainly for low discharge values. However, it is worth remarking that the obtained findings are the result of a conceptual study, predicted on simplifying assumptions regarding the reservoir

operation. The effective operation, instead, is extremely complex and challenging due to the interplay between hydropower generation and flood control (Reszler et al., 2008).

Keywords: detention basin, theoretically derived probability distribution, flood frequency distribution.

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Mesoscale maps of the wind hazard over Italy

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The design wind speed is commonly determined through wind speed maps. Synoptic extreme winds are traditionally mapped at the lower bound of countrywide macroscale resolution (hundreds of km) based on time series of records measured at land anemometric stations, while the assessment of the design wind speed at the construction site is entrusted to the designer within the so-called return criterion formalized by Ballio et al., 1999 that it is traditionally adopted in Italy through the standards in force (DM 17-01-2018; EN 1991-1-4:2005).

Coarse, uneven distribution of the stations, uncertainties in their setup, and measurement errors are among the drawbacks of the mapping. Challenging subjective evaluation of the exposure roughness and inconsistencies among various national wind provisions are some of the critical issues affecting the return approach. The proposed approach is based on the weather forecast computational model developed by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts, its reanalysis by means of assimilated remote sensing observations (ERA5), and the dynamic downscaling based on the COSMO convection permitting model, carried out by the Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC) over the Italian Country (Raffa et al 2021, Raffa et al 2023). Wind speed maps over the Italian Country are critically compared with measurements at 21 land anemometric stations. The errors made by each model are assessed for current and extreme wind speed with different return periods. The error affecting the once in 50-year wind speed is compared with the one made by applying an in-force standard. The directionless wind speed at 10-meter height above the ground is mapped in terms of the mean current wind speed V , and of extreme wind speeds with return period T_R equal 2, 50, 100 and 200 years over the whole Italian Country.

The research output consists in the Italian mesoscale maps of the wind hazard, published in a webGIS platform based on a tailored geodatabase available at <https://geowindy.polito.it/projects>). The map planimetric resolution reflects the model native one and it is equal to about 2.2 km. To obtain the design wind speed from the reference value provided by the map, a correction factor covering in average modelling errors shall be applied. By comparing obtained results with the most reliable anemometric stations, the values of the model correction factor are equal to 0.95, 1.20, 1.38, 1.42 and 1.47 for the mean wind speed and for extreme wind speeds with T_R 2, 50, 100 and 200 years, respectively. Interested readers can find a detailed description of the study in Raffaele et al 2024.

The research and development activities are currently focusing on general methods for georeferencing the wind hazard metrics in the mesoscale map, and for downscaling from mesoscale to micro scale along specific segments of critical infrastructures. In particular, the focus is on cross regions Italian critical infrastructures with complex topographies, such as the Alps and Apennine Mountain chains, and rugged coastlines. In these areas, further downscaling is mandatory to account for microscale wind flow conditions. In progress work is focused on

downscaling wind field from meso- to microscale to account for local orographic effects, e.g. induced by gorges and escarpments on viaducts.

This study was carried out within the RETURN Extended Partnership and received funding from the Euro-pean Union Next-GenerationEU (National Recovery and Resilience Plan – NRRP, Mission 4, Component 2, Investment 1.3 – D.D. 1243 2/8/2022, PE0000005) – SPOKE TS 2. This study would not have been possible without the huge research effort paid by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) and by the Foundation Euro-Mediterranean Centre on Climate Change (CMCC), and the datasets ERA5 (<https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.adbb2d47>), ERA5-Land (<https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.e2161bac>), VHR-REA_IT (https://doi.org/10.25424/cmcc/era5-2km_italy) and CORINE Land Cover 2018 (<https://doi.org/10.2909/71c95a07-e296-44fc-b22b-415f42acdf0>) made available in Open Access.

Keywords: wind hazard mesoscale map, current and extreme speeds, webGIS.

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Natural Hazard Triggering Technological Disasters (NaTech): data analysis and risk assessment

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Natech disasters (Natural Hazard Triggering Technological Disasters) represent a category of events where natural hazards trigger technological incidents, causing significant damage to infrastructure, ecosystems, and human communities. This phenomenon has become increasingly relevant due to the rising frequency and intensity of natural disasters, often linked to climate change, and the growing interconnection of modern technological infrastructures.

In fact, Natech events account for between 2% and 8% of the total number of incidents, and they are rapidly increasing due to the rise in extreme weather phenomena (Ricci et al., 2021).

Natech events are characterized by their complex nature, as they combine risk factors associated with both natural events and technological incidents. Typical scenarios include earthquakes damaging chemical plants, floods causing hazardous substances to spill from storage tanks, and hurricanes disrupting electrical and communication networks. The combination of these factors can amplify the overall impact of the event, making emergency management and response much more challenging.

Indeed, the impact of Natech disasters can be severe. Immediate consequences include explosions, fires, and the release of toxic substances into the environment. In the long term, these events can cause soil and water contamination, public health problems, and severe economic damage.

For the assessment of Natech risk, it is essential to understand the interactions between natural hazards and the vulnerabilities of technological infrastructures (Cozzani et al., 2014). Advanced tools such as simulation models and probabilistic analysis techniques are used to predict possible Natech scenarios and to develop effective mitigation strategies.

Natech risk management involves proactive planning and the design of resilient infrastructures. Mitigation measures include the construction of physical barriers to protect industrial installations from floods and the adoption of seismic building standards. Additionally, the implementation of monitoring and early warning systems can improve the ability to respond promptly to Natech events.

Through the application of the methodologies developed in the POC 3 case study, the analysis will highlight the dynamics and consequences of Natech disasters.

Keywords: Natech event, risk assessment, multi-risk approach.

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Physically-based modeling for dam filling prediction

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Dams are systems of engineering essential for drinkable purposes and energy production, essential issues in the modern days due to the energy crisis and climate change associated with fossil fuel consumption. In addition to this, artificial reservoirs play a crucial role in water storage and river flow regulation, contributing to the mitigation of flood risks for downstream inhabited areas. Therefore, understanding the dam system in all its elements from design to operation and maintenance is essential to ensure the capacity of performing constantly its function.

One element able to reduce the reservoir capacity and thus limit the functions of the dam system is the phenomenon of the dam filling (i.e. the gradual accumulation of sediments within the reservoir). It can cause a reduction of the total capacity and limit the functionality, especially in terms of hydroelectric energy production. The aim of the work is to evaluate the response of an erosion and sediment transport model applied to the dam filling issue in different geological contexts (Corti et al., 2023); to reach this target, the physically based model SMART-SED (Sustainable Management of sediment transpoRT in responSE to climate change conDitions), developed in recent years by the Politecnico di Milano (Gatti et al. 2023) was applied. SMART-SED can simulate hydrological, erosion, and sediment transport processes at a watershed scale, starting from geographical and meteorological input data, often available for free from regional/national geoportals or global databases. The final raster-type outputs relate to various simulated processes, such as water velocity, water and sediment height, infiltration, erosion, evapotranspiration, and liquid/solid flow values for each calculation time step at user-defined control points.

The SMART-SED model was applied to different case studies in Italy covering different areas and geological contexts: in the North Italy the watersheds of the Tartano stream (SO) and the Caldane stream (LC) were considered, whereas in South Italy the Carmine and Nocellito dams along the Alento River (SA) were tested: the analysis started from historical data on dam filling, such as bathymetry and sediment volumes removed over the years. Following a sensitivity analysis of input parameters and calibration related to land use and local geological context, SMART-SED was applied to the above cases simulating different years to assess sediment production under varying rainfall regimes. The obtained results were then validated based on available dam filling data. It was observed that the SMART-SED model, initially designed for assessing flood hazard and sediment transport in mountainous areas, is also suitable for estimating dam filling. The model provided a precise approximation of the order of magnitude of the cumulative volume of sediments produced within the analyzed watersheds and transported into the reservoirs.

Furthermore, the validated SMART-SED model will be applied to the Camastra dam completed in 1968. The reservoir of the Camastra dam shows signs of the phenomenon of the dam filling: in specific, starting from an initial reservoir capacity of 35,3 106 m³, a reservoir capacity of 17.6 106 m³ was estimated in 2017, because of the sediment present. The collection

of all the necessary data to estimate the current sediment volume is now in progress and successfully a comparison between experimental data and simulated ones would be carried out. One of the future developments will be also the simulation of rainfall variation due to climate change with the aim to develop different dam filling scenarios depending on this parameter.

Keywords: dam filling, physically-based modeling, sediment transport.

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Potentialities of the satellite-based monitoring of multi-span pre-stressed concrete bridges

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The aging of structures, material degradation, and increased traffic are just a few of the factors threatening the structural integrity of bridges, which are critical components of global transportation infrastructure networks. These bridges not only facilitate rapid and safe connections but also play a fundamental role in supporting economic development and social interactions. Ensuring the integrity and usability of bridges is therefore essential not only for safeguarding the health and lives of users but also for mitigating (when it is not possible to avoid) potential indirect losses. This is particularly true for strategic bridges for road traffic, where interruptions could significantly impact economic activities and society.

Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) techniques constitute an effective tool for those who manage and supervise the integrity of civil structures and infrastructures. Traditionally, these techniques use sensors such as strain gauges, accelerometers, or load cells that can acquire real-time information with a high level of accuracy, but they present significant limitations in terms of adaptability and scalability. These sensors, in fact, require physical installations that can be invasive and expensive, and often cover only limited portions of the monitored structures.

An alternative (or in some cases complementary) approach to contact techniques is represented using data derived from satellite Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry (InSAR). Thanks to this technology, it is possible to monitor very large areas, identifying the onset of structural damage in infrastructures and buildings. Radar interferometry also allows the analysis of available historical data, tracing the behaviour of structures prior to the onset of damage or, in the most severe cases, to collapse. Recently, the Differential SAR Interferometry (DInSAR) technique has been developed, which allows for mapping the observed scenes with centimetres or even millimetres resolution and extremely reduced revisit times. This technological advancement significantly improves the detection capability and measurement precision.

The present work aims to highlight the versatility and potential of satellite monitoring techniques for the assessment and monitoring of the health of critical infrastructures. This will be done through the application of these techniques to two distinct case studies, each with specific objectives. In particular, the first case study concerns the Schottwien Viaduct on the S6 Semmering highway in Lower Austria, which, with its 632 meters length, is one of the longest pre-stressed concrete beam bridges in Austria. Satellite data are integrated with environmental data to understand how this influences the behaviour of the structure. The results of satellite

monitoring are compared with those provided by an in-situ monitoring system to demonstrate consistency in terms of results. The data used in the analysis of this first case study come exclusively from the European Ground Motion Service (EGMS) databases, developed by the European Space Agency as part of the Copernicus Program, which uses the Sentinel-1 satellite constellation for data collection.

The second case study concerns about a bridge over the Po River located near the municipality of San Benedetto Po, in Lombardy. The bridge is formed of 10 spans, with a total length of about 600 meters, eight of these spans have a length of 67 meters and the two terminal spans have a length of 37.5 meters. In this case, interferometric data are used to study the correlation between environmental factors, primarily the hydrometric level of the Po River, which flows a few meters below the road deck, and the displacements of the bridge structure, which has been closed to traffic since early 2024 and is scheduled for demolition. These data are also used to study the correlation between the displacements of the bridge and the temperature. The results provided by EGMS data can be supplemented by those from the high-resolution datasets provided by the COSMO-SkyMed constellation, developed by the Italian Space Agency (ASI). The results from the two datasets are then compared to highlight any environmental factor interferences with the measurements taken to once again assess the reliability and consistency of satellite measurements.

Through these studies, the present work aims to demonstrate the effectiveness of satellite monitoring techniques in providing precise and reliable data, which can be integrated with other forms of monitoring to obtain a comprehensive and accurate view of the health status of infrastructures. The ability of these technologies to offer scalable and adaptable solutions represents a significant advantage, contributing to the improved management and maintenance of critical structures worldwide. The results obtained underscore the importance of adopting an integrated approach that combines various monitoring techniques for more effective and sustainable infrastructure management.

Keywords: monitoring, concrete bridge, InSAR.

Sand boil phenomena in large river embankments

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River embankments resting on sandy soil layers are susceptible to an internal erosion mechanism known as backward erosion piping (BEP). In particular, if the pervious sandy layer is unconfined, BEP can occur at the landside toe of the embankment at an unfiltered exit area forming a wetland. Alternatively, when a cohesive roof (or “blanket”) layer overlays the sandy foundation soil, BEP may develop at a distance from the embankment in a localized spot. In this case, under the influence of seepage forces, during medium-high water events, starting from the exit hole, shallow erosion pipes begin to form at the interface between the cohesive top cover and the underlying pervious sand layer. As sand particles are carried by the flow to the unfiltered exit, they accumulate and settle outside this point, creating a characteristic feature known as “sand volcano” and technically termed “sand boil”. Eventually, erosion pipes may progress to reach the source of the hydraulic load, enlarge the erosion pipes and thus increasing the risk of the embankment potential collapse.

Backward erosion piping (BEP) is a common issue along major lowland rivers worldwide and in the Po plain over one hundred sand boils are known to periodically reactivate during medium-high water events, providing a significant risk to the stability of embankments. The widespread occurrence of BEP phenomena requires vigilant monitoring and novel mitigation measures to be implemented in order to reduce the related risk. Addressing BEP is crucial for ensuring the long-term stability and safety of flood control earthen infrastructures along waterways.

Any intervention aiming at mitigating such embankment vulnerability requires an initial in-depth understanding of the seepage processes occurring within the permeable layers of the embankment foundation soil and, in particular, in proximity and within the exit vertical pipe. In this regard, the accurate simulation of the water dynamics within the soil layers involved in BEP is crucial and relies on the precise calibration of significant model parameters, which can only be achieved through extensive data collection. These pieces of information may come from a combination of standard laboratory and in-situ tests, together with a properly installed monitoring system and field data on past sand boil reactivations.

The applied methodology for parameter calibration ensures the development of a reliable model of the underlying processes, which is essential for designing effective mitigation strategies. Different mitigation measures have been tested, from traditional, as the partial cut-off trench, to innovative, as the coarse sand barrier. Various lengths and positions of these barriers, along with different hydraulic properties of their materials, are compared to evaluate their effectiveness in reducing vulnerability. The comparison has been performed through the elaboration of fragility curves for each proposed solution, expressing the probability of BEP activation or reactivation as a function of the hydraulic load increase. The results thus obtained are then compared to data on historical sand boil activations or reactivations. This

comprehensive analysis enables a detailed assessment of each mitigation measure performance, providing valuable insights into the most effective strategies for minimizing BEP risk and ensuring the long-term stability of embankment structures.

Keywords: sand boil, backward erosion piping, mitigation intervention.

Source detection into the sewer system by Eulerian and Lagrangian sensors

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In recent decades, due to increased urban industrialisation and the identification of many contaminants of emerging concern for environmental preservation, the urban drainage systems are under the spotlight as a potential path for contamination of receiving water bodies, generating an environmental problem. Also, urban demographic growth, which has notably increased in many areas of the world, has played an important role. For this reason, the prevention and rapid interception of contamination sources through continuous monitoring using water quality sensors has become crucial. Contaminants may also have a relevant impact on asset durability in the presence of high salinity, acidity or basicity.

This study utilizes Lagrangian sensors to monitor water quality in part of the urban catchment of Mondello in Palermo, Italy, focusing on the interception of brackish water infiltrations. The results from the use of moving (Lagrangian) sensors alone were compared with those from the combined use of these sensors and fixed (Eulerian) monitoring stations. Lagrangian sensors, also known as drifters or floaters, passively move with the water's velocity and are equipped with multiple sensing modes, including temperature, pH, salinity, and turbidity. An essential component of these sensors is the localization hardware, typically GPS for natural water bodies, though radio-based technologies are used underground. For saline infiltration interception, electrical conductivity and temperature were the primary parameters analyzed.

Electrical conductivity (EC) measures a solution's ability to conduct electric current, increasing with the concentration of dissociated salts, thus serving as an indicator of salt content. This parameter is measured with a conductivity meter, enabling straightforward tracking of water's salt content. The study area, part of Mondello's urban catchment, features a combined sewer system with HDPE pipes (Manning's roughness coefficient of $0.0125 \text{ s/m}^{1/3}$) and spans 2.7 km^2 , consisting of 112 pipes, 112 junctions, and a sewer outfall. The positioning of the fixed (Eulerian) monitoring stations was optimized using a mathematical model (Sambito and Freni, 2021) to rapidly intercept contamination sources and reduce the number of sensors and associated costs.

Initially, the fixed station monitoring points were determined using the mathematical model, identifying 19 monitoring points and excluding approximately 70% of the investigation area. Subsequently, mobile sensors were employed one at a time, and the results were analyzed. The investigations identified sewer sections with the highest EC values, pinpointing two sewer stretches (totaling 500 m) as potential sources of brackish water, confirmed by visual inspections.

The analysis of individual sensor results revealed that Lagrangian sensors alone tended to return lower EC values due to their inability to quickly detect conductivity changes while in motion, a phenomenon more pronounced in sections with steeper slopes and higher water

velocities. However, combining data from Lagrangian sensors with fixed stations enabled the identification of contamination sources and the affected lengths. While Eulerian sensors offer more precise readings, their fixed positions limit their detection range, necessitating numerous stations for comprehensive monitoring, which is impractical. Therefore, the combined use of Lagrangian and Eulerian sensors proves advantageous for tracing contamination origins and extents.

The study's findings demonstrate that moving sensors can effectively complement fixed monitoring stations. For tracing contamination origins and extents, their combined use is essential, though they cannot entirely replace fixed stations. Depending on the chosen monitoring strategy, different performance levels in rapid contamination interception can be achieved with minimal cost and time expenditure. The common challenge with mobile sensors is their provision of asynchronous data across various time and space points. Future studies will focus on addressing this issue to enhance monitoring efficacy.

Keywords: sewage pollution; water quality sensor; Eulerian and Lagrangian sensors.

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The modernization of the railway infrastructure planning process and the integration of the study of vulnerability related to climate change

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Climate impacts generated by increasingly extreme temperatures, flooding and sea level rise affect rail transport networks more frequently, causing impacts on both operation (Ortega et al.2020) and maintenance (Kasraei et al.,2024). This highlights the need to pay more attention to the concept of vulnerability and risk from the planning of such infrastructures, i.e. feasibility studies. In terms of transport supply, more attention must therefore be paid to the monitoring of geometric and functional conditions and their state of degradation must be taken into greater consideration in order to ensure greater safety and quality of travel. In terms of transport demand and its continuous growth, attention must be paid to factors external to the transport system that influence its vulnerability. These studies must be approached from the perspective of weather conditions and natural disasters, paying particular attention to the consequences of disruptions to the railway system that can become unsustainable and create a significant impact on society and economies. This research work starts from the study conducted on these issues from 2008 to 2019 (Bešinović,2020), expanding the time spectrum to 2023, confirming the comprehensive definition of resilience that incorporates aspects of vulnerability, survival, response, recovery, mitigation and readiness. By comparing the works, five different aspects related to the concept of vulnerability emerge, namely

- physical vulnerability, i.e. the susceptibility of a transport infrastructure subjected to a disaster event of estimated intensity to suffer structural damage that locally compromises its functionality. It depends on the interaction between the type, magnitude and duration of an event and the physical and structural characteristics of critical elements of the railway network, such as bridges, viaducts and tunnels (Hong et al., 2019);

- functional vulnerability, which expresses the susceptibility of a railway element to suffer limitations in its functionality as a result of physical damage or external events that do not damage it (physically) but reduce or cancel its efficiency. It therefore depends on the local functional characteristics of the infrastructure, such as line capacity, speed, number of tracks, type of traffic regulation, etc.

- organisational vulnerability, which considers possible procedural or technological flaws in rescue and emergency management operations. The organisational component of vulnerability can be estimated by studying the interactions that occur between the characteristics of an event, the behaviour of the users involved and the actions carried out by the rescuers, security and information systems contained in an emergency plan (Rosness, 2017);

- topological vulnerability related to the configuration of a transport network and independent of the critical events it is subject to and the traffic circulating through it (Pagani et al., 2019);

- systemic vulnerability identifies the global effects that manifest themselves on an entire transport network following the occurrence of a major event that reduces the functionality of some of its infrastructural elements and may compromise the activities, economic and otherwise, that take place on the area itself. Systemic vulnerability depends mainly on the topological vulnerability and the evolution undergone by the traffic flows on the network, while it is independent of the type and intensity of the events and therefore of the different levels of functional vulnerability (Pitilakis et al., 2016). In particular, it is possible to classify resilience approaches by taking into account data-based, topological, simulation and optimisation aspects. Several papers point out that mathematical optimisation tends to be more suitable for determining, for example, the most critical combinations of critical linkages and optimal response/recovery strategies, due to its ability to handle the greater combinatorial complexity of resilience challenges.

Furthermore, topological and simulation approaches could be used for rapid assessments of certain outage scenarios, which usually include single failures. Simulations can provide in-depth information on system behaviour, but may be too time-consuming.

It is therefore essential to

- put more emphasis on operational changes that can be made in the short term and with limited cost, such as analysing traffic adjustments to respond to and recover quickly and effectively from single and multiple outages.

- analysing case studies and generally designing rail operations that are increasingly flexible and adaptable to possible future disruptions

- pay more attention to methods of improving rail infrastructure networks by moving towards the development of multidisciplinary forecast models.

Therefore, given the risks that climate change imposes on rail transport, it is increasingly necessary to ensure the adaptation of railways along with modernisation.

The general objectives of railway modernisation projects should therefore

- increase the quality and competitiveness of rail transport

- improve the benefits of this mode of transport in economic terms and in terms of overall travel on a national and international scale

- contribute to environmental protection by developing an environmentally friendly transport solution, replacing other modes of transport

- meet the challenges of climate change throughout the infrastructure's lifetime by considering aspects of vulnerability and risk.

Keywords: railway infrastructure vulnerability, feasibility study, climate changes.

The TERIMAAS framework to bridge scales in Multi-Hazard Assessment

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In the modern era, the Digital Twin Khallaf et al. (2022) paradigm has disrupted the idea of representing the world through simplified models that describe its behaviour. Innovative digital technologies and rapid advances in telecommunications and information technology have led humans to want to achieve ever more accurate and detailed descriptions of the built environment. The volume of information to be achieved and managed in the perspective of obtaining a representative twin model of the territory configures data collection and visualisation activities in a crucial, unprecedented way. In the context of investigating the resilience of critical infrastructure with a focus on multi-hazard assessment, the dimensions to be managed and monitored necessarily require the involvement of Big Data and interoperable platforms integrated with information systems referring to the building and spatial scale, to ensure fruitful collaboration among the stakeholders involved. The outlined complexity must recognise the need to intelligently converge highly heterogeneous data sources such as type, format, discipline, and granularity.

The Spoke TS2 of the RETURN project also reflects on this need to evaluate integrated platforms that can facilitate the cognitive and educational activities of the asset management workforce.

The idea of the TErritorial Risk Management & Analysis Across Scale (TERIMAAS) open platform Muhammad et al. (2024) is to promote the integrated management of data through a relational database management system. Specifically, monitoring and analysing territorial resilience requires (i) time-scale information referring to environmental parameters, (ii) geographic spatial knowledge, and (iii) specific information relating to point artefacts and distributed infrastructure. IoT, GIS, and BIM systems constitute the primary databases that implement the central storage unit. Dynamic data updates the database by enabling scenario processing by calculating indicators. Once the data is processed, it can be exposed through dashboards and specific visualisation platforms. Within this scope, the most relevant novelty lies in integrating BIM data within a Postgres PostgreSQL (2024) database and, consequently, their use to increase the level of detail of the analyses, which can thus move from a spatial to a more local scale. GIS spatial analysis assesses risk scores for each hazard type Ugliotti et al. (2023), providing insights into vulnerability and potential impacts. BIM data further refines this assessment by incorporating structural and functional characteristics, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of resilience and risk mitigation strategies tailored to dynamic environmental conditions across scales.

The methodology above is tested through an illustrative use case concerning flood impact assessment on a school complex to clarify the practical application. From the dynamic

rainfall dataset Free Open-Source Weather API (2024), the precipitation height has been derived and related to the construction BIM data, allowing the identification of all model elements affected by the phenomenon to assess potential damage. The focus is not only on the envelope and structural building components but also on the interior environments. About potential flooding, it will be possible to identify in detail the functions and assets affected, for example, sensitive rooms such as archives and libraries or IT equipment such as servers often located in basements. After obtaining the results of the calculations, there was the need to represent them graphically so that any potential stakeholder could easily and immediately understand. As a first test of representation of the results carried out, the BIM Authoring software used for the modelling was tested as a viewer thanks to the communication possibilities with the Dynamo visual programming language platform. Through a combination of functional categorization of spaces and a view filter applied to the visualization of building components, it was possible to represent a selection of flood risk scenarios in which, based on the intended use of each space and the type and height of the related components of the envelope, the model is themed to immediately and directly show the risk to which the various parts of the building are subject.

This example provides only a cue related to possible queries of the centralised database in multi-risk management, where the different types of risk can be understood as system modules, further reinforcing the robustness of the proposed framework. The results of the proposed scalable approach could provide a valuable understanding of the territory for policymakers, urban planners, and any stakeholder involved in disaster risk management and infrastructure resilience planning.

Keywords: Digital Twin, Relational Database Management System, TERIMAAS

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Towards an Italian flood data repository: a natural language processing technique application on literature and social media

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Floods are among the most destructive natural disasters, frequently causing extensive damage and significant losses worldwide. Italy, with its varied terrain and numerous rivers, is particularly susceptible to severe flooding. In the recent years, regions like Veneto, Emilia-Romagna, and Tuscany, have been severely impacted by floods, leading to considerable economic damage and major disruptions to daily life. In our research on flood susceptibility and risk assessment, we recognized the importance of an exhaustive historical flood data repository. Italy already possesses a significant amount of flood data from regional governments and the Copernicus Emergency Management Service. However, to further enhance our flood data repository, we sought to incorporate additional information from various sources, including social media and existing literature. We employed web scraping and natural language processing (NLP) to collect relevant data from online sources. Initially, we conducted web scraping on academic databases such as Google Scholar and ScienceDirect using the keywords "Italy" and "Flood," resulting in around 6,000 scholarly articles. To refine our dataset, we used a dictionary-based search that included the names of river basins and cities in Italy, helping us to map the distribution and frequency of well-documented flood events. In addition to academic literature, we explored the potential of geotagged data from social media and news platforms. Geotagged posts offer real-time information on flood-affected areas, providing valuable insights into the spatial and temporal dynamics of flooding. By integrating these diverse data sources, our goal is to enhance the existing flood database, making it more comprehensive and current. This enriched flood data repository will serve as a vital tool for researchers, policymakers, and emergency response teams. It will facilitate more accurate flood risk assessments, improve the effectiveness of early warning systems, and support the development of targeted flood mitigation strategies. Ultimately, our work aims to contribute to improved flood management practices, reducing the impact of future flood events in Italy and beyond.

Keywords: railway infrastructure vulnerability, feasibility study, climate changes.

Updating risk assessment for hydraulic infrastructures: evaluating the impact of extreme rainfall events in Italy

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Extreme rainfall events cause tragic loss of human lives and substantial economic damage worldwide every year. Risk reduction strategies typically involve structural measures designed to protect people and areas from events with a fixed annual exceedance probability, often expressed in terms of return. Despite the heavy reliance on these mitigation strategies, the possibility of overload events, i.e. those exceeding the design values of the structures, persists throughout their design life. Such events are linked to the probability of failure, also known as residual risk. In this study we introduce a systematic procedure to continuously revise the design variables over the design life of hydraulic structure or infrastructure (Moccia et al., 2024).

At the design time, only historical data are available to define the quantile value for design purposes. However, new observations can be collected post-construction and during structure's operational life. We assume a 30-year observation period to estimate the quantile to design hydraulic protection structures, aligning with standard practices in time series statistical analysis. After selecting the optimal probability distribution function and evaluating its parameters (Moccia et al., 2021), the design variable for a fixed return period can be determined, setting the design life of the structure and deriving the probability of failure. Post-construction, new data can be integrated into the original sample to enhance its robustness, enabling the definition of an updated probability of failure.

We applied the methodology to daily rainfall observations from the National System for the Collection, Elaboration and Diffusion of Climatological Data (SCIA, Desiato et al., 2007), recorded by 2282 rain gauges in Italy between 1860 and 2022. This methodology is also applicable to other hydrological variables (such as peak flows) and different time scales (including sub-daily).

Results indicate that for 64% of the analyzed samples, there is a tendency for the updated probability of failure to be higher than the initially expected. Such increase is associated to a reduction in the return period of the design variable, suggesting that the design event is more likely to occur, with potentially severe consequences for people and areas at risk.

To better understand the probability of failure concept, we also analyze extreme rainfall events exceeding estimated rainfall quantiles for six different return periods over the recording years. Using the entire sample length to determine the quantiles, we counted the number of events and the recording stations involved. Significant findings include the years 1951 and 1966, which had the highest overload cases, causing severe floods and landslides, resulting in hundreds of deaths and significant economic damage. In the most recent decade, despite fewer

active stations, three millennial events occurred in 2013, 2015, and 2022, particularly affecting the Marche region with multiple landslides and riverine floods. From 1920 onwards, overload cases showed a consistent pattern with higher intermittency for longer return periods. This analysis highlights the occurrence of multiple exceedances at several locations, emphasizing the need for continuous risk assessment and updating of hydraulic infrastructure design variables.

This proactive approach allows us to assess the likelihood of rare yet possible events, enhancing our understanding of the potential vulnerabilities of existing hydraulic infrastructures. By employing this approach, local, regional, and national managers can quantify and update the risk levels associated with hydraulic structures and infrastructures. This enables decision-makers to develop investment plans for necessary extraordinary maintenance and establish risk-based priorities for interventions. Additionally, the creation of dynamic risk maps aids in monitoring critical areas across the territory. Thus, it is crucial for decision-makers and authorities to invest significantly in hydraulic risk protection, combining structural and non-structural measures to effectively reduce flood risk. Engaging citizens in preparedness and responsiveness can foster a resilient environment and minimize losses (Ridolfi et al., 2021).

Keywords: flood data repository, web scraping, natural language processing.

WWTPs mapping using a multi-hazard, multi-scale approach

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Climate change induces complex variations in climate characteristics on different spatial and temporal scales by influencing the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events such as heavy rains, droughts, and heat waves. In addition, climate change is considered to accelerate coastal erosion processes due to sea level rise (IPCC, 2023). In order to estimate the effects of climate change on population, it is certainly important to identify areas and related infrastructure that may be damaged by these events (Masud & Khan, 2024). In this framework, critical infrastructures such as Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTPs) are a central element of the analysis because any damage to these could adversely affect human health and the environment.

The European Commission issued Directive 2022/2557 on the resilience of critical infrastructures. Each member states are required to identify and assess risks related to the such infrastructures due to natural and anthropogenic hazards.

In this regard, the research question was: can WWTPs be characterized at different scales through a multi-hazard approach to identify vulnerability signals relevant to their surrounding territories? For this reason, the aim of this research was to systematically characterize WWTPs from a multi-hazard approach.

Firstly, considering the high number of WWTPs on a national scale (17897) (data referred to 2015 from ISTAT), it was decided to carry out the study on a regional scale. Space-dependent analyses were developed using data provided by Sicilian region and authorities of integrated water services and developed on geographical information systems (GIS). From the provided information, the WWTPs were represented as point infrastructures, distinguishing between existing, abandoned and expected.

Secondly, the natural hazards in the area of interest (hydraulic, geomorphological, seismic and coastal) were identified. These were cross-referenced to assess the most vulnerable installations to the natural phenomena analysed.

Third, a multi-hazard GIS-based tool was applied at the municipal scale with a focus on the wastewater treatment plants. The aim was to characterize vulnerability scenarios considering the bidirectional interaction between industry and territory (Castro Rodriguez et al., 2023). In particular, the municipality of Cefalù was considered as a case study. For each natural hazard an indicator (0-1) was defined. Following, these indicators were aggregated into an index by assuming an equal weight for each of them. Finally, a multi-hazard map was created. This mapping was carried out at the municipal level, focusing on the two existing wastewater treatment plants "Presidiana S. Antonio Treatment Plant" and "Sant'Ambrogio Treatment Plant".

The tool contributes to increasing awareness of territorial vulnerability based on spatial analysis, making it possible to analyse the combined effect of different hazards according to a

holistic approach. The analysis conducted in the municipality of Cefalù made it possible to determine the multi-hazard index for the two plants in the area, where it was found that the territory in which they are located is characterised by a high level of hazard. The study will be extended to all the municipalities in the province of Palermo and subsequently to Sicily.

These topics are investigated within the RETURN project. Specifically, within the Spoke TS2-Multi Risk Resilience of Critical Infrastructures. WP 3 - Dynamic mapping of natural and climatic hazards over the infrastructure systems. T 3.2 – Robust hazard mapping over point critical infrastructures. Sub Task 3.2.2. Natural Hazards classification maps of point-like infrastructures of national relevance.

Keywords: multi-hazard, climate change, wastewater treatment plants.

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TS3 ‘Communities’ resilience to risk: social, economic, legal and cultural dimensions’

**Co-design processes towards new approaches in integrated
planning for DRR and CCA policies: methods, tools, and
responses in the different phases of risk**

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The paper presents considerations emerged from the seminar entitled “Conoscere per prevenire. Approcci, metodi e strumenti partecipativi per comunità resilienti al rischio” held on the 4th and 5th June 2024 at Politecnico di Milano. In the framework of the topics discussed, the debate among experts and representatives of both scientific and local communities revealed aspects and issues that will become essential in developing the participation process and the guidelines in compliance with the objectives of Work Package 4 “Community-Based (CB) approaches, codesign and policies”, Task 7.4.4 “New approach in integrated planning based on co-design processes for DRR e CCA policies”.

The discussion around the different temporalities of risk paid attention to the effectiveness of ex-ante approaches in multidisciplinary planning involved in disaster management, mitigation, and prevention.

The importance of ex-ante preparation is evident to achieve anti-fragile territorial conditions: these can be pursued through community preparedness, which implies risk education and awareness creation in the practices of transformation, care, and management of built heritage, open spaces, and landscapes. The multidisciplinary debate addressed those territorial fragilities induced by conditions of risk and uncertainty, which might be accelerated by climate change and environmental crises. Uncertainty is a peculiar aspect of risk preparedness, especially considering that climate change might render existing knowledge, its consequent predictions, and measures to be taken ineffective.

Preparing for the unexpected requires knowledge of a community and its dynamics and trust in science and institutions: it is necessary to become aware not only of risks, but also of the possibility that risks can occur in unforeseen forms, intensities, and frequencies. The outcomes of the discussion suggest combining large systematic interventions with a bottom-up approach. Such method should intertwine ordinary and scientific knowledge within a form of participation that can look critically at the role of communities in the processes of transformation, care, and management of places.

Ex-post interventions such as the Reconstruction Plans (Piani di Ricostruzione) of municipalities affected by earthquakes in central Italy combined the needs of reconstruction with those of prevention, including cross-actions for seismic risk mitigation in the system of paths and safe spaces. Such actions include the identification of suitable pathways for escape routes; another measure is ensuring the safety of facades to preserve the usability of paths in case of evacuation. Concerning ex-ante interventions, the adoption of Multi- Criteria Analysis (MCA) is peculiar to support decision-makers in a multi-risk environment. MCA considers social, economic, and environmental aspects and systematizes impacts that a disaster may cause on different exposed categories with different intervention strategies. These factors incorporate weights assigned through a value judgment, to deal with the uncertainty intrinsic in forecasting decisions and the management of subjectivity.

The sharing of some experiences of co-design allowed the identification of participatory processes aimed also at the care and management of the tangible and intangible heritage of communities in fragile contexts, promoting a paradigm shift from the identification of needs to the formulation of common goals. While the responsibility of institutions requires awareness-

raising processes, bringing citizens closer together must be mediated by sharing data, sources and by defining a common language: the translation of technical knowledge and plans could lead to a collective participation that can be understood as a tool to improve risk awareness and emergency management. Co-design finds fertile ground in different fields of investigation and application, responding to the territorial fragilities through risk mitigation and preparedness. This is especially evident in rural contexts, where resident communities are often in conditions of fragility, marginalization, and aging. This also implies the need for integration and coordination among planning tools and policies, including reflections on inclusiveness in emergency responses.

The research process aims to define a co-design path that can systematize scientific and local knowledge, to develop actions that are effective and shared with communities facing challenges posed by transformations.

To achieve such objectives, the investigation adopts an ethnographic approach that complements the on-desk analysis based on the review of scientific and grey literature, and the systematization of data, information and documents retrieved from archives and open-access repositories. In the first phase of the investigation, the ethnographic research included on field surveys in the municipalities assumed as pilot cases, and semi-structured interviews with members of the communities identified, such as local administrators. The preliminary outcomes of such analysis resulted in the individuation of both critical aspects, opportunities and resources when dealing with hazards and climate change within the contexts and communities investigated, which will become the basis to develop the next steps of the co-design process that will delineate the guidelines tool.

In the knowledge that disaster risks and climate change pose scenarios characterized by uncertainty, it will be necessary to adapt the actions foreseen within the co-design process on a place-based perspective, and on the needs and requirements of communities, through a people-based approach.

Keywords: preparedness, bottom-up approaches, co-design.

Group-Decision Methods for Real-Life Experts

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In my poster at the plenary meeting in Turin in February 2024, I focused on strengthening the ethics of group decision-making by improving methods for aggregating experts' opinions to avoid

the risk of manipulations of aggregated opinions. However, my results required an idealised assumption that real-life experts will violate. My current research (which I want to present at the plenary session in Bari) focuses on relaxing that idealised assumption and so making my result applicable to group decisions of real-life experts.

Let me briefly recapitulate my results presented in February to give context to my current research and presentation for Bari. I have shown that aggregating odds (i.e., not directly probabilities) with two weighted geometric means (that I call f_n and f_m) prevents any rank reversals and is less controversial than aggregating experts' pReferences: in the form of ratios. Aggregating with f_n and f_m prevents any manipulations of experts' aggregated opinions via purposefully adding or deleting alternatives from the agenda (a set of alternatives under consideration). I also showed that aggregating with f_n and f_m satisfies many desirable properties, such as being able to assign different weights of importance to different experts, non-existence of a dictatorial decider, or a version of the independence condition meaningful for odds (an aggregated opinion about comparing alternatives A and B depends only on how A and B compare with respect to each other and not on how either compares to any other option in the agenda). However, my results required an idealised assumption about the consistency of experts' opinions that real-life experts will violate. For opinions expressed in the form of odds, it means that they meet the multiplication law for odds: if any two of the three odds $od(B : C)$, $od(C : D)$, and $od(B : D)$ exist, then so also does the third, and $od(B : D) = od(B : C)od(C : D)$. It is well-known Brunelli (2018) that real-life experts' pReferences: (in the form of ratio judgements) violate an equivalent consistency assumption for pReferences: and there is no reason to believe that epistemic ratio judgements in the form of odds will satisfy the multiplication law. This begs the question of whether we want to allow some minor inconsistencies and if so what is the acceptable limit and associated risks.

My current research and presentation for Bari aim to suggest axioms that determine a set of good inconsistency measures. So, we can use those measures to decide which inconsistency of opinions is tolerable (and analyse its risks) and which are intolerable so that experts' opinions should be revised and aggregated again. To do so, I modify, extend, and combine recent results in epistemology and multi-criteria decision theory.

First, epistemologists Staffel (2019) have recently discussed desirable properties of inconsistency measures (especially in the form of scoring rules from statistical decision theory) but only for probabilities and mostly without giving a proper mathematical representation of those properties. So, the first goal is to carefully formalise those properties and see how they fit with opinions expressed in the form of odds. Secondly, axiomatising inconsistency measures of preferential ratio judgements is a current discussion in multi-criteria decision theory Csató (2018). So, my second goal is to modify these axioms for the epistemic context of opinions (beliefs) expressed in the form of odds. This again requires modifications and extensions since those axioms are primarily meant for pReferences:.

Some decision-theoretic axioms can be easily interpreted for epistemic cases. For example in Brunelli (2017), continuity of inconsistency measures prevents any jumps in inconsistency scores, lower bound requirement says that consistency should get 0 from inconsistency measures, or that permuting alternatives does not change the inconsistency score. Other preferential axioms pose a bigger challenge to translate into epistemic context. For example, how inconsistency measures should behave under intensifying one's pReferences:.. It is not obvious how "intensification" translates into epistemic context and how inconsistency

measures should react to learning new evidence that may intensify one's beliefs. Finally, the third goal is to combine the adapted results from epistemology and decision theory to determine a set of appropriate inconsistency measures for odds that can be applied to my previous results to improve the group decision-making of real-life experts.

Keywords: group decisions, inconsistent beliefs, inconsistency measures.

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Multi Risk assessment and role of Cultural Heritage on resilience

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Cultural Heritage (CH) is often affected by natural hazards, e.g., floods, earthquakes, ground instabilities etc. CH is a hotspot of natural hazard impacts, on one hand for the direct tangible impacts, i.e., costs for restoration and recovery, on the other hand, for intangible impacts. Particularly intangible impacts have been often overlooked by researchers. The deal with social and communal values, aesthetic, spiritual, historical values which are rarely estimated in risk analyses. In the Work Package 7.3 the research groups of CIMA Foundation, EURAC and UNIFI have completed four specific literature reviews aimed at (i) understanding the connection between CH and resilience to natural hazards, (ii) understanding methods for valuing CH, (iii) revealing the role of the scale of multi-risk analysis and mapping for CH, (iv) identifying existing and innovative methods for monitoring systems specifically tailored for CH. The findings of the research groups highlight the utmost importance of CH in shaping community resilience in the aftermath of a disastrous event, not limited to tangible CH, i.e., buildings, sites or artefacts, but also in terms of traditions and local knowledge. Such a role justifies a specific interest in including CH in multi-risk mapping with several limitations at certain scale of analysis especially due to a limited availability of geospatial data with the necessary information for risk prioritization and assessment. Moreover, monitoring systems for CH can go beyond the classic measurements of physical hazard quantities, e.g., ground motion, precipitation, moving towards a dynamic quantification of exposure and vulnerabilities to specific natural hazards.

Keywords: multi-risk, resilience, monitoring.

The road to adaptation action: a study of community perception in Ischia

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This presentation merges two complementary studies by WP5-TS3 focusing on adaptation actions. The first study is a reasoned review of the dynamics of trust in decision-making processes for climate adaptation. The second is an empirical study conducted in Ischia, Italy, to identify variables relevant to citizens for adopting flood and landslide adaptation actions.

Understanding Resilience and Trust

Resilience is defined as the ability to adapt to challenging life experiences through mental, emotional, and behavioral flexibility (American Psychological Association, 2023). Individual resilience depends on environmental interactions, social support systems, and coping mechanisms. Community resilience, emerging alongside individual resilience, involves active, coordinated interactions among community members and is influenced by demographic, historical, jurisdictional, and economic factors (Ellis et al., 2022). Key components of community resilience include decision-making capabilities, adaptability, collaboration, and trust in reliable information sources (Pfefferbaum et al., 2013).

In psychological sciences, trust is defined as confidence in the reliability of someone or something (American Psychological Association, 2023). Trust involves a psychological state of accepting vulnerability based on positive expectations of another's behavior (Rousseau et al., 1998). McAllister (1995) emphasizes that trust is built on cognitive evaluations of abilities and competence, and emotional bonds within a community.

Trust is fundamental for effective risk communication and disaster management (Marincioni, 2020). It predicts the willingness to cooperate with authorities and adopt preventive measures (Pagliaro et al., 2021). Trust in institutions and government influences individual preparedness for emergencies (Basolo et al., 2009).

Empirical Study in Ischia

The empirical study in Ischia focuses on local perceptions of flood and landslide risks and factors influencing adaptation strategies. Using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) in focus groups, the study aims to:

1. Explore the role of citizens' perceptions in shaping flood and landslide adaptation strategies.
2. Highlight local perceptions of flood and landslide risks.
3. Apply multi-criteria analysis to assess the weights of factors influencing adaptation strategies.

Mitigating natural disasters involves complex decision-making with diverse stakeholders and uncertainties. Effective strategies must integrate qualitative and quantitative parameters. The AHP is a valuable method for structuring decision problems, determining criteria, and weighting them according to stakeholder preferences. It simplifies decision-making by breaking down multidimensional problems into hierarchical structures, allowing decision-makers to prioritize factors methodically.

The study employed five focus groups with 8 to 9 non-expert citizens each, totaling 44 participants. Participants reviewed potential causes of flood and landslide disasters, providing valuable insights into public perceptions. The focus group discussions aimed to explore perceptions, attitudes, and experiences related to floods and landslides, identifying shared understandings and meanings.

The sample consisted of 44 participants from Ischia Porto and Casamicciola Terme, primarily property owners. Despite recognizing the severity of floods and landslides, participants paradoxically perceived these events as rare, influencing their overall risk assessment.

Discussions highlighted moderate perceptions of predictability, emphasizing the need for enhanced communication and community engagement. Participants showed heightened concern for future occurrences, likely influenced by climate change projections and media coverage.

Participants expressed a need for intervention and mitigation measures, indicating an overconfidence bias where they felt secure about their properties but concerned about broader environmental vulnerabilities. Using AHP, the study captured diverse perceptions, revealing that participants prioritized environmental criteria over economic ones, indicating a strong emphasis on resilience and sustainability. Social factors like mortality, information, and trust were also highly valued, underscoring the importance of effective communication and community trust.

Nevertheless, lack of trust in institutional competence and neighbor preparedness is detected.

Regression analysis showed trends like a lower emphasis on evacuation plans among those who felt secure in their homes, aligning with the optimism bias. Enhancing risk awareness and realistic appraisals of control could improve disaster preparedness and mitigation efforts.

The study provides valuable insights into community perceptions and attitudes toward flood and landslide risks in Ischia. By incorporating these findings into decision-making frameworks like AHP, policymakers can better prioritize interventions and allocate resources to enhance community resilience and disaster preparedness. The results highlight the need for a comprehensive approach addressing both physical and socio-psychological dimensions of risk perception, fostering informed decision-making and robust adaptive strategies.

Keywords: adaptation action, trust, community perception, optimism bias.

Toward a multi-criteria analysis tool for evaluating the effectiveness of risk reduction strategies within a multi-risk framework

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The establishment of national guidelines for applying Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) to natural hazard risk management is complex. This is mainly due: i) to the multiple natural hazards that can impact the Italian territory, calling for the adoption of a multi-risk approach (Arrighi et al., 2023); ii) the wide variety of structural and non-structural measures that can be applied in the different phases of risk management chain during which decisions are made (Thiebes and Winkhardt-Enz, 2023); iii) the different dimensions from social, economic, environmental, cultural, to technical, that are involved in a disaster risk reduction analysis. To address the structural complexity of the problem, it is fundamental to break it down into simple, manageable parts, supporting the application of a more detailed analysis for each individual component (sub-problem) at stake. For this reason, the methodological approach has been decomposed into two operational steps. First, the development of a “matrix hazards-impacts” that classifies the exposed elements representing the different dimensions of the problems to the multiple single natural hazards and analyzes the potential direct and indirect impacts in case of an event occurrence based on an extensive literature review. Second, the definition of an “abacus of measures” which identifies the most promising measures that can be applied in a specific context. This contribution presents the results reached so far toward this direction.

The main objective of risk reduction strategies is to reduce the impacts of a natural hazard event on the exposed elements of an affected area. To evaluate the effectiveness of these measures within an MCA approach it is therefore necessary to define a set of attributes, sub-attributes and related indicators that allow an ex-ante assessment (i.e., before the occurrence of an event or during the planning phase of the measure), by comparing the natural hazard impacts with or without the implementation of measures. This is why the development of the matrix hazards-impacts is crucial as first operational step. The matrix consists of seven sub-matrices, each of which refers to one of the different exposed elements classified into individual well-being, built environment, business activities, public services, environmental systems, communities, and financial system. For each exposed element we have identified the expected impacts in case of an event, described through specific attributes and sub-attributes. The analysis focuses on floods, landslides, drought, volcanic activity and earthquakes as the most widespread natural hazards in the Italian context. As a starting point for adopting of a multi-risk framework, common and/or specific attributes have been identified for the different hazards that can co-exist in a certain area (no compound, cascading events, etc. are considered).

The sub-matrices report for each attribute and for each natural hazard the indicator that has been identified, its measurement units and the respective evaluation scale. Moreover, they highlight the model or methodology that can be adopted, the required input data for its evaluation distinguished between hazard, exposure and vulnerability parameters, and the reference sources. The selection of indicators was based on the possibility of an ex-ante estimation, the availability of models and data for its evaluation at national level, and the use of as more quantitative indicators as possible, also through the use of proxy variables; in case this is not possible, one of the MCA advantages is that it also allows the use of qualitative indicators.

The second operational step, that is the development of the abacus of measures, is further divided into two sub-phases. The first sub-phase concerns the characterization of measures in terms of the risk management phase that they are referring to, whether these are

structural or non-structural, the spatial and temporal scale of effectiveness and the associated risk reduction (or even increase). The second sub-phase is related to the characterization of strategies in terms of feasibility, as well as the social and environmental co-benefits and/or dis-benefits (Baills et al., 2020). The main arising challenges concern the identification of alternatives, their classification by function and the identification of synergies or trade-offs between the different risks due to the limited availability in the literature. To deal with the latter, grey literature, field evidence and expert judgement can be also considered.

Finally, the integration of these two ongoing steps will lead to the development of a “performance matrix” that will allow the comparison between risk reduction strategies with respect to their effectiveness, aiming to provide a prioritization or ranking.

Keywords: risk reduction strategies, multi-criteria analysis, multi-hazard risk.

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Unravelling the role of cultural heritage for community resilience to climate- related risks: advancement and operational framework

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Cultural heritage and local knowledge are increasingly recognized as essential resources for enhancing community resilience to future challenges (Tavares, 2021). Their role is particularly relevant in understanding natural hazards risks, addressing them and supporting resilience building and climate change adaptation processes. Their importance is also acknowledged in global policy frameworks and international reports such as the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, the Paris Agreement, and the latest IPCC WG2 report (UNDRR and ICCROM, 2022).

Despite this growing recognition, the means of operationalization of the dynamics between cultural heritage and community resilience to disaster risks are still greatly under researched. This gap represents a limit to increasing community resilience worldwide.

Within the framework of the Extended Partnership (EP) RETURN, our task and the connected activities aim at bridging this gap by presenting an operational framework guiding the inclusion of cultural heritage and local knowledge in risk reduction and community resilience strategies.

In this contribution we will present a framework developed to facilitate resilience assessment acknowledging the risk-resilience-heritage nexus. The framework is based on an extensive literature review analysing the role of cultural heritage within the hazard-risk-resilience nexus. We have identified four key spheres of community resilience in which cultural heritage plays an influencing role. The framework investigates specific dynamics and identifies specific functions through which identified forms of cultural heritage (e.g. traditional and technical knowledge, community traditions, rituals, traditional social supports systems, etc) can play this role in relation to the different community resilience aspects.

Finally, we showcase some possible practical applications of this theoretical framework in real-world contexts, demonstrating how to integrate cultural heritage aspects into the design and implementation of strategies that strengthen community resilience and climate change adaptation.

Keywords: community resilience, cultural heritage, climate-related risks.

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DS ‘Science underpinning climate services for risk mitigation and adaptation’

A 1-km gridded dataset of daily temperature and precipitation observations for the Adige River catchment supporting local impact-oriented assessments

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In the framework of the RETURN Extended Partnership (European Union NextGenerationEU, National Recovery and Resilience Plan – NRRP, Mission 4, Component 2, Investment 1.3 – D.D. 1243 2/8/2022, PE0000005), and specifically in the context of the Diagonal Spoke 8, our activities focus on the Adige River catchment (eastern Italian Alps) and aim at developing a 1 km-scale climatic product based on recent observations for an extended area centered on the basin (~ 40'000 km²).

The considered area encompasses different Italian regions and part of Switzerland and Austria, and diverse socio-economic and environmental zones, from the Alps to the Adriatic Sea, which are also exposed to different climate-related risks. The varied topography and climatic conditions make the Adige River catchment an ideal natural laboratory for studying the interactions between climate drivers and natural and socio-economic factors. The availability of a harmonized and updated cross-border gridded climate dataset for the area, based on a high density of local observations, is still an open issue. Such a product is crucial for analyzing spatial and temporal climate variability in the area, fitting model projections, and obtaining tailored information for decision-making.

The dataset will include daily minimum and maximum temperature and precipitation fields, as essential climatic variables to support impact-oriented analyses in the region, especially related to hydrometeorological extremes and heatwaves. Due to the fragmented nature of the considered area, one of the first challenges to deal with regards the collection and harmonization of station observations from multiple data providers, each of them using different data standards, policies and storages. The collected observation database includes about 700 stations for precipitation and 660 stations for temperature, even though the series do not have the same temporal extent and the data coverage of the area significantly increased in the 1990s. All data undergo harmonization procedures to unify data format and standards, and quality controls to detect outliers and inconsistencies. Once the data preprocessing is complete, different interpolation techniques will be applied and tested to identify the approaches for each variable providing the most accurate and reliable estimates over the area for the period 1990-2023. Attention will be paid to understand the ability of reproducing local-scale features, such as thermal inversions, localized rainfall episodes and accumulated precipitation in mountain areas. The final dataset at 1-km resolution for the extended Adige River catchment is expected to extend and improve the existing dataset developed by the authors for Trentino – South Tyrol region and to enable subsequent assessments for the entire catchment.

The gridded observations will be compared to other climate products, including reanalysis-based datasets at different spatial resolutions, to further evaluate the quality of the new regional dataset. In collaboration with researchers involved in the Vertical Spoke dedicated to water-related topics and the Transversal Spoke to urban settlements, the interpolated variables will be considered in the assessment of climate drivers for local impacts in the area based on past records and modelling activities. The intercomparison and the impact-oriented analyses will highlight advantages and limitations of the product thus supporting a proper evaluation of the accuracy of the impact-oriented indicators identified by the DS Spoke when calculated for the area starting from the new gridded fields.

Keywords: climate observations, gridded dataset, Adige river catchment.

A regionalized framework for the Metastatistical Extreme Value Distribution applied to daily and sub-daily rainfall

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The estimation of extreme rainfall based on short records is of considerable interest, above all in the context of rapidly changing rainfall regimes. Regionalization techniques, by

trading space for time, allow us to partially overcome the lack of observational records. The recently introduced Metastatistical Extreme Value (MEV) distribution, a non-asymptotic extreme-value model, accounting for all observed rainfall events to infer the probability distribution of annual maxima, also contributed towards improving our ability to determine large quantiles based on short observational time series. Here we combine established regionalization techniques, aggregating data from multiple adjacent stations complying with set homogeneity criteria, with MEV-based methodologies to explore how their joint use may further reduce the predictive uncertainty associated with the estimates of the probability of extreme events. In this work, we use precipitation data sets from a selection of worldwide regional station networks, mainly from Europe and North America, deployed in a wide range of elevations and different rainfall regimes. The temporal data resolution varies according to country ranging from sub-daily to daily scales. We analyze different event durations, between 5 minutes and 24 hours for the sub-daily scale, 1 day and 5 days for the daily one, and we implement a cross-validation procedure to evaluate predictive uncertainty. To evaluate possible improvements with respect to regionalization techniques based on traditional extreme value theory, such as the Generalized Extreme Value (GEV) distribution, we comparatively apply them and the proposed MEV-based regionalization approach. The results show the benefits arising from the regionalization technique, which enhances the robustness of the models by increasing the consistency of the observed data population within the stations of the same cluster. The proposed regionalization approach based on the metastatistic distribution brings a significant reduction of the estimation uncertainty for very high ratios between the forecasting return period value and the length of the calibration sample, clearly outperforming traditional approaches.

Keywords: extreme rainfall, regionalization techniques, non-asymptotic methods.

Database of key climatic variables in Mediterranean marine sediments: analyzing paleoclimatic signals from the last 20,000 years

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The Mediterranean Sea is a crucial area for the study of past climate dynamics thank to its unique geography and hydrology. Its relatively small size and rapid response to climate

changes make it an ideal laboratory for deciphering the impact of marginal basins on global climate (Chiggiato et al., 2023). As the quality of historical data and instrumental records fades over time, geological archives and climatic indicators (proxies) become crucial for reconstructing past climates and predicting future scenarios. This is especially important given the current hazards caused by intense human environmental pressures, including rapid anthropogenic carbon emissions, which affect sea water temperature, precipitation rates, nutrient cycling, and that lead to ocean acidification (Bolle, 2003).

Here, we present a comprehensive database derived from more than 1500 marine sediment cores collected in the Mediterranean Sea spanning the last 20,000 years, from the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) to the deglaciation phase and finally to the Holocene (present interglacial). This database provides general information about oceanographic cruises and detailed descriptions of the recovered sediment cores. For each core, proxies of the main past environmental variables are provided from the literature.

The aim of this effort was to identify the most studied climatic variables for reconstructing past climatic conditions over the last 20,000 years and to identify any knowledge gaps in terms of proxies, spatial, and temporal coverage. To achieve these goals, we analyzed over 400 published scientific articles and selected 36 cores from the Mediterranean Sea, including both extensively studied cores and those with potential scientific interest for future research. Our work offers a comprehensive graphic basin-scale synthesis of the main environmental variables available in the Mediterranean Sea over the last 20 kyr and the existing proxies categorized into abiotic (physical or chemical indicators; 76%) and biotic (marine fauna and flora; 24%) proxies.

Our data reveal an uneven distribution of cores, with higher densities in certain regions, particularly in the Eastern Mediterranean and near the Italian coasts of the Adriatic Sea. Planktonic foraminifera, examined in 70% of the total cores, stands out as the most studied biotic proxy, while AMS 14C, carbon and oxygen stable isotopes, and elemental data are the most studied abiotic proxies. Overall, our analysis shows that sea water temperature is the most extensively researched variable, accounting for 26% of the total variables investigated.

Keywords: Mediterranean paleoclimate, marine sediment cores, climatic proxies.

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Evaluation of high resolution hindcast simulations in the Western-Mediterranean area years

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Reliable climate information at regional scale is of primary importance for users and decision makers.

Although global models provide the first source of climate information also for the regional scale, particularly as to the attribution of the forced changes and to the quantification of the role of the internal variability, the dynamical downscaling by means of Regional Climate

Models (RCMs) allows to represent at higher resolutions the complex phenomena that emerge over regions of complex orography or with heterogeneous surface characteristics (Doblas-Reyes et al. 2021), such as the Mediterranean basin and our national territory.

Currently, RCMs allow us to reach horizontal resolutions of the order of 10 km for extended assessments, as documented for European climate projections has been recently published (Coppola et al. 2021)

A relatively recent thread in regional climate modelling consists in pushing model resolution to scales where deep convection can be solved explicitly rather than parameterized. At few kilometers of horizontal resolution (< 4 km) convection parameterization can be switched off. The interest in studying and simulating convection is mostly related to its high relevance in driving extreme events such as heavy precipitation, windstorms and floods. Performances and added value of the climate projections at the so called grey-zone of resolution (between 10km and 5km) has not been yet fully addressed.

Many research questions are still open in Regional Climate science and understanding. One aspect that deserves investigation is to understand the reasons for differences/similarities/contradictions in climatology, variability, and extremes across the different scales represented and among different data sources, and better explain the implications for regional climate information.

Relying on the climate projections produced so far we will investigate in this work the differences and/or similarities of the main climate variables (surface temperature and precipitation) at two different resolutions (15 km and 5 km) and we will compare the results with available observational datasets.

We will start an analysis of the extremes in the present climate simulation of the very high resolution model (5km), in order to further investigate whether there is an added value in the simulations performed within the grey-zone and how they compare with respect to Convection Permitting Simulations.

Keywords: regional climate projections.

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Hazard indicators – A statistical approach for estimating and testing prediction uncertainty

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Estimation of hazard indicators is a key activity of the spoke DS8 of Return. Indicators have been defined through a interspoke consultation, that highlighted their key value for decision making and climate change adaptation planning. The consultation also identified prediction uncertainty for indicators as a key attribute of information to end users. Indeed, supplementing a prediction with an indication of confidence allows us to provide an additional important support to decision making.

The cross-spoke interest in prediction uncertainty led to the composition of an interspoke task force, that is now composed of almost 40 members, who is working to provide a review and classification of uncertainty assessment methods that can be used in the context of RETURN.

Here, we consider the application of Bluecat, a statistical approach for prediction uncertainty assessment that was recently presented by the literature (Koutsoyiannis and Montanari, 2022). It can be applied when observed historical values of indicators are available and the prediction model allows their hindcasting.

Bluecat (Brisk Local Uncertainty Estimator for Deterministic Simulations and Predictions) is a method to transform a deterministic prediction model into a stochastic prediction model, therefore turning from a point prediction to the probability distribution of the true value of predictand. From the latter distribution, a mean (or median) prediction is obtained along with the confidence bands. Therefore Bluecat performs two tasks: (a) it updates the deterministic prediction, therefore providing a new point prediction; (b) it provides confidence limits for the prediction for an assigned confidence level.

Bluecat can be applied in conjunction with any deterministic prediction model. The information that is needed to perform the above transformation is obtained in Bluecat by building on the well established concept of comparing the output of a deterministic model with observed data; namely, the same concept that we commonly use for parameter estimation. Basing on such comparison, Bluecat estimates the probability distribution of observed data. Note that the stochastic prediction may be markedly different from the deterministic one. In fact, the latter is not necessarily included into the confidence bands of the stochastic predictions, which are displaced around the mean stochastic prediction.

Being based on the comparison between the deterministic model output and observations, the concept of Bluecat is therefore transparent and easily understandable, while the theoretical development ensures that such interpretation of uncertainty is rigorous and asymptotically consistent in estimating global uncertainty of the prediction.

Keywords: floods, droughts, uncertainty.

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Hazard indicators for marine ecosystems

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Biogeochemical indicators allow to monitor the status and assess hazards and trends in important marine ecosystem processes such as primary production, nutrient cycling, carbon budget, acidification, oxygen depletion and eutrophication. For example, the EU's Copernicus Marine Service (CMS) has developed Ocean Monitoring Indicators (OMIs), which are defined as trend and variability indices for key marine variables and are computed for the global ocean and European seas (<https://marine.copernicus.eu/access-data/ocean-monitoring-indicators>).

As part of the Return Spoke DS within WP2 and WP3, we provide data and calculate indicators for the Marine Ecosystem and Coastal zones impact sectors, and analyse the associated uncertainties in WP5. This activity is done in synergy with WP3 in the VS Spoke 4. The selected indicators are physical, such as temperature, salinity, and biogeochemical, such as dissolved oxygen, dissolved inorganic carbon, pH and trophic index (TRIX, Vollenweider et al. 1998). The northern Adriatic Sea is the proof-of-concept area.

In particular, the indicators within Spoke 8 WP2 “State of the art and knowledge base to define impact-oriented hazard indicators” are derived from three datasets: the CMS reanalysis (period 1999-2023, horizontal resolution of ~4 km, 100 vertical levels; Teruzzi et al., 2021), a high-resolution implementation of the MITgcm-BFM for the northern Adriatic Sea (period 2006-2017, horizontal resolution of ~750 m, 27 vertical levels; Cossarini et al., 2017) and a Mediterranean-scale climate simulation (period 2005-2100, horizontal resolution of ~6 km, 72 vertical levels; Reale et al., 2022).

The available modelling data for the proof-of-concept domain were used as learning source for a neural network. This network-based model is used for downscaling the 3D fields of physical and biogeochemical variables generated by the climatological models. In our first experiments, we trained the neural network on the Copernicus reanalysis, with a resolution of about 4 km, having as target the northern Adriatic reanalysis with a resolution of about 750 m; then we tested its performances on the climate model data, with a resolution of 6 km. In future works we will use both the low-resolution datasets for the training phase.

The experiments were performed with a U-net architecture, which is based on convolutional networks, and has already been used in the literature to increase the resolution of digital images. In our experiments, we tested different training configurations (univariate and multivariate, with and without river flow data, with and without seasonality information).

Considering the reanalysis of the northern Adriatic as the data closest to the real state of the system, we have evaluated the error obtained by standard interpolation techniques and the error obtained after applying the neural network. The latter is always lower, with a more significant improvement for the biogeochemical variables. The code is written in Python using Pytorch and Pytorch Lightning and can be run also on GPUs. The same techniques used for the northern Adriatic can be reused for downscaling procedures in other geographical areas.

The evaluation of uncertainties in the estimation of indicators (e.g., hazard indicators) is a challenging task, but it is becoming more and more important for scientific applications, science communication and decision makers. Different approaches are available to tackle uncertainty, such as the distance of the simulated variables from available observations (Salon et al., 2019), or ensemble predictions based on different modelling systems or model parameters (e.g., examples from the EU SEAMLESS project). The available approaches will be integrated with the workflow developed within Return Uncertainty Task Force.

A dedicated GitHub repository has been set up to collect Task 8.3.4 tools for hazard indicators calculation and visualisation.

Keywords: marine ecosystem, biogeochemical models, hazard indicators.

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Impact-oriented indicators related to landslides: identification, collection, and harmonization of historical climate records

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In the framework of the RETURN Extended Partnership (European Union Next-GenerationEU, National Recovery and Resilience Plan – NRRP, Mission 4, Component 2, Investment 1.3 – D.D. 1243 2/8/2022, PE0000005), and specifically in the context of the DS Spoke’s initiative called “Adopt an Indicator”, the VS2 and DS Spokes proposed a collaboration act to detect (and consequently adopt) impact-oriented indicators connected to landslides, a specific typology of ground instabilities considered in VS2 Spoke. Indeed, VS2 Spoke has categorized the ground instabilities distinguishing among landslides, sinkholes, subsidence, and liquefaction. Further, landslides are distinguished considering their kinematics (i.e., slow and fast) and typologies (i.e. flows, slides, spread and slope deformations, falls and topples). Different typologies of landslides can vary their frequency and magnitude in response to climate change both in Alpine-Apennine and Coastal sectors, among the most sensitive environmental systems. Certainly, different researchers have already demonstrated a strong correlation between the variation in frequency and magnitude of slope instabilities and changes in weather-climatic conditions (Bertolini et al., 2004; Borgatti and Soldati, 2010; Alvioli et al., 2018; Pánek, 2019). For instance, changes in short-term rainfall over small catchments with landslides can be considered for assessing the impact of climatic and weather forcing.

From a hundred of Learning Examples proposed in VS2, a total of 35 impact-oriented indicators were selected, playing a relevant role in the activation of different landslides. Specifically, the indicators are treated as predisposing, preparing and triggering factors, and derived from the most common weather-climatic parameters like rainfall, temperature, snow-glacial data, wind, wave and sea data.

In this perspective, the impact is represented by landscape variation (e.g., landslide activation) due to one or more specific weather-climatic indicators (e.g., rainfall intensity). The selected indicators are derived from national or regional databases, in-situ measurements, and historical archives that have to be collected and harmonized. In this workshop, we present the state-of-art of national and local databases, their availability, and their preliminary harmonization.

Keywords: impact-oriented indicators, landslides, climate change.

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Impact-oriented hazard indicators related to climate change: adoption, calculation, and storage

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We discuss the set of climate-related hazard indicators compiled under RETURN-wide activities. Indicators are defined based on 15 Impact Sectors are: Water Resources, Soil and Land Use, Terrestrial Ecosystem, Marine Ecosystems, Alpine and Apennine Environment, Coastal Zones, Health, Forests, Agriculture and food production, Fisheries and Aquaculture, Energy, Urban Areas, Cultural Heritage, Industry and Tourism, Transport and Infrastructure. Within this framework The newly developed impact-oriented hazard indicator set within RETURN offers a versatile framework, incorporating meaningful indicators derived from diverse data sources—observations, projections, and at times, paleo-reconstructions. Under this framework, about 60 indicators have been adopted by different RETURN researchers, who committed to their calculation under current climate conditions and, when RETURN scenario will be available, for future conditions as well.

The indicators have been largely calculated by the researchers responsible for them and are being stored, along with their description and metadata, in a common space accessible to all RETURN researchers. They will eventually be published on the RETURN data platform.

Keywords: indicators, climate change, hazard.

Preliminary analysis of climate indices over Italy using dedicated climate simulations

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There is a consolidated agreement in the scientific community that Earth's climate is changing, yet the complex nature of the climate system, the systematic errors that still affect future projections, and the often-disregarded human behaviour, make it difficult to unequivocally predict the impacts of such changes at any given location and/or time. Nevertheless, the evidence is now overwhelming that the effects of climate change already

threaten the wellbeing and even the survival of human communities and of the ecosystems that so far allowed and sustained their development.

This poses the urgent question of how to design and implement effective solutions in the presence of uncertainty, making a conscious effort to recognize inherent knowledge deficiencies in the decision-making process so as to increase our level of preparedness.

Informative and reliable indicators need therefore to be derived out of a hierarchy of progressively refined climate projections, from the continental to the regional scale, and verified across all the relevant spatial scales against available observations, in order to guarantee their significance for specific local management issues, at the same time allowing for sufficient spread and for the identification of best- and worst-scenarios, so as to bound intervention options.

To this end, we have identified a set of climate indices related to daily temperature and precipitation extremes, that can serve as a reference basis for climate-change-related impact assessments, although local tailoring is liable to be needed for practical applications. This work presents the preliminary results obtained within the RETURN DS Spoke by performing and analysing dedicated climate simulations.

Keywords: climate indices.

Sub metric Late Holocene sea level fluctuations recorded by intertidal red algal rims

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The calcareous red algae *Lithophyllum byssoides* colonizes the intertidal zone of sea cliffs close to the tidal notch developing thick bioconstructions, also called ‘trottoir’. Thus, these algal bioconstructions are powerful sea level marker frequently used to model precise eustatic curves. Two algal build-ups were sampled around the Capo Caccia Mesozoic limestone peninsula (NW Sardinia, Italy) to define the late Holocene relative sea level fluctuations. The internal pattern of both rims is characterized by an in situ superposition of several generations of

L. byssoides thalli binding sand-sized clasts composed of shell fragments along with quartz and feldspars grains. Thin sections and SEM analysis confirm L. byssoides is the dominant framework builder with minor C. elongata and Serpulidae worm encrusters, competing with bioeroder as L. lithophaga. Macrostructure of both algal build-ups reveal the presence of two accretion phases separated by a well developed erosive surface. The AMS radiocarbon dates selected along the algal growth directions define that rims developed during the last 500 years and confirm the presence of two formation phases separated by a relatively long hiatus. Phase1 takes place during a warming pulse within the Little Ice Age whereas phase 2 during the modern warming Era (post 1850 AD). Moreover, the well developed erosive surface is associated with an half a meter of relative sea-level drop occurred at the acme of the Little Ice Age. Finally, our results indicate an average growth rate for the bioconstructions of about 2 mm/yr.

Keywords: Holocene, sea level, Mediterranean.

The Mediterranean Sea mean sea level from satellite altimetry and reanalysis

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It is now undoubtful that the global mean sea level has been accelerating over the last decade (IPCC report, 2023). However, local sea level can deviate substantially from global trends, making precise local estimates crucial for developing management solutions. Recent studies (Chen et al., 2017) demonstrate that global mean sea level rise is a nonstationary, nonlinear response to several climate change forcings and impacts. Reanalyses (Storto and Masina, 2017) and satellite altimetry data, available for the past 30 years, have the potential to

greatly improve the accuracy of mean sea level estimates and its understanding on both global and regional scales.

In this study, we use satellite Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) data to estimate decadal trends of the Mediterranean Sea over the past three decades: 1993-2002, 2003-2012, and 2013-2022. In addition, we use the existing Mediterranean Sea reanalysis (MEDREA24, Escudier et al., 2021) to try to explain the dynamical balance that determines the decadal trends. Consistent with the global behaviour, the Mediterranean Sea shows a SLA positive trend (2.6 ± 0.9 mm/year), which is smaller than the global (3.3 ± 0.3 mm/year, CMS Service). However, breaking down the trend in decadal components, it is found that the Mediterranean sea level has slowed down from the second decade (4.3 ± 2.0 mm/year) to the third decade (2.6 ± 3.0 mm/year). This change is particularly pronounced in the Eastern Mediterranean basin, especially in the Adriatic and Aegean Seas, where the SLA trend has become negative in the last decade (-1.3 ± 0.90 mm/year). This finding is supported by Adriatic observations from tide gauges.

The Mediterranean Sea reanalysis allows the computation of the mean sea level balance to identify the primary drivers of the observed slowdown. MEDREA24 data proved the existence of a compensation effect between the thermosteric and the halosteric sea level components, as previously demonstrated by Meli et al. (2023). Furthermore, decadal changes in the surface water budget contribute to a decrease in the mean sea level trend, primary due to an increase in evaporation that is not balanced by other component changes. This interpretation is confirmed using independent evaporation, precipitation, and river runoff datasets to calculate the surface water budget.

Within the DS8 program, this study will be the starting point for assessing the quality of the new Mediterranean Sea reanalysis currently under development.

Keywords: sea-level trend, Mediterranean Sea, water budget.

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Versatile protocol for pollutant detection in human tissue using Raman Spectroscopy and Scanning Electron Microscopy

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Climate change directly or indirectly impacts on the environmental quality (e.g., on air and water quality), for example introducing pollutants, particles or contaminants throughout the increase of extreme weather events (Bolan et al., 2024). Human interactions with exogenous agents would become more frequent over years, as highlighted by recent works analyzing the particles/fibers/pollutants presence in human tissues and their potential health impact (Peters et al., 2020; Visonà et al., 2021; Krause et al., 2024). Thus, reliable and validated procedures are needed to quantitatively detect pollutants and contaminants in human tissues.

We here introduce a step-by-step protocol for mapping, quantitatively evaluating, and chemically characterizing inorganic particles/fibers/pollutants (also considering microplastic particles) present in human tissues. In particular, the biological material obtained from biopsies is extracted from the matrix and digested, soaking them in sodium hypochlorite solution (7% active chloride) or potassium hydroxide (KOH, 1.5M), depending on the pollutants under investigation, at 60°C: 2 to 10 days are needed for a complete digestion of the biological material and the solution is then filtered on polycarbonate membranes which are finally placed inside a petri dish and dried (50°C). The digestion protocol versatility was successfully proven on lungs, ovary, bladder, ureter, lymph node, bone marrow, and prostate tissues.

For a broaden pollutant investigation, Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and Raman spectroscopy are employed for inorganic fibers/particles and microplastics imaging, respectively. A quantitative analysis of the exogenous agents, in terms of dimensions, shape/morphology and concentration per milligrams of dried biological tissue, together with their chemical investigation, enables to extract fundamental information that might be correlated to diseases, inflammations and other direct or indirect impact on tissue/human status. For example, we are currently assessing and investigating morphology and concentration of asbestos fibers in lungs and talc particles in ovarian tissues, owing to their correlation with cancerous tumor formation. On the other side, we are studying the influence of microplastic particles in placenta on cell metabolomics or as “Trojan horse” for environmental pollutants and contaminants.

Further studies would be directed towards the automatization of SEM-EDX and Raman spectroscopy, comparing the automatic procedure versus a manual one, for saving sampling and analysis time, while maintaining the quantitative and reliable evaluation.

This work is investigated in Spoke DS8 of the Return Project.

Keywords: Electron Microscopy, Raman Imaging, Pollutants in human tissue.

‘Multi-Spokes’

(VS1-DS)

Assessment of future changes on sub-daily precipitation extremes using an ensemble of convection-permitting models

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Predicting and understanding the future evolution of intense precipitation events is vital for enhancing risk management, especially in regions with mountainous terrain and urban areas vulnerable to natural disasters caused by extreme weather. Convection-permitting climate models (CPMs), which operate at kilometer-scale resolutions, offer a realistic depiction of convective precipitation mechanisms and complex terrain, thereby improving the representation of sub-daily extreme precipitation. However, the computational cost of these models limits simulations to relatively short periods (10-20 years) and restricts the number of ensemble members, which poses challenges for assessing changes in extreme events and their associated uncertainties.

In this study, we employ a novel non-asymptotic extreme value approach that has demonstrated efficacy in estimating rare return levels with lower stochastic uncertainty, even with short datasets.

Specifically, we utilize the Simplified Metastatistical Extreme Value (SMEV) distribution to project future changes in extreme sub-daily precipitation in North Italy, a region with diverse terrain encompassing both lowlands and the Italian Alps. Our analysis includes an ensemble of nine CPMs from the CORDEX-FPS project, featuring a spatial resolution of about 3 kilometers. We investigate three time periods: historical (1996-2005), near future (2041-2050), and far future (2090-2099), under the RCP8.5 emission scenario. Return levels are estimated for precipitation durations ranging from 1 to 24 hours, for different yearly exceedance probability up to 1% (100-year return period). The future changes are assessed at each grid point using a permutation test to determine the statistical significance of these changes.

Our findings reveal a general increase in extreme precipitation across the study area for all durations. The spatial patterns of significant changes differ based on duration, time period, and location. Notably, a marked increase is observed in some mountainous regions: at short durations in the Eastern Alps and across all durations in the northern Apennines. Conversely, the western part of the domain exhibits moderate and non-significant changes. By exploiting SMEV's

capability to separate the distribution of precipitation intensity from event occurrence, we analyze changes in distribution parameters to interpret the shifts in return levels, considering alterations in thermodynamics (linked to temperature and water vapor content) and atmospheric dynamics.

These findings offer critical insights for quantifying and understanding future changes in precipitation extremes. This information is beneficial for stakeholders involved in risk management and the design of adaptation measures.

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Keywords: extreme precipitation, climate change, convection-permitting models.